

MEGA-SPORTING EVENTS AND THE INFLUENCE
ON INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS:
A POSITIONING CASE FOR QATAR

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Abstract

Mega-sporting events have been criticised for some of the negative socio-economic and human rights implications they often facilitate within different host nations. In this thesis, the relationship between the development of these mega-sporting events and the necessity for human rights protection was closely and carefully examined and evaluated. Focusing specifically on Qatar's hosting of the 2022 FIFA World Cup, the following research identified and explored both the human rights implications of mega-sporting events and the efforts the government of Qatar has undertaken in protecting the rights of its migrant workers and whether that has silenced their critics. The study came in response to previous allegations made by several international watchdog institutions and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), including Amnesty International, who have claimed that the peninsula's preparations for the World Cup reportedly infringe on the human and labour rights of its construction workers. As such, the following research carefully explored some of these claims surrounding the organisation of the event, but also closely evaluated Qatar's comprehensive efforts towards the preservation, protection, and continued development of its migrant-population construction worker industry and assessed Qatar's approach to countering these claims.

A study of the 2022 World Cup, scheduled to take place in Qatar, provided an incredibly important and significantly valuable opportunity for still largely unexplored academic and theoretical research, not only because of the country's unique socio-economic make-up, but also because of the cultural trajectories that shape the peninsula's society and economy. As such, a careful study of the country's preparations for the event helped shed much-needed light on the intricacies, complexities, and challenges of human rights. Much like in the remainder of the Arabian Gulf,

Qatar's economic development is highly dependent on a population of skilled and unskilled migrant workers, who not only make up 88.4% of the population, but whose contributions to the nation's rapid growth have often proven indispensable. As a result of the nation's unique demographic, economic, and socio-cultural profile, a study of the nation's experience in preparing for the world's largest and most popular sporting event is not only crucially important but is also valuable in terms of its assessment of the relationship between the trajectories of human rights and the coordination of a largely immigrant-based migrant population.

The case study was conducted via qualitative methods with quantitative features: it combined content analysis (of Qatar's laws, policies, strategies, and other normative approaches) with interviews conducted with twenty-six individuals from a number of different spaces (construction workers, public officials, and private sector representatives) within the 2022 World Cup preparation process.

As part of the research process, a comprehensive literature review was conducted examining several different sources that evaluate the relationship between mega-sporting events and human rights, including international human rights, and international labour laws. By closely committing to examining several international and local sources throughout the literature review process, several gaps were found, which have encouraged the following thesis' continued development and theoretical basis. This study finds strengths and challenges in the way mega-sporting events have been evaluated, both in terms of the treatment of workers, as well as the general promotion of human dignity. Throughout the following research, I not only contributed an important research-based assessment to the growing body of theory examining the relationship between mega-sporting events and human rights, but I have also made an original contribution to the research on policy and practice of labour laws in Qatar. Following the scheduled 2022 World Cup,

a further evaluation and assessment of the nation are strongly encouraged to trace Qatar's progression and sustainability of reforms that are now in place. This study provides evidence that mega-sporting events can be a helpful tool in measuring the host country's compliance with international human rights in terms of its commitment to the protection of its workers.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

This introductory chapter sets the groundwork of this thesis by elaborating on the study's background, purpose, and its aims and objectives. While the study's background revolves around mega-sporting events, its general purpose is centred on Qatar's efforts to ensure the protection of human rights and migrant workers within the country's construction industry. The study also possesses three primary objectives, which are divided into several different categories and sub-categories. Beyond these components of the thesis, the introduction also lays the groundwork for the study's significance and its theoretical framework, as well as details on the case study and the target group (Qatar's 2022 World Cup).

1.2 Background

The general focus of this research revolves around the various efforts taken by the government of Qatar in ensuring the general wellbeing and safety of its migrant workers as it prepares for the 2022 World Cup. Mega-sporting events highlight global attention at international level, as many nations compete to host these events because of the benefits to the host nation. As a result, international bodies pay specific attention to the preparation and management of the events. Qatar has gone one step further by highlighting the treatment of workers involved in hosting nations. Accordingly, for several years Human Rights Watch (HRW) institutions have been consistently documenting the various forms of abuses linked to mega-sporting events. They have noted the disconcerting human rights violations that have been reported (World Reports, 2015). These mega-sporting events range from the Football World Cup, the Olympic Games, and the International Volleyball Tournaments. The HRW (2016) pointed out numerous cases where human rights violations surfaced during these events. Several reports from Amnesty International, the Institute for Human Rights, and the HRW have provided broad coverage of mega-sporting events and how

these events perpetuated the abuse of people's freedom. These reports illustrate that severe abuses arose consistently when these mega-sporting events were awarded to countries with high records of human rights abuses (Amnesty International, 2012, p. 3). Amnesty International (2012) indicated that, following the Beijing and the Sochi Olympics, numerous allegations of wrongdoing prompted human rights protection to be added to the contract that countries must sign (p. 3). The Institute for Human Rights and Business (IHRB, 2013) notes that a total of ten workers died, and 17,000 more complained of exploitation at the height of the Beijing Olympics (p. 3).

The HRW (2008) highlighted that immigrant construction workers who worked in the construction of New Beijing were highly exploited (p. 2). Workers endured unsafe working conditions, were denied fair wages, and were not offered health insurance or provided medical services. Consequently, mega-sporting events journalists continually seek to provide coverage on these critical topics, including gender discrimination and the jailing of activists trying to raise awareness about these types of abuse (HRW, 2016, p. 4). For example, Beijing residents were forcefully evicted from their homes, leaving them homeless, because of the Olympic Games. Several other mega-sporting events follow a similar pattern including London, in 2012, and the Glasgow Commonwealth Games in 2014 (Horne, 2016, p. 8). Further, Horne (2014) illustrated the seriousness of the issue, stating that in preparation for the 2008 Beijing Games, Olympic Games contractors not only forced 300,000 residents to be displaced from their homes but were then actively recruiting the same exploited residents to construct complex infrastructures. In addition, the contractors denied workers fundamental human rights, forcing them to endure unfavourable working conditions.

Matheson and Finkel (2012, p. 33) further note that several human rights cases of abuse were associated with the staging of mega-sporting events. Housing rights were continuously violated, especially for those in economically vulnerable communities who were forcefully relocated to allow space for the staging of the events. Matheson and Finkel (2012, p. 34) report that these violations were present in different Olympic Games in other countries. Critics emphasised that one of the more serious human rights violations is allowing human trafficking during the events. It is commonly found that during mega-sporting events, lax policies and ineffective forms of regulation can potentially lead to increased occurrences of human trafficking, and in other instances, it may be argued that a motivation of the visiting attendees may be actively seeking such services throughout their trip.

Following the increase in reported cases of human rights transgressions, a special session was convened in Monaco in 2014. President Thomas Bach chaired the International Olympic Committee to develop recommendations on rules that could be adopted to mitigate these concerns regarding human rights violations. The rules ensure that every step of the hosting process, including bidding, preparation, and staging of mega-sporting events, should operate within a larger framework that respects and upholds human rights understandings. These decrees were regarded as 'Olympic Agenda 2020', with a recommendation to make the reforms part of the contracts with future cities interested and willing to host the events.

First, a new method of invitation was launched, which encourages the countries involved to present their suitable Olympic projects and best match their environmental plans, economic gains, and long-term sport-related objectives, among many others. Secondly, the Olympic charter was revised to strengthen issues related to human rights. Among some of these issues are the 'Six

Fundamental Principle of Olympism’ and included principles on non-discrimination in the Olympic charter (HRW, 2016, p. 23). Changes were integrated based on the recommendations of the HRW, and contract terms that call for the respect of human dignity and ban discrimination, were implemented across the spectrum (IHRB, 2016, p. 4).

As a member of the Human Rights Council (HRC), Qatar has always played an incredibly important role, both domestically, regionally, and globally, in ensuring that human rights are safeguarded in all its political, economic, infrastructural, and socio-cultural engagements. Nevertheless, new challenges are cited relating to human rights infractions during mega-sporting events, raising concerns about the implementation of human rights initiatives, health, and the welfare of construction workers (Worden, 2017, p. 6). These concerns influence the perception of Qatar and its ability to host the event. Such examples illustrate the need to procure more significant commitment and demonstrate more ways of safeguarding the rights of people, both those working at the mega-sporting events site and those otherwise in the country. The changes, notably those related to the environment, health, labour, and other policies forbidding indiscriminate arrest, forced labour sentencing without trial, and the protection of freedoms, have made human rights requirements more explicit (Fox, 2016, p. 3). The focus on the protection of human dignity during these events should include all these aspects.

The International Federation of Association Football (FIFA), the sport’s global governing body, has received criticism for failing to effectively and meaningfully approach some of the issues regarding the human rights violations of its participatory nations, many of which are directly related to the wellbeing of immigrant workers. FIFA is expected to evaluate suitable host countries, efficiently consider the many issues involved, and impose clear and strict measures (Gibson, 2016). In the recent years leading up to the scheduled 2022 World Cup, Qatar has repeatedly come

under the spotlight for the alleged human rights violations of its immigrant workers (Gibson, 2016).

According to Grix (2015), Qatar has an unobstructed vision for its future, having money derived from oil revenues (p. 13). The government of Qatar wants to create a well-rounded dimension to diversify income from various sectors rather than depend on oil export revenue. Qatar is now developing sport, finance, and entertainment sectors, among many other industries (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 23). Qatar is strategically planning economic policies focused on increasing private and foreign investment in sectors such as energy.

As part of the 'Qatar National Vision 2030,' an excess of USD 17 billion worth of investments was injected due to the economic diversification policies between 2010 and 2015 (Qatar National Development Strategy 2011-2016, p.17). Hosting a significant mega-sporting event will expand Qatar's global outreach by attracting investors worldwide, and by observing Qatar's capabilities first-hand they may be more willing to invest in Qatar's diverse economic sectors. However, these investors will only be willing to invest if the country has well-established measures to ensure human rights are respected, and Qatar currently exemplifies the best standard because other countries have failed. Qatar can illustrate its capabilities and humanity during its preparations for the 2022 World Cup.

The HRW (2016) argues that globally no country has been credited with a perfect record for human rights protection (HRW, p. 7). The Human Rights Report illustrates that Qatar is facing some criticisms of human rights abuse, especially regarding mega-sporting events in the preparations for the 2022 World Cup. So far, however, the country is making considerable progress in employing measures that will ensure that the rights of people are respected to comply with the

regulations and protocols recommended by the international community (HRW, 2016, p. 7). Furthermore, as will be argued in chapter five, large portions of the criticisms facing the peninsula are not wholly based on evidence-based fact, but is rather fuelled by discriminatory stereotypical perceptions, both of the Middle East as a region, as well as of Qatar as a relatively conservative Islamic nation.

During these global mega-sporting events, Qatar has an opportunity to step up and demonstrate to the international community its genuine progress on human rights. Qatar is willing to illustrate that it can be a premier destination for world sport events, unlike other states involved in human rights violations. Consequently, the world is watching to see what Qatar will do to uphold fundamental human rights as it prepares to host global citizens on a larger scale. Qatar argues it will exemplify it has taken adequate measures to ensure the safety and well-being of the people who will attend the events, regardless of their countries of origin or their faith.

This research, therefore, aims to investigate and identify the changes that Qatar has implemented in order to understand and see if there is indeed evidence of the aforementioned points by the government of Qatar. This study examines whether Qatar has only implemented a pragmatic temporary change to secure a positive impact for the upcoming event, or a long-term ideological change to influence others in the region. Furthermore, Qatar's metrics will illustrate to a larger global community how mega-sporting events can be enjoyed as a force for advancing human rights compliance and human resource issues relating to workplace, health, and safety standards.

1.3 Thesis Statement

Several of the host nations associated with mega-sporting events have historically and consistently infringed fundamental human rights. In several recent mega-sporting events' preparation and construction phases, human rights violations have taken place. With the advent of the internet,

and especially of social media platforms, these human rights violations have been broadcast to larger global audiences (Institute for Human Rights and Business, 2013). According to Grix and Lee (2013), human rights violations have taken place in China, which hosted the 2008 Olympic Games, South Africa, which hosted the 2010 World Cup finals, India, who hosted the Commonwealth Games in 2010, and Brazil, who hosted the 2014 World Cup. These event organisers enacted a number of domestic and economic policies, either directly or indirectly, that led to housing violations through the forceful eviction of vulnerable communities, sexual exploitation, and the abuse of children's rights.

Qatar was specifically cited for exposing migrant construction workers to harsh working conditions during its preparation for the 2022 World Cup, in reports from several different independent international watchdogs, including Amnesty International, the Institute for Human Rights, and HRW, amongst many others. The following study, however, aims to explore Qatar's ethical and sustainable approach to mega-sporting event management. More specifically, it aims to explore, through qualitative means, the specific mechanisms through which the nation has ensured the continued wellbeing, safety, and health of its construction workers.

1.4 Purpose of the Study

This research examines the various efforts initiated by the government of Qatar and the private sector to ensure that human rights are protected, that violations are investigated, and whether these standards have been translated into normative approaches such as national laws, policies, and strategies to ensure compliance post the mega-sporting event. Sport plays a leading role in regional and world integration and is not explicitly driven by political or economic demands. Qatar also aims to use the World Cup 2022 mega-sporting event to encourage tourism in

the country and change the perception of many people who believe that the region is a centre for terrorism. It will do this by promoting sport events.

1.5 Aim and Objectives

A. Aim

This study aims to critically evaluate the trajectories and elements associated with mega-sporting events in relation to the potential for human rights violations, by closely evaluating and examining the case of Qatar's hosting of the 2022 World Cup. The thesis aims to identify the policies and reforms, both governmental and non-governmental, and their effectiveness in the employment sector that Qatar has implemented in the treatment of workers working on mega-projects. In addition, the importance of the reforms on human rights protection and how other host nations can replicate the same beyond the 2022 World Cup.

B. Objectives

There are three specific objectives to the thesis, all of which are centred on the relationship between mega-sporting events and the need to protect against potential human rights violations. They are as follows:

1. Evaluate the policies and reforms of Qatar, both governmental and non-governmental, in protecting human rights.
2. Analyse the effectiveness of the measures put in place by Qatar to ensure that human rights are protected.
3. Evaluate people's perceptions on the importance and effectiveness of the reforms, their applicability after the 2022 World Cup finals, and how others can embrace these best practices in the region.

By design, this study aims to broaden awareness about the importance of mega-sporting events as a promoter of human rights. The 2022 World Cup scheduled to take place in Qatar has generated significant reactions from different people. Gibson (2012) notes that the nation styles itself as the most modern and progressive Gulf state. The key issues surrounding the debate are focused on human rights. The Middle East region has been the epitome of criticism regarding treatment of workers. Immigrant workers face challenges when they travel to work in some of the Middle Eastern countries. Most of these immigrant workers are from developing nations like India and other Asian countries. Immigrants are recruited as a source of cheap labour, given that they are paid low wages in exchange for hard work. Their working conditions are deplorable, with some employers failing to provide basic life insurance policies or even health insurance coverage to seek medical care. As a result, this study examines various aspects of human rights promotion, using global sport events as the backdrop, and provides a well-rounded evaluation of Qatar's first experience with hosting the World Cup event. This study offers an important assessment with regard to how mega-sporting events require comprehensive forms of planning, structuring, and monitoring, all of which should be developed in line with the safety, security and wellbeing of the event's planners, workers, and attendees.

Beutler (2008) highlights that the international community has increasingly recognised and drawn on the power of sport as a way of promoting global peace, sustainable development, and the overall protection of vulnerable communities. Therefore, the 2022 World Cup in Qatar acts as a sort of litmus test for examining human rights promotion and better treatment of workers, given that the event attracts world viewership. For instance, behind the recently concluded Russian 2018 World Cup, immigrant workers from Central Asia were recruited in large numbers to construct stadiums. They were among the many migrant workers involved in the menial jobs across Russia

to ensure a smooth flow of the events (Kowalski, 2018). Unfortunately, they faced ethnic profiling and police harassment, amongst several other forms of reported mistreatment.

1.6 Research Questions

The research question is one of the essential parts of any study. Research questions should be specific, appropriately complex, and relevant to a social or scholarly issue to guide the research to be precise and maintain the subject of the study. The research guides readers on how to carry out a similar study. According to Tashakkori and Creswell (2007, p. 209), research questions play an essential role in the investigations and further explorations of the study topic. Furthermore, the aims and objectives of the study generated the inquiry. Thus, the questions guided the study to achieve the objectives. The research question and sub-question are essentially aimed at translating and converting the aforementioned objectives into specific, measurable, and potentially attainable question and answer formats.

This thesis is guided by one research question and one sub-research question, which are as follows:

Research question: How important and effective are some of the reforms that the Government of Qatar is trying to put in place in ensuring that human rights are protected?

Sub-research question: Are the reforms translated into normative approaches, i.e., national laws, policies, legislations, and strategies, to ensure post-game compliance and post-2022 applicability?

1.7 Significance of the Study

The significance of this research is to provide a case study which shows evidence of the achievements and positive efforts that have been put in place by Qatar regarding human rights issues in mega-sporting events in response to global criticism in the media. After winning the bid to host the 2022 World Cup events, the country has repeatedly come under criticism from various organisations and the international media for matters related to human rights. Many governments

and agencies worldwide have continuously criticised Qatar for violating human rights by exposing immigrant workers to unsuitable working conditions. The research question framework and subsequent research uncovered that much of the criticism is due to a specific lack of awareness about Qatar. Much of the negative perspective is rooted in historical and cultural bias. Critics fail to address the positive measures that Qatar has put in place to protect human rights. Despite the previous existence of these violations, several reforms have been put in place by the government to ensure that these rights are not violated. As well as this, several different governmental reports have been released on the reforms that have been put in place.

As such, this research has covered various state reports and interviewed several state officials and workers to cover this gap by making the information available and influencing policy. Therefore, this study aims to provide concrete evidence through primary research that involves primary data from Qatari officials, as well as secondary data that, in spite of accusations against the country, show that there are substantial government-led efforts to protect human rights.

By identifying human rights-related issues in Middle Eastern states, the study has sought to expose how mega-sporting events could be used to bridge the gap between countries' management schemes for large-scale events, and the protection of human rights. The 2022 World Cup will be a prominent event that will attract millions of viewers and thousands of fans who will travel to the hosting nation to witness the event. As a result, their safety must be guaranteed through the host country showing and upholding its commitment to promoting human rights. Through the workers working on mega-sporting events stadiums and developments, the study examines their treatment in line with the development of human dignity. A systematic and thematic analysis of the interview data with the workers informed this part of the study. Key themes that emerged from the interviews were issues such as the promotion of workers' health through the food supplied to

them, health insurance policies, and the provision of safety equipment while working, among other things. For instance, FIFA recommends constant monitoring of working conditions (FIFA, 2017). The international standards include a safe working environment with workers' health being actively monitored. The employer should provide safety equipment. Health inspectors should also maintain routine checks to ensure that the workers are safe and do not acquire diseases from the work environment. The inspections should be held at the construction sites regularly, at least once every three months. Discrepancies from the workers are noted, and the companies are compelled to work on such issues. Since the entire world will be watching Qatar prepare for the event, this will help us understand the impacts of such spectatorship on promoting people's rights through Qatar's employment of domestic and foreign workers. Moreover, the study is essential to highlighting other benefits of mega-sporting events, including regional integration and development, cultural understanding, promotion of tourism, and trade. Other factors include stability in the region, among other social, political, and economic benefits associated with mega-sporting events, as witnessed in the London Olympics games (Grix, 2012). The watchful eye of the media and the actions of other nations in promoting the event before it takes place, puts pressure on Qatar to act to protect workers' rights and show the world they deal with such issues.

1.8 Theoretical Framework

As states are brought together to participate in the 2022 Qatar World Cup, the research will show that sport is an essential component in the promotion of human rights and general societal wellbeing.

Accordingly, this study employs the concepts of the international event and the promotion of human rights, to underpin its theoretical background in formulating the critical understanding of mega-sporting events and their role in establishing international unity and corporation. There

are different global sport events such as Olympic Games, athletics, international football, and other sports encouraged worldwide. The primary role of these sport events is to foster international co-operation in various aspects and exchanges at different levels (Ang, Isar, &, Mar 2015, p. 367).

In most cases, these events attract global attention, thereby encouraging the host nation to promote human rights. The events play a significant role in advancing gender equality in different areas such as employment and governance. The international community requires those involved to take an active role in establishing equity and promoting human rights and dignity. The research utilises sport events as a watchdog and promoter of international cooperation and human rights across the host countries. In this case, the research focuses on Qatar as a Middle Eastern State and pays particular attention to the negative picture that has been painted regarding the region. Thus, Qatar forms an essential backdrop for more closely understanding the intricate complexities of human rights in association with infrastructural growth and a mega-sporting event. This study also provides a perspective, which is perceiving Qatar's role in international human rights contexts, including international agreements of human rights, labour rights and migrant rights, as well as Qatar's participation in multilateral frameworks within international organisations such as the International Organization for Migration (I.O.M.) and the International Labour Organization (I.L.O.).

1.9 Case Study

Sport is an essential part of human lives, and sports have been practiced for many years in different forms. They function as a catalyst for bringing people together and influencing their understanding of each other. Sport has taken a key role in bringing people together, sharing cultures, solving disputes, and promoting peaceful coexistence in the modern world. Global sport events foster international relations and economic growth. As a result, most countries take pride in hosting

the events. As part of the international community, Qatar has been awarded the chance to host the coveted World Cup event planned to take place in 2022. However, the pressure that results from managing such events has resulted in some countries using unacceptable means of labour to facilitate fast growth in creating the proper infrastructure. As a result, the global community has expectations of a certain standard. It expects those staging the events to conduct themselves properly, especially when dealing with human rights. Thus, this study is focused on evaluating the measures that have been put in place by Qatar as a nation as it seeks to host the tournament. The research will assess the perspectives of the government and private sector as they both have a permanent role in realising the event's success.

The potential success of the event will, as previously suggested, have a range of short and long-term advantages, many of which will help improve Qatar's long-term regional and international position, both as a viable economic marketplace worthy of international investments, as well as a regional hub of sporting influence. Much like in the instances of all other mega-sporting events of this calibre, the 2022 World Cup will also provide Qatar with a sense of increased global soft power, which may arguably provide it with a more strengthened political, economic, and sociocultural standing moving forward. Nye attests that soft power can depend on three factors: 'its culture (in places where it is attractive to others), its political values (when it lives up to them at home and abroad), and its foreign policies (when others see them as legitimate and having moral authority).' (Nye, 2011, p. 84). It is wrong to treat soft power as a cultural power because 'it is a mistake to equate soft power with the cultural resources that sometimes help produce it. (Held and Archibugi, 2004, p. 127). Soft power can be achieved through cultural practices, but can also be achieved through public diplomacy, solidarity, charity, international discourses, or speeches (including via journalists). Nye further argues that there is a mutual give and takes between states' interests and

soft power made through diplomacy and scholars and their interest. For instance, soft power will grow because of the number of people willing to study a country's language at language institutes. In the context of Qatar, soft power can grow because the country is seen as a host of a cultural event (more specifically, the mega-sporting event FIFA World Cup 2022). Consequently, it is paramount for the study to evaluate how this success will be achieved and how it can be replicated in other countries.

Through hosting the 2022 World Cup finals, Qatar wants to benefit from being framed as the 'regional sport hub' to secure other mega-sporting events and improve its economy through global tourism (Flowers, 2017, p. 6). The event organisations, including FIFA and the International Olympic Committee (IOC), receive pressure from the international community to ensure that countries staging these events embrace and ensure that human rights are not violated (Maennig, 2012, p. 16). In this regard, for Qatar to be awarded a chance of hosting other noteworthy events by the event organisers, it must first prove to the world that it has put in place sufficient measures to protect and safeguard human rights (Cotton and Welden, 2014 p. 22). The world has been exposed to many events of terror and witnessed the encroachment of human rights. These infractions have created fear among people, and unless their faith is restored, many will opt not to attend the global sport event. The fear of having only a few fans attend negatively impacts the event's sponsors, as they pay attention to the event's turnout. Any advertiser will target a considerable population; hence, low turnout discourages them from investing their resources. The event aims to bring people together, but that will be difficult if human rights violations increase. Accordingly, the events promoter and organising committee should strive to strike a balance and promote and restore faith among the fans to avoid the issues of a boycott. In this view, Qatar must show its commitment to the world to ensure that safety is guaranteed. This forms the basis for why Qatar is concerned with

ensuring that it creates a positive image by providing reforms to its laws that will ensure that human rights are respected.

Choosing an appropriate research design can help ensure that the study's methodologies, and theoretical/practical applications are effectively aligned with the research's general objectives and goals. The choices made influence the outcome considering that the study relies on the data collected and analysed. It is impractical to use the wrong design and expect to get the correct answers. Accordingly, it was essential to select the right research design and methodology that would be practical and offer accurate information that can be used to develop specific knowledge in the areas of the study. A qualitative approach is a suitable approach when dealing with the data. The study aimed to contribute to and extend the theory supporting mega-sporting events to promote cohesion and integration in a region. As previously suggested, mega-sporting events such as the 2022 World Cup can also create environments within which increased international collaboration.

Considering that it was impractical to factor all these issues using primary data alone, the research opted to use secondary information as the main basis of data then supplement that with a series of twenty-six qualitative interviews. The secondary data was attained by evaluating a mix of scholarly journals, books, magazines, newspapers, and government policy documents, government reports, and other web sources. The interpretation and the context were suitable for this scenario in that the qualitative design employs observation through inductive means. The observations are then used to contribute to and extend theory and influence government policy. As a result of the process, the research goals were achieved through exploration and discovery.

1.10 Justification of the Study Population

The importance and potential application of a research assessment is almost completely associated with its degree of legitimacy and coherence, both of which are greatly impacted by the validity, soundness, and relevance of its collected data and findings (Duffy & Chenail, 2009). As such, it was essential to have the right population to represent the situation on the ground correctly. Considering that the study takes place in Qatar, the population was selected from the study region. Among those in the study included the workers in the projects, government officials, and several members operating within the private sector. The selection was based on several factors, including a complete perspective of the situation and an appropriate representation. The number of the study population was defined by factors such as suitable representation and a varied range of opinions. By relying on these underlying frameworks of assessment, the research study was capable of providing an honest, reliable, and legitimate understanding of the issues and challenges associated with the research topic.

The first set of interviewees are the workers in the field, those who experience first-hand the impact of poor treatment and unsuitable working environments. The justification is that through random sampling of the workers, the information collected is well balanced. Government officials were the second group of interviewees that were sampled and provided essential knowledge regarding the government's position for the case study. The private sector was the third group of stakeholders interviewed and they provided an understanding of their role as stakeholders in the bidding for, and delivering, the mega-sporting event as funders or sponsors. Their perspective on how they feel about the treatment of employees and how they were able to influence, was an important voice for the study since they may be in a position to influence the government in ensuring human rights were adhered to. Since members of the government and the private sector

were selected depending on name and position, purposive sampling was used. Firstly, the history of the interviewee was studied, based on their essential function in the government/private sector in different capacities. Then their knowledge of the subject was examined in the first interaction, explaining the orientation of the research, and they were informed what would be required of them. Through these groups, the study population is justified as including key informants who helped produce the data. Their role in the study was critical in gathering information that represents the actual situation in the field. Their acceptance of being involved in the study was recorded in the consent form. They were provided with the form at the beginning of the study. They were reminded of their rights during participation and that if they wished to leave the study, they were at liberty to do so. Once they accepted, the information was then recorded, and the privacy of the data was guaranteed.

1.11 Target Group

Once the background, the importance of the study, and the guiding principles were established, the study population was identified. Criteria for selecting the participants were also determined to ensure that the population represents the people working on the World Cup developments and the situation on the ground. The essential criteria were to select a group of workers, government officials, and officials from the private sector. The workers were interviewed on construction sites. This allowed them to have an opportunity to give details when they were not being monitored.

Additionally, the research maintains the anonymity of those interviewed. The workers were allowed to do a phone interview to maintain confidentiality and protect their identity. Moreover, the workers are the direct recipients of the actions; the employers are the ones who instigate the effects, while the government comes in as the principal balance between the workers and their

employers. Therefore, the research will clearly show the importance of each category and how those involved in specific groups are critical in establishing a clear picture of the situation. The justification of these categories is based on distinct aspects, for example the contribution of each category of the participants. Each group was selected because it provided a particular perspective and specific data that will offer insights on the subject under investigation. In this view, this process was done systematically, but some groups needed more time as each group had its challenges, and it was not possible to access all the participants at the same time. Thus, this study employed different approaches, such as sending emails to those selected to find suitable times to engage them in interviews. A schedule was made to meet with the person or the group for the interview process.

1.12 Summary of Findings and Conclusion of Study

Since the end of 2010, when Qatar initially won the bid to host the 2022 FIFA World Cup, a number of allegations from the international press and several NGOs, such as Amnesty International, claimed that the nation has infringed on the human rights of its migrant construction workers. With these allegations in mind, this thesis attempts to evaluate and develop a well-researched and effectively explained evaluation and assessment on Qatar's different policies, reforms, and measures meant to protect the human rights of its workers. This was made possible by facilitating a critical discourse analysis, relating to Qatar's laws, policies, strategies, and reforms. It was also dependent on the qualitative findings of its conducted interviews, of which the sampling consisted of twenty-six participants in the 2022 FIFA World Cup work plan. The findings are measured in several percentage values throughout the thesis, and they showed that respondents believed that specifically measurable reforms proved immensely valuable.

The interviews rated respondents' opinions on the level of Qatar's particular measures to protect human rights. The steps discussed included: the workers' welfare forums, capacity-building exercises, inspections, public reporting/transparency, the grievance hotline, and compliance and audit systems. The overall rating of the reforms was enormously appreciated at 80% agreement to protect human rights.

Additionally, respondents could also add comments allowing for qualitative analysis. The interviews show that respondents tended to comment more when something positive was mentioned. However, disbeliefs and challenges were discussed briefly but not described in lengthy comments like the positive ones. This may be because of their steadfast belief in the positive effects of the reforms. Still, it could also show reluctance to freely discuss the challenges for fear of repercussion even though anonymity was completely guaranteed. However, the findings illustrate a generally positive opinion of Qatar's reforms and approach to mega-sporting events preparation. From the interviews alone, it can be deduced that in the respondents' perception, Qatar's reforms fully protect human rights or diminish the possibility of human rights abuses (with no overall rating measure rated at below 80%, and one measure placed at 100% agreement).

Qatar introduced new measures to protect the human rights of its workers, such as the workers' welfare forums, capacity-building exercises, inspections, updating the working and living conditions (cooling technology and renovation of accommodations), reporting exercises, the grievance hotline, and compliance and audit systems including four-tier systems. The nation's World Cup body, the Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, published the 'Worker Welfare Standards' in 2014. This is a significant achievement as the standards are applicable to the country's construction workers. Those are detailed in chapter five, and the main conclusion is that each measure has positive aspects and challenges. Nevertheless, there is room for improvement,

although the steps are seen as a ‘first’ in Qatar’s history regarding their treatment of construction workers (migrant workers). Some of the recommended improvements that can be deduced from this thesis are detailed below.

Health measures have been put in place. Every accommodation/worksite with more than 100 workers has a permanent doctor available, together with a facility appropriately equipped to respond to medical emergencies. But, of course, the medical facility is not fully prepared to respond to chronic diseases and other health issues that need long-term treatment. For that, the workers are to be transported to a hospital as the Workers’ Charter stipulates. However, the medical facility responds to work emergencies such as injuries, fatigue, and so forth. It is important to note that there is no permanent doctor in places with fewer than 100 workers, but there is a first aid officer.

By identifying human rights-related issues in Middle Eastern states, the study has sought to expose how mega-sporting events could be used to bridge the gap between countries’ management schemes for large-scale events, and the protection of human rights. There are three specific objectives to the thesis, all of which are centred on the relationship between mega-sporting events and the need to protect against potential human rights violations. They include the evaluation of policies and reforms of Qatar, both governmental and non-governmental, in protecting human rights, the analysis of the effectiveness of the measures put in place by Qatar to ensure that human rights are protected, and the assessment of people’s perceptions on the importance and effectiveness of the reforms and their applicability after the 2022 World Cup finals, and how others can embrace these best practices in the region. By design, the study aims to broaden awareness about the importance of mega-sporting events as a promoter of human rights.

1.13 Overview of Chapters

This thesis is based on six chapters as follows:

- **Chapter 1: Introduction.** The introductory chapter includes information about the thesis statement, the purpose of the study, the aims and objectives, the research questions, significance of the study, theoretical framework, the case study of the thesis, the justification of the study population, and the target group employed.
- **Chapter 2: Background on Events, Sport, and Qatar.** This chapter provides contextual information for the research study. Furthermore, this chapter offers a general discussion about events, mega-sporting events, sport events, Qatar's role in sport events, and sport sponsorships. Additionally, the chapter elaborates on Qatar's multi-cultural demographic background and the role of migrants in Qatar's society, especially in employment.
- **Chapter 3: Literature Review.** The literature review is based on human rights theories, including labour rights, migrant rights, and how human rights are intervening in positive or negative ways in policies and the organisation of mega-sporting events. It also elaborates on Qatar's benefits and challenges in hosting the 2022 World Cup mega-sporting event (benefits include: the establishment of regional unity, framing of the image, regional agreement, and economic benefits; while challenges include: the financial dimension and high preparation costs, legacy planning, legal dimension, and the role of event owners). Finally, it provides a perspective which analyses Qatar's role in international human rights contexts, including international agreements of human rights, labour rights, and migrant rights, as well as Qatar's participation in multilateral frameworks within international organisations such as the International Organization for Migration (I.O.M.) and the International Labour Organization (I.L.O.).

- **Chapter 4: Research Methodology.** This chapter details my methodological approach, the methods employed, the study area description, methods, research design, data gathering, data analysis, ethical considerations, and thesis limitations.
- **Chapter 5: Findings and Analysis.** This chapter highlights the reforms that the government of Qatar has put in place to diminish the probability of human rights violations and increase workers' rights. It is constructed on several sections combining critical analysis and survey-based data on areas such as the *Kafala* system (meaning Qatar's employment system for migrants), the working conditions of employees working on construction sites, the payment and reduced number of working hours, cooling technology, accommodation facilities, the establishment of the workers' charter, welfare and health regulations, compliance and audit procedures, transparency and reporting procedures, as well as information on stakeholders, contractors, and individual perceptions of surveyed persons.
- **Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations.** This chapter includes the overview, recommendations, and contribution to knowledge (via human rights theory). It is also an opportunity to consider the future of research on mega-sporting events and Qatar's human rights reforms path. This chapter also identifies the World Cup 2022 stakeholders.

The next chapter will therefore provide information that contextualises the research. It will discuss the background knowledge on events, mega-sporting events, sport events, sport ownership, and detail Qatar's approach towards sport, its multi-cultural demography, and employment data for Qatari and non-Qatari employees.

Chapter 2: Background on Events, Sport, and Qatar

2.2 Introduction

It has only been 30 years since the International Olympic Committee (IOC) abandoned its amateur-only policy and made professional athletes eligible for participation. Professionalisation quickly followed on several other levels, with the intention to reach its full commercial potential (Zimbalist, 2016, p. 22). After emerging from IOC, FIFA also evolved 'from a sort of gentlemen's club to large corporation and modern enterprise' (Homburg, 2008, p. 34).

This chapter focuses on the importance of events at large, what differentiates a mega-sporting event from a simple event, and the diverse range of benefits for organising events, sport events, and mega-sporting events. This chapter also sets the scene on Qatar's role in sport events and sport sponsorships. Additionally, the chapter elaborates on Qatar's multi-cultural demographic background and the role of migrants in Qatar's society, especially in employment.

2.3 Significance of Events

The word 'event' has been used to describe a wide range of facts that are happening. The Oxford Dictionary presents an 'event' as 'a thing that happens, especially something important' (Oxford Dictionary). The Cambridge Dictionary attests that an event is 'anything that happens' (Cambridge Dictionary). Both dictionaries exemplify the word event in several contexts, such as sport events, social events, tragic events, fundraising events, historical events, adverse events, cultural events, art events, gala events, charity events, celebratory events, and so forth.

If asked why people need events, many will have different answers: children and teenagers seek amusement and playfulness; adults seek a space setting after work and see it as a socialising area; companies see events as a place to promote their brands and markets; states seek to increase their national economy and international prominence, amongst others. Events have existed since

ancient times, with the first Olympic games estimated to have taken place in 776 BC, Greek theatre plays at the Acropolis around the fifth century, and gladiator competitions in the Roman Empire.

Events can be a significant attraction for tourists, and an enriching cultural life makes a country a potential destination for a holiday. Tourism and management studies reveal that events, no matter their nature, have a significant impact on marketing the country and attracting tourists for economic purposes (Raj and Musgrave, 2009; Spirou, 2011; Smith, 2012). Such events may include sport competitions. There is a wide range of individual selections such as cycling, football, marathons, gymnastics, tennis, basketball, wrestling, alongside others, and regional and global competitions such as the Olympics and Paralympics. Getz noted 'events are a major component of sport tourism,' (2003, p. 49).

Events can also mean concerts and song contests, circuses, theatre, opera, filmmaking, and other creative activities. Recently, political and professional events (or events focused on knowledge-sharing) such as medical conferences, private sector/multi-national companies' events, Ted Talks, and international organisations' conferences have also contributed to attracting tourists and transforming a professional setting into an event, attracting a different type of tourist: the international press, international investors, and competitors, which can be called 'professional tourists' (Wise and Harris, 2017). Events are strategically chosen for enterprise and entrepreneurial opportunities where they are often promoted to the public and require an audience; events often need private investment, sponsors, and donors.

There is an entire literature on the regeneration of facilities and infrastructure development and their impact at the social and community levels. Such facilities include stadiums, conference halls, outdoor settings, auditoriums, and transformed spaces resulting in social development and urbanism (such literature includes authors such as Spirou, 2011; Deery et al., 2012; Richards and

Palmer, 2012). The spaces used for events are a piece of urban transformation leading to an industrialised city, a mega-city, or the regeneration of the destination city which is seen as the host of such events. The sustainable effects of events and their regeneration purposes are measured through the 'event scorecard' or 'event-management-system' where mega-sporting events are evaluated for their socio-economic impact (Wise and Harris, 2017, p. 5).

2.4 What Makes an Event a Mega-Event?

The body of literature on mega-sporting events is extensive and academic interest in mega-sporting events has grown significantly over recent decades. However, much of the dominant discourse on those events today concentrate on their 'economic dimensions, and the short- and long-term impacts an event could have for hosts' (Cornelissen, 2010, p. 311).

The title of this section comes from Müller's article asking exactly 'what makes an event a mega-event? Definitions and sizes.' (Müller, 2015). Comparisons between mega-sporting events have proven difficult since each one has a unique specificity. Over the past decades, standards, requirements, and parameters on hosting a mega-sporting event have changed. Definitions of the term mega-event are approximations at best. For instance, Maurice Roche understands the term as 'large-scale cultural (including commercial and sporting) events, which have a dramatic character, mass popular appeal and international significance' (2000, p. 1). Martin Müller brings four key dimensions: 'visitor attractiveness, mediated reach, cost and transformative impact' (2015, p. 628). However, these categories could apply to a broad range of events, including significant cultural events like World Expos, political summits like G20, international conferences, and even single-sport events such as the United States of America's Super Bowl competition. The question remains how do we approach these characteristics, and how do we measure them? Should a mega-event be evaluated by the number of tickets sold, number of visitors, financial implications, the prestige of

performers/players, or other reasons? The number of tickets sold can serve as a variable proxy since counting the number of visitors is hardly feasible. Nevertheless, visitors often buy more than one ticket, so the mere number has minimal informative value unless visitors' consumption patterns are analysed (Preuss, Seguin, and O'Reilly, 2007). However, there is no international agreement on a benchmark for how many tickets an event must sell to be considered a mega-event.

2.5 The Rise of Mega-Sporting Events as a Strategy for Economic Transformation, Urban Growth, and Tourism Development

Mega-sporting events can lead to positive effects on host countries. For example, Burbank et al. (2002, p. 21) highlighted the link to hosting global sporting events, such as the World Cup and Olympics, which resulted in infrastructural development, improvement in transport, economic growth, and stimulated urban development. Over the last decade, mega-sporting event organisers such as the International Olympic Committee (IOC) and the International Federation of Association Football (FIFA) has awarded noteworthy events to developing nations across the world as each country has an equal right to bid for an event (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 9).

Some of the developing nations (and by developing we use the definition of the 2008 World Bank's classification of countries by income) to host mega-sporting events within the last ten years include: the 2010 FIFA World Cup in South Africa; the 2014 FIFA World Cup, and 2016 Olympic Games, both in Brazil; the 2018 FIFA World Cup in Russia; and the awaited 2022 FIFA World Cup in Qatar (McGillivray and McPherson, 2012, p. 24). The events have a significant implication for the country's tourism and economic developments (Srivastava, 2016, p. 40). Witt, Brooke, and Buckley (2013, p. 11) anticipate that the action will create a boom in Qatar's tourism industry

because, as projected, more than one million tourists will witness the mega-sporting event. Expenses from tourism are made through restaurants as tourists require various social amenities such as food, park fees, recreation facilities, and accommodation services (Witt, Brooke, and Buckley, 2013, p. 12). Other expenses include conferences, meetings, and several exhibitions for business investors. Srivastava's (2016, p. 40) estimations indicate that the sector alone will generate about QAR 66 billion by 2025. While this event has attracted global attention, the country has made appropriate plans to offer the visitors. Bellinger (2010, p. 22) argues that when a tourist spends \$500, the restaurant's income increases by \$500.

Hosting a mega-sporting event has led to the Qatari government developing a sharp vision and development strategy that can realise the continued development of the tourism sector after the 2022 World Cup finals. According to Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson (2012, p. 31), the need to achieve economic imperatives is the primary rationale for hosting peripatetic mega-sporting events. Tourist numbers are expected to remain high (Viehoff and Poynter, 2016, p. 14). As the country heads towards the tournament, it has eased the various restrictions initially concerning foreign investments within Qatar's tourism sector. That decision has been enhanced through the country's National Tourism Strategy, pioneered by the Qatar Tourism Authority. A strategy was unveiled to ensure that Qatar has developed into a world-class hub through an appropriate plan of cultural offshoring, various sporting events, business investments, and facilities for hosting important conferences (Qatar Report, 2015, p. 231). The mega-sporting event is one such aspect that promotes the nation.

Lellinger (2010, p. 26) outlines how the events influence the transport sector with the service offering employment to the suppliers of the buses, the tour guides, and the drivers involved in carrying tourists to various places. Gayle and Goodrich (2014, p. 90) state that the media benefits

from advertising services promoting mega-sporting events and their sponsors. The media plays a significant role in explaining and justifying the returns gained from the staging of mega-sporting events. Mosedale (2016, p. 2) argues that the economic benefits accruing from these events lead to an increase in the overall Gross Domestic Product of the nation through a spill over effect to other sectors of the economy. For instance, present earnings from tourism are significant contributors to the economy in the Caribbean. In support of these assertions, Gayle and Goodrich (2014, p. 20) state that in 2013, the sector contributed 14% of the total GDP from the expenditure made by tourists. That scenario presents a significant contribution that foreigners can generate, especially if there are many visitors in the hosting countries.

Urban and regional projects that are meant for long-term developments are often regarded as critical requirements. Schuessler (2011, p. 4) further illustrates that the event intends to redirect most of the venues used for sporting and transportation services linked to the events. As the opening ceremony for the event ends, more funds are appropriated towards the events. These are funds that were meant for schools, hospitals, and social inclusion, among many others. In addition, the events require large venues, which can be underutilised after the events. That makes these infrastructures highly unprofitable unless further events are hosted (Müller, 2016, p. 33).

Infrastructure further requires other facilities with a capacity of hosting the considerable numbers of people that are expected. High-class restaurants are expected to support the substantial number of tourists that will flow into the region. The most challenging part of the infrastructure comes in its management after the attendees leave the country. It is unclear if the country will be able to sustain this infrastructure and ensure that the investment put in the government does not go to waste after one month of the sporting event. Infrastructure, therefore, requires massive investment. Looking at the long run, it might not be possible to support the infrastructure, especially if

the event fails to attract the anticipated substantial number of fans. The agenda of hosting a significant event has moved from the idea of being culturally advanced, economically wealthy, and capable of being culturally rich, developed, and democratic (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 31). In contrast, previous events were awarded based on the capacity and capability to deliver, and to being developmentally oriented through economic, social, and political factors.

To expound on the impact of hosting a mega-sporting event on urban growth and tourism development, South Africa's 2010 World Cup was estimated to receive 12% additional growth for that year. (De Aragao, 2015, p. 8). De Aragao (2015, p. 8) also noted that 'the government estimated that around 306,600 tourists visited the country for the event, spending USD 444 million, mainly in shopping, food, and accommodation'. On the other hand, the government spent about USD 3.12 billion to construct stadia, telecommunications, and transportation services (De Aragao, 2015, p. 13). However, despite the country's citizens complaining of such a massive investment from the country's coffers, De Aragao (2015) illustrates that the national government of South Africa reported a positive economic impact from the 2010 World Cup, with the event contributing about USD 509 million to South Africa's 2010 Gross Domestic Product. Consequently, USD 769 million was created that benefited households, whereby USD 228 million of that total was designated to families with low incomes. This shows the benefit from the commitment of the government to finance the sporting committee, which was subsequently repaid by facilitating the country's growth.

2.6 Sport Events Sponsorships

The theory on sport sponsorships is substantial, as they include tobacco, food and beverages, and clothing. Sport sponsorships create enormous expenditure from both public and private sector companies. For instance, some students assessed: 'The degree to which a sporting event's

image was transferred to a brand through event sponsorship activity' and found that 'subjects in the sponsorship pairing treatment were more likely to report similarities on brand-event personality components than subjects who were not exposed to the event-brand sponsorship link, thus supporting the notion that sponsorship results in image transfer' (Gwinner and Eaton, 1999, 47).

The sport sponsorship procedure is not new. In the late 1990s, one event alone was attracting so many sponsors that it was comparable to passengers on subways: 'there are so many riders that it is getting hard to find an open seat' (Wilber, 1998, pp. 8). It was stipulated that sport sponsorship was attaining saturation, however since the late 1990s until 2020, subsidies have been growing as various new brands became interested in using sport as a marketing tool. Based on a study compiling data from the Sport Sponsor Factbook, it is estimated that 'firms which engage in sport marketing typically end up spending about one-third of their total advertising budget on sport sponsorships' (Branikas, 2019, p. 2).

It is worth noting that even if the product market advertising is very costly, the companies (both private and public) end up benefitting on a long-term basis as the brand sponsorship creates momentum and builds a brand's image. A study of the McKinsey company from 2014 attested that there are five crucial metrics for measuring the worth of sport sponsorship: the cost per reach (number of people exposed to the subsidy); unaided awareness per reach (activation activities such as booths and direct merchandise promotion); sales/margin per dollar spent (linking the sales to the sponsorship directly); the long-term brand attributes; and the indirect benefits (Jacobs, Jain, and Surana, 2014).

Qatar's sport sponsorships cover football competitions. For instance, Qatar Airways, the national airline company, has a portfolio sponsorship of various global sports such as A.S. Roma, Boca Juniors, and FC Bayern Munich (Sports Business, 2019). Furthermore, in 2020, the airline

company decided to also sponsor Paris Saint-Germain for the next three seasons, including the 'Paris Saint-Germain Handball and women's football teams until 2022' (FTN News, 2020). In addition, Qatar Airways also offers regional sponsorships, including acting as a three-year official airline partner of the Philippines Football League, and the Australian Football League (AFL). It is also a partner of CONMEBOL, the governing body for football in South America (Sports Business, 2019 and FTN News, 2020).

Additionally, Qatar Airways covers several FIFA events such as: 'the 2018 FIFA World Cup in Russia, the FIFA Club World Cup, the FIFA Women's World Cup, the 2022 FIFA World Cup in Qatar, and the FIFA World Cup, the world's largest online gaming tournament' (Qatar Airways). Figure 1 shows an example of the sponsorship ramifications of Qatar Airways and its influence across the globe. There are also other sports covered by the airline company such as the men's Qatar ExxonMobil Open, and the women's Qatar Total Open Tennis Tournaments, the 2017 CHI AL SHAQAB, the first equestrian competition of its kind in the Middle East and Asia, as well as the Qatar Classic Squash Championship (Qatar Airways). All these sponsorships are a firm commitment to sport, and it appears that the company's agenda for supporting sport is a parallel path to its primary mandate as an airline company. In this regard, the company attested that 'the values of sport as a means of bringing people together, [is] something at the core of the airline's brand message – Going Places Together (Sports Business, 2019). Recent impacts, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, means it is estimated that sponsorship spending will fall as much as \$17.2 billion because of the health crisis causing delays and cancellation of events (Cutler, 2020).

Figure 1: Qatar Airways Network of Sport Sponsorship Transactions

2.7 Sport in Qatar

The Ministry of Culture and Sports manages sport in Qatar. According to the Emiri Decree No. 4 of 2016, it is the Ministry's responsibility to 'raise the level of sport in the State to the extent of excellence, and the general supervision over the bodies concerned with sport, supporting them and following-up their works and coordinating between them' (Ministry of Culture and Sports). Accordingly, the Ministry launched the Qatar Sports for All Federation (QSFA) by Resolution No. 47 in 2015. The resolution aims to promote sport within activities such as the national sports day (celebrated on 11 February), the 356 Active fitness programs aiming to promote a healthy lifestyle, the Qatar Youth League, a football tournament for youth, and other general sport activities (QSFA).

Qatar's traditional sports include 'Arabian horse racing, camel racing, and falconry, all rooted in the country's nomadic past' (Topend Sports, 2014). In addition, contemporary sports such as golf, swimming, football, volleyball, and table tennis have become popular in recent years. Qatar's interest in sport was prominent in December 2006, when the country became the first one

in the region (and second in West Asia following Tehran in 1974) to host the 15th Asian Games (Asia's Olympic-style sporting event) at the Khalifa International Stadium in Doha (Topend Sports). Qatar's participation in the Olympic Games took place for the first time in 1984, and the first time that Qatar hosted a regional event was in 1988 when it welcomed the AFR Asian Cup. Qatar hosted two other international competitions in the 1990s: the 1995 FIFA U-20 World Cup and the 1999 Handball World Junior Championship. It is at the start of the 21st century that Qatar showed its interest in being a host country for various sporting events. It hosted the 2006 Asian Games, the 2011 AFC Asian Cup (soccer), the 2014 FINA World Swimming Championships (25m) in Doha; the 2015 World Handball Championships, the 2015 IBA World Championships (boxing) in Doha; the 2019 World Athletic Championships, in Doha; and the 2019 World Beach Games in Doha. (Topend Sports). In 2020 alone, Qatar announced a calendar of sixty-five sport championships and events to be hosted between January-December, covering sports such as marathons, gymnastics, basketball, horse riding, tennis, squash, weightlifting, rugby, badminton, cricket, handball, and many others (The Peninsula). Even if some of the events are postponed because of the COVID-19 pandemic, it still confirms the increased interest of Qatar in sporting events – regional and international, building Doha as the centre of Middle Eastern sporting events. The 2022 FIFA World Cup remains the major expected event to take place in Qatar.

2.8 Conclusion

This chapter has set the scene for exploring an event, namely a mega-sporting event: it has looked at definitions, tourism and brand benefits, economic and urban transformation, and long-term benefits of events beyond the momentum itself. Furthermore, this chapter elaborated on Qatar's role in mega-sporting events, how much sponsorship is allocated to mega-sporting events,

the importance of mega-sporting events at large, the organisation of regional and international sport competitions, and the Ministry of Culture and Sports.

The following chapter will put forward an analysis of Qatar's benefits and challenges in hosting the 2022 World Cup. It will also discuss Qatar's positioning in international human rights and labour laws, especially within the context of international human rights covenants (civil and political rights; and economic, social, and cultural rights), as well as Qatar's role within two international organisations: the International Organization for Migration (I.O.M.) and the International Labour Organization (I.L.O.). Moreover, the next chapter will elaborate on the literature review concerned with: a) human rights, b) the organisation of mega-sporting events and human rights in context with positive and negative impacts over labour rights, children's rights, migrant rights, corruption, and other infractions.

Chapter 3: Literature Review

3.2 Introduction

The literature review discusses the unique relationship between mega-sporting events and international human rights. It will discuss human rights and the international context of labour rights, migrant rights, and the benefits and challenges of organizing a mega-sporting event from a human rights perspective. A multi-faceted approach will be presented, in which several different aspects of the research topic will be discussed and evaluated. The first two sections will discuss Qatar's unique demography, employment systems, subsequent sections and sub-sections will explore the relationship between human rights and mega-sporting events with regard to existing literature.

3.3 Qatar's Multi-Cultural Demography

Qatar's population is estimated at 2,444,174 as of July 2020 (CIA World Factbook). The ethnic groups within the country are Qatari at around 11.6% and non-Qatari at about 88.4%, with a net migration rate of 6.5 migrants per one thousand population (2015 est., CIA World Factbook). The difference between Qatari and non-Qatari residents has rapidly increased since 1970 when 59.5% of the population was non-Qatari (Gulf Research Center, 2014, p. 6). In 2013, it was stipulated that 'migrant workers dominate Qatar's labour force, comprising 94% of all workers and 86% of the country's total population of two million - the world's highest ratio of migrants to citizens' (Migration Policy Institute, 2013). In the recent 2020 International Organization for Migration World Migration Report, it is estimated that 78.7% of Qatar's population are international migrants (p. 23). The report also stipulates that the Arab region is the top destination for migrant workers. The Gulf States have a 95% labour force composed of migrant workers, especially for the construction and domestic work, with many male individuals constituting this workforce (p. 34).

While most nationals in the Gulf Cooperation Council are employed within the public sector, non-nationals are employed in the private sector. In 2014, in Qatar, 80.6% of the employees in the public sector were Qatari and, by contrast, 78.4% of the private sector employees were non-Qatari (Gulf Research Center, 2014, p. 7). Qataris occupy 81% of white-collar positions within those groups, from managers to clerks, while non-nationals occupy the lowest work positions (Gulf Research Center, 2014, p. 7).

Migrants are attracted by oil and gas industries, which provide unskilled and semi-skilled workers opportunities to construction and maintenance sites. Indeed, in 2017, 50.3% of Qatar's GDP originated from the industry sector, while 49.5% came from the services sector, and another small percentage of 0.2% originated from agriculture (CIA World Factbook). The industrial sector of Qatar focuses on liquefied natural gas, crude oil production and refining, ammonia, fertilisers, petrochemicals, steel reinforcing bars, cement, and commercial ship repair (CIA World Factbook). In Qatar, 'the recent increased demand for workers in areas such as construction is partly driven by the country's preparation for the 2022 World Cup' (World Migration Report, 2020, p. 83).

In terms of the demographic composition of migrants in Qatar, the majority originate from developing and emerging countries, with an essential percentage of individuals from South and East Asia. Kapiszewski estimates that the data for Qatar does not provide a breakdown of countries of origin for the migrant population. While attempting to obtain this data, the author revealed the following composition: India, the Philippines, and Nepal were the top three countries migrants originated from in 2002 (Seshan, 2012, p. 158). The Gulf Research Center confirms that statistics from 2013 reveal that foreign workers in Qatar originated from India (31.2%), Nepal (23.5%), the Philippines (11.4%), and Bangladesh (9.0%) (p. 9). However, there are rapid changes in Qatar's demography. For instance, the Bangladeshi community was at around 137,000 in 2013, while in

2019, it reached 400,000, increasing 190% (Online Qatar, 2019). Thus, as the literature shows, Qatar possesses a demographic make-up which is somewhat similar to that of its neighbouring GCC countries. The country possesses a substantial number of foreign residents which are often employed in service industries. Some of these assessments of employment industries will be discussed in more detail in the following section.

3.4 Employment in Qatar

Migrants and employees in Qatar are monitored and protected by the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs. From 2009 to today, the employment rate in Qatar fluctuated no lower than 97.7%, reaching 99.8% in 2019 (Statista). The unemployment rate in Qatar is meagre, situated somewhere at around 0.10% (Trading Economics website). According to Trading Economics, the minimum wage in Qatar is estimated at QAR 750 per month. In 2017, in the context of Doha's preparations for the 2022 World Cup, the Minister of Justice announced that the minimum wage for migrant workers was set at 750 riyals (\$195, 166€) per month which would immediately come into effect (CNBC, 2017). It is estimated that the 'average Qatari household, comprising around 8 or 9 people, earns QAR 72,700 per month. This is nearly three times what the average (Western) expatriate household, of 4 or 5 people, earned at QAR 24,400 monthly' (Expactica, 2020). Another discrepancy is between Qatari and non-Qatari employees and between the country of origin of non-Qatari, as Asian expatriates have a low income compared to Western expatriates, the latter of whom negotiate competitive benefits packages with the employer (Expactica, 2020). This may also differ because Asian expatriates in a vulnerable position seeking an urgent job to support their family do not usually have high-level university degrees and are mostly expected to stay in a work camp.

Qatar's Planning and Statistics Authority effectuated within the first quarter of 2020 a labour force sample survey on 2,292 participants, both Qatari and non-Qatar. Among the findings, it is essential to note that 408 non-Qatari and 0 Qatari responded that they were unemployed because of lack of job opportunities, 235 non-Qatari and 0 Qatari responded that they were unemployed because of low wages, and 173 non-Qatari and 0 Qatari responded that they were unemployed because they got discharged (p. 22). These figures show the differences in the work landscape between Qatari and non-Qatari and the vulnerability of non-nationals in employment. Although there is a demographic imbalance between nationals and foreigners, the distinctions of status and employment opportunities/challenges separate further the two parties. The Planning and Statistics Authority of Qatar does not offer statistical information on the migrants' labour workforce specifically. The survey effectuated by the authority does not disaggregate data by nationality of non-Qatari residents; it only differentiates between Qatari and non-Qatari for purposes of non-discrimination. Thus, as this brief section showcased, Qatar's employment framework is highly dependent on a large group of foreign workers which not only make up the vast majority of the nation's service industry, but which also make up its working-class positions.

3.5 The Multi-Faceted Relationship Between Human Rights Abuses and the Development of Mega-Sporting Events

As this research will establish, mega-sporting events are incredibly important opportunities for expanding international economic cooperation, political collaboration, and more generally, the potential growth of a genuinely interconnected global community (Gaffney, 2013). Although one-time occurrences, these mega-sporting events can have long-lasting economic implications, inviting substantial amounts of foreign investment, and creating the necessary platforms for international cultural, economic, political, and social exchange (Kassens-Noor et al., 2015). If anything,

the development of a mega-sporting event should allow for the continued expansion of individual living standards, and the growth of a strong, independent, and humane national political and economic system. As argued by Foley et al. (2012), the need for achieving several diverse and various economic imperatives is the primary rationale for hosting almost all of the world's largest mega-sporting events. However, much like it will be continued to be highlighted throughout this study, mega-sporting events can also lead to the deterioration of existing human rights systems, and in many instances, can have both domestic and global repercussions. Throughout this sub-section, the direct relationship between mega-sporting events development and between the greater notion of human rights systems will be closely evaluated and discussed. The overall examination will revolve around three key factors associated with the preservation of human rights, and the need to adhere to internationally developed and monitored human rights standards. The first of these is housing vulnerability, which has often proven one of the most prevalent and far-reaching negative implications of mega-sporting events development, while the second relates to the exploitation of domestic and foreign workers. Finally, the third element is associated with the dangers and challenges of global supply and procurement chains often utilised within mega-sporting events development systems.

The strategising, developing, and planning processes associated with many mega-sporting events often require substantial domestic investments and infrastructural improvements. Moreover, the events often also require vast amounts of physical space within potentially attractive urban city centres. As a result of these requirements and precedents, mega-sporting events development programmes often result in governmental measures aiming to create new space within already

occupied residential neighbourhoods. Because many urban city centres are often partially populated by smaller local slums, these are often the most vulnerable neighbourhoods to be affected by mega-sporting events development projects (Wang & Bao, 2018).

Furthermore, several recent examples have continued to show, the need for creating new space within urban city centres often results in the increased abuse of already marginalised communities, including the socioeconomically vulnerable, and the ethnically foreign. Forced eviction and subsequent homelessness is a significantly important and particularly dangerous theme of abuse often associated with some of the world's most important sporting event preparation processes. For example, certain segments of Beijing's resident population experienced different forms of forced eviction throughout the country's preparation process for the Olympic Games, leaving them homeless and extremely vulnerable to theft and abuse (Wang & Bao, 2018). In preparation for the 2008 games, Beijing contractors not only forced approximately three-hundred thousand residents to be displaced from their homes, but then actively recruited the same vulnerable individuals within infrastructural development projects, as construction workers (Müller, 2015; Wang & Bao, 2018). In addition, the contractors denied workers fundamental human rights and forced them to endure a variety of unfavourable working conditions. Thus, the implications of most human rights abuses are not only dangerous because of how they directly undermine the wellbeing of specific domestic communities, but also because of how they potentially emphasise already-existing inequalities and injustices. As Shin has shown, the instance of the Chinese housing evictions directly impacted socioeconomically vulnerable communities living within densely packed urban city-centres, who possessed incredibly high living costs in comparison to their existing capabilities. Large parts of Beijing's working class, much like in many other emerging economies, come from the nation's rural peripheries in hopes of finding financial opportunity within the rapidly

developing Chinese capital (Shin, 2009). However, these individuals are often exploited by their inability to find reasonable housing and the struggles they face as being the most vulnerable communities within the city (Shin, 2009). This is in line with the proposition that nations with already-existing track records for human rights abuses will often resort to increased violations in preparation for the event. Existing research has also often suggested that sporting event preparation management is much more likely to undermine the wellbeing and rights of society's most vulnerable groups, including individuals within socio-economically vulnerable housing communities, as well as immigrants.

In the same way that Beijing's socioeconomically vulnerable communities present a vulnerability, and in turn, social and political responsibility to the Chinese government, Qatar's diverse and multi-ethnic working class should be able to enjoy the same human rights and privileges. However, Qatar's specific issues with its approach to a mega-sporting event have revolved around another incredibly important aspect of the relationship between mega-sporting events and potential human rights abuses — the alleged exploitation of workers. The exploitation of workers' rights has been a significantly important component of the general relationship between mega-sporting events development and human rights abuses, and as studies show, has been prevalent in the Beijing Games, as well as the Olympics in Sochi (Müller, 2015). In Beijing, for example, the communities that faced eviction from their housing communities were placed within workers groups that then helped construct the city's sporting event infrastructure. It was claimed that approximately ten of the city's construction workers had died due to a variety of complications and injuries resulting directly from the contractors' failure to create adequately safe working conditions. It was found that immigrants operating within the space of the city's construction industry were not only highly exploited because of their exposure to unsafe working conditions, but also because of their

being forced to live within unsanitary communal spaces. Workers were also denied fair wages and were not offered health insurance or provided medical services.

Finally, another important aspect revolves around the need for carefully reviewing and developing more human procurement strategies. It is an undeniable fact that mega-sporting events often require substantial investments in infrastructure, which in turn, often place increased pressure on domestic and global supply chains. For many of these global suppliers and contractors, the need to increase production is often paralleled by an increase of exploitative procurement strategies, environmentally and ethically unsustainable methods of extraction, and other procurement abuses to human rights. Therefore, it is the sole responsibility of the host nation to ensure that its suppliers, collaborative partners, and economic peers, are all practicing procurement strategies that do not infringe on the individual rights of its workers, which provide each of its affected individuals with the necessary rights and privileges that they so deserve under the guidelines of HRW, Amnesty International, and the United Nations.

In this section, the multi-faceted relationship between mega-sporting events and human rights cases has been explored with regard to a number of different human rights issues and challenges, almost all of which have been evidenced, through the use of existing literature, in different recent mega-sporting events. Therefore, as this review section shows, it is incredibly important for mega-sporting events planners to develop more nuanced and advanced mechanisms for potentially exploring the ways through which mega-sporting events can expand the potential for human rights development, and this is an aspect of sporting management which is significant to Qatar, where the 2022 World Cup is to be hosted.

3.6 Qatar's Benefits in Hosting the 2022 World Cup

There is a plethora of crucial authors (Kahane and Shmanske, 2012; Maening, 2012; Smith, 2012; Cotton and Welden, 2014; Hong and Lu, 2016; Zimbalist, 2016; Flowers, 2017; McGillivray and Turner, 2017) that offer critical evaluations on the benefits of bidding and hosting a mega-sporting event. The benefits include sport diplomacy and economic benefits and other specific factors contributing to hosting a mega-sporting event, such as framing the country's image and promoting regional unity.

Sport tourism gains attraction worldwide as it brings economic growth when hosting sport events or mega-sporting events. Sport tourism has mainly gained prominence in Asia, the Gulf Region, and the Middle East as a crucial development, urban growth, and economic driver. In the past ten years, states from the Gulf region have started to bid for mega-sporting events. In the process, human rights and government policies have been revised and become a crucial part of securing the rights to host a mega-sporting event. De Aragao (2015) undertook a study on the impact of hosting mega-sporting events and established that significant development arises from increased exposure globally and the economic activities that come from the event. In addition, there are other indirect impacts like enhancing a country's international profile, urban growth, an opportunity to improve infrastructure, and to create employment opportunities. According to (Weinberg 2017, p. 18), Qatar has undergone a crucial transformation from hosting the 15th Asian Games held in 2006, in Doha, to the ongoing preparations to host the 2022 World Cup. However, changes may have started even earlier when Qatar demonstrated its commitment to equal rights for women by establishing the Qatar Women's Sports Committee in 2001. This Committee was a major milestone, resulting in a bronze medal in shooting at the 15th Asian Games in Qatar itself (Foley, McGillivray and McPherson, 2012, p. 10).

The recent developments have put the country closer to its Western counterparts, emphasising sport equality, particularly the involvement of women (previously excluded), the abolishment of the *Kafala* system, and workers' rights improvements. (Lemon, 2016, p. 29). Moreover, by improving the country in sport tourism, infrastructure development, and new facilities, the country's citizens have bought into the government's vision of development and growth through mega-sporting events.

On the flip side, sporting events sometimes fail to achieve their intended target, leading to adverse effects. Some countries are accused of overspending and thereby burdening their economies, while others use the events to gain international and regional dominance (Igel, 2017, p. 7). While some praised the decision to provide Qatar with a platform to operate on a global stage by hosting such a large event like the 2022 FIFA World Cup, others questioned the legitimacy of the country hosting the event.

3.6.2 Promoting Unity, Integrity, and Security

According to Brannagan and Giulianotti (2014, p. 11), Qatar's government is also motivated to promote unity between nations. This significant theme centres on the state's foreign policy, for which the nation has sufficient economic abilities (Schuessler, 2011, p. 3). In this regard, the country aims to embed itself in the international scene by emerging as a significant centre where dialogues for global issues may happen (Holt and Ruta, 2015, p. 22). These issues are associated with continued economic benefits, especially for Qatar. Moreover, the government must ensure sufficient security is well established during the event (Brannagan and Giulianotti, 2014, p. 711). This type of initiative will result in Qatar being positioned and valued as a significant contributor in international affairs and thus receive attention from many foreign investors willing to invest in Qatar.

Addressing the national health crisis of Qatar is another objective of the country. Based on international measures, Qatar is a country that is experiencing some national concerns associated with health levels (Raed, 2014, p. 1). For example, 71% of the citizens of Qatar are obese, while 20% of Qatar nationals suffer from diabetes (Raed, 2014, p. 2). This health crisis emanates from the high consumption of fast foods and less engagement in physical activities (Brannagan and Giulianotti, 2014, p. 712). According to Jeffreys (2014, p. 12), Qatar aims to curb these health crises of obesity and diabetes. One of the strategies that is laid out is the employment of sports and physical activities. Jeffreys (2014, p. 12) continues to illustrate that the sporting facilities that have been well developed are aimed to have a positive impact on the health of the nationals, as the sporting event will leave a sporting legacy for the citizens, which will lead to a sporting culture being established. Sporting culture is intended to challenge the obesity and diabetes health issues experienced in Qatar (Raed, 2014, p. 1). Based on Jeffreys (2014), the construction of hospital facilities as the country prepares for the 2022 World Cup are such a substantial investment that the country will continue to benefit from these facilities after the events. As a result, citizens will have a broader range of medical access, which is a critical step towards lowering some of the national health crises experienced by Qatar.

Notwithstanding the considerable benefits that Qatar will acquire from hosting the 2022 FIFA World Cup event, there are multiple challenges that include the high cost of preparation, legacy planning, financial allocation dimensions, infrastructural priority dimensions, and the legal dimensions of the hosting country assessed below.

3.6.3 Framing of Image

Qatar is set to benefit profoundly from hosting the 2022 World Cup finals (Zimbalist, 2016, p. 44). Zimbalist illustrates that the country has an effective plan to demonstrate to the world that

it has significant potential. The government is already viewing Qatar as an economic power that is emerging in the world. In this regard, the government is aiming at gaining prominence both regionally and nationally. According to the government spokesperson of Qatar, the chance given to the country of hosting the mega-sporting event is a catalyst for positive change for the country in terms of both human rights and economic contexts, among many others in the Middle East region. Cotton and Welden (2014, p. 7) agree that the FIFA World Cup will considerably improve the country's image and perception in the countries within and beyond the region. Todd and Jewell (2016 p. 12) give an example of the 2014 World Cup in Brazil, which significantly boosted the country's exposure and image. Hosting a mega-sporting event will implicitly involve a specific influence in a country's soft power ranking, such as the *Soft Power 30*, an annual index published by Portland Communications, or the *Monocle Soft Power Survey*, which also ranks countries according to their soft political intervention. Qatar is not ranked among those reports as an extraordinary soft power, but this does not mean that its influence will not grow in time.

The Brazilian tourism President Mr. Vicente Neto revealed that staging the World Cup event was essential; it made the country climb ten positions in the 'International Congress and Convention Association' rankings. That is from 29th to 19th based on the number of conferences and conventions that the country hosts. Furthermore, there was an increase in the number of events held in Brazil, from 62 events to 315 events. Consequently, the number of cities involved with the staging of the events increased further from 22 to 54 (Todd and Jewell, 2016, p. 12). Todd and Jewell (2016, p. 13) continue to illustrate that, during that period, the decentralisation policy that Brazil adopted was a significant attraction of international events. From the evidence provided, through the 2022 World Cup, Qatar will gain a positive image by demonstrating to the world its

vast potential. In this regard, it is also possible to increase international rankings, that has been experienced before in other countries such as Brazil.

3.6.4 Regional Unity

By hosting the events, Qatar aims to bring the Middle East region together. Currently, the area is experiencing turmoil, with some countries allying against each other through the imposition of sanctions. According to the AFP (2017, p. 4), one of the instabilities experienced within the Middle East comes from the various diplomatic sanctions imposed on Qatar by countries within the region. This threatens the aims of establishing regional unity. Based on the illustrations presented by Maennig (2012, p. 22), Qatar has put in place measures to use mega-sporting events to promote regional unity in the Middle East. For instance, according to the 'Qatar-American Partnership', Qatar will hold the events during the winter months since the nation experiences high temperatures during summer periods. However, the country has initiated a ground-breaking technology that will provide a cooling effect in the region through the year, both in summer and winter periods. Qatar will then dismantle the stadiums after the 2022 World Cup and offer these structures to other countries within the region.

In addition, Qatar is determined to use the event to achieve its objective by physically bringing the region together by constructing an extensive metro system. (Flowers, 2017, p. 32) That system will be available in Qatar and cover several other states, such as Bahrain and Saudi Arabia (Flowers, 2017, p. 32). The intensive network of future roads and the improvement of the existing roads could link Qatar to other countries in the region.

Qatar will benefit from being framed as the 'regional sporting hub' by staging this mega-sporting event. The country has successfully hosted several other mega-sporting events, including the World Cup for the U-20 in 1995, the Asia games held in 2006, the 2011 A.F.C., and the 2019

IAAF World Athletics Championships. In addition to the economic gains from the 2006 Asia games, the country gained state political recognition, and demonstrated outstanding potential for organising several other prestigious sporting events (Attali, 2016, p. 91). Moreover, Qatar won the bid to stage the 2022 World Cup events, thereby serving as evidence for its potential. Hong and Lu (2016, p. 3) illustrate that combining all these with the 'Aspire' program reflects what the nation has put in place, and the ownership of K.A.S Eupen (short for Königliche Allgemeine Sportvereinigung Eupen, in English: Royal General Sports Association). At the same time, Qatar will be able to secure and expand the influence it has in football all over the world. In this regard, Qatar aims to be viewed as the 'global soccer power' (Sulayem, O'Connor, and Hassan, 2013, p. 22). The position will benefit the state through sport tourism and sponsorship of its major leagues.

However, despite these theories placing Qatar in a suitable position of significant gains, sport events as a vehicle for these gains may not be sufficient. According to the AFP (2017, p. 5), it appears that some of the countries within the region are not pleased with Qatar as the primary host of the 2022 World Cup finals. That was especially noticeable when the 'U.A.E. will host the World Cup' hashtags used in social media prompted an angry reaction online. In addition, several diplomatic and economic sanctions have been imposed on Qatar by other Middle East countries, who force them to comply with specific regional standards. As a result, some countries that have also imposed sanctions on Qatar are less inclined to participate in the 2022 World Cup finals, completely locking themselves out of the event. In addition, the Gulf Cooperation Council recently sent a list comprising 13 demands that they wanted Qatar to agree on, upon the failure of which the Council explained that they would isolate Qatar (Igel, 2017, p. 2). Igel (2017, p. 1) further explains that Qatar's government rejected the list, terming it unreasonable and aggressive. This resulted in the officials from Bahrain, the U.A.E., Saudi Arabia, and Egypt meeting to discuss any

new sanctions for Qatar. This illustrates that the instability experienced is far from over. This means that sport may not be an acceptable way of solving the elusive regional unity problems that Qatar intends to achieve. Nevertheless, there was a substantial positive turn of events when all the Gulf countries participated in the 24th Arabian Gulf Cup held in Qatar from 24 November to 6 December 2019. This may be an indicator that sport could lead to regional unity after all.

Amara noted that 'sport in its multiple forms is becoming a tool for leaders in the Gulf to reposition their countries on the world map' (Amara, 2005, p. 493). While examining the political discourse around the 2006 Qatar Asian Games, he noticed a 'sportification' of the Arabian Peninsula' mentioning that 'large investments are being poured into Gulf countries in the staging and sponsorship of the world's leading sport events and the building of sporting infrastructures' (Amara, 2005, p. 500).

3.6.5 Economic Benefits

Srivastava (2016, p. 40) states that the exposure impact of hosting mega-sporting events was evident in the international attention received by Qatar after the country secured the chance to host this event with the nation's name featuring heavily in the global sport media. In addition, the HSRC (2009, p. 185) points out that the hosting country has several potential benefits that involve direct financial advantages. Opportunities associated with the event include tourism revenue, participating teams, media services, accommodation facilities, transportation services, technological innovations, and many other critical investments resulting in spill overs.

Since Qatar secured the ticket to host the 2022 World Cup events, the country has put several measures to ensure it remains in the international spotlight. Real Estate is expected to realise considerable growth due to the high demand for the various facilities used by tourists, including resorts, restaurants, and hotel rooms (Lellinger, 2010, p. 23). Therefore, the mega-sporting

event is meant to give Qatar a significant boost in multiple advancements, vital to its growth and development (Srivastava, 2016, p. 42). The gain is critical to the growth of the state and the whole region at large. In this regard, increased infrastructure construction and the advancement of tourism revenue led to increased employment for the locals. Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson (2012, p. 29) state that countries with alternative systems of governance, such as Middle East countries, have the means of attaining the desired outcomes, but the events policy rationale remains the same.

The consecutive hosting of mega-sporting events such as the 2022 FIFA World Cup final and the 2030 Qatar National Vision has attracted the attention of many global investors (Mosedale, 2016, p. 3). Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson (2012, p. 13) state that the change in strategy and the subsequent award of hosting rights to Qatar has created an extensive debate in academia, politics, and the media, as the established world order is turned on its head. After winning the right to host the event, the nation has shown significant improvements in the global sporting arena. As Qatar prepares for the Events, the country's construction industry is growing faster than any other sector. (Smit, 2012, p. 18) *The Qatar Report* lists some of the mega projects that have already been completed, such as the developments in Downtown Doha, roads, metro lines, air-conditioned stadiums, and many other facilities. The increase in projects has created several opportunities for various sectors, including companies supplying raw materials, financing, design, and real estate firms (Qatar Report, 2015, p. 33). To support these development projects, there has been an increase in the construction sector in employing many workers, from both local and foreign populations. (Smit, 2012, p. 13). Estimates indicate that over 1.5 million jobs have been created so far, making Qatar a desirable job market. (Srivastava, 2016, p. 42). Considering that the global economy has not been conducive to the labour market, such statistics are encouraging.

Hunter (2010, p. 10) further highlights that Qatar will experience accelerated urban growth by staging the 2022 World Cup events. According to Hunter (2010, p. 12), commercial banks in Qatar expect infrastructural investments injected by the government of Qatar alone to be worth 100 billion Qatar rials. In addition to investments by the Qatar government, many foreign organisations are planning various projects in the country (Laghani, 2014, p. 2). One example is that German National Railways was offered a contract to construct a 320-kilometre metro system in Doha.

The boom has benefited stock exchange traders in Qatar, particularly the Doha Stock Exchange (D. S. E.), with the index rising by 0.68% soon after the country won the hosting rights in December 2010 (Hunter, 2010, p. 11). Since then, FIFA's official announcement of the 2022 World Cup event has affected the Doha Stock Exchange of Qatar. Al Refai and Eissa (2017, p. 4) highlighted that the D.S.E. market is sensitive to the tournament, resulting in volatility in the stock market. The Doha Stock Exchange market typically governs all the transactions made regarding bonds, Qatar's shareholding companies' shares, companies owned by the government, negotiable instruments, the quasi-government companies, and several other securities that are authorised for trading. Doha Stock Exchange is a body that is autonomous and indirectly regulated by the Trade Ministry of Qatar and the finance economy. The impact cited in the stock market reveals the long-term effects that the announcement had on investors in government and private expenditures anticipated for the period between the announcement and the hosting of the 2022 World Cup. This implies that several business entities, foreign investors, stock companies, and other medium firms are trying to secure deals with the country to share or be part of the development (Laghani, 2014, p. 2). The investments will result in the most prominent economic booms that have ever been

experienced in the country's history. Both corporate and retail banking sectors expect to benefit highly since they will be given an inducement (Hunter 2010, p. 13).

In addition to the economic benefits associated with the process, the mega-sporting event presents other non-financial benefits by promoting cultural, political, and social values, among many others (Laghani, 2014, p. 2). The mega-sporting event will experience a high level of attendance by visitors across the globe, bringing together people from different cultures, races, backgrounds, and religions. Staging these mega-sporting events will promote Qatar's culture, values, and ways of life globally, and attract many other global talents and foreign players from different parts of the world. The work highlights the socio-economic benefits of hosting mega-sporting events in Qatar's context. Over a decade, the justification for hosting a mega-sporting event needs to be more than just economic (Al Refai and Eissa, 2017, p. 4). Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson (2012, p. 6) point out that the host nations have used the staging of mega-sporting events as a significant global appeal to achieve their political, economic, social, and cultural objectives. For instance, the South African developmental plan for the 2010 World Cup was built on addressing poverty issues, inequalities experienced, and infrastructural capacity, among many other problems in the country. In addition to urban growth, tourism development, and the non-economic benefits of hosting a mega-sporting event, the following section evaluates the specific benefits that Qatar will gain from hosting the 2022 FIFA World Cup.

By staging the 2022 World Cup, Qatar is looking forward to economic gains (Srivastava (2016, p. 40). The country is focused on its economic growth, and mega-sporting events appear as one of the significant boosts towards expanding its developments (Sulayem, O'Connor, and Hassan, 2013, p. 33). The projections revealed that Qatar's economy is being spearheaded by the high export of oil to other states (Hong and Lu, 2016, p. 4). The changes in demand imply that countries

now have realised the value of hosting such events which attract investors, tourists, visitors, and the economic growth following the pre-eminence of the neo-liberalised order (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 14).

Consequently, Qatar is focusing on expanding the economy through other industries. Lee (2016, p. 2) explains that the country is already spending billions of dollars preparing for mega-sporting events. Infrastructure development is one of the significant factors that can lead to economic expansion. In this regard, over the next five years, the country has dedicated \$140 billion towards developing transport infrastructure only. Estimations made reveal that the country will spend more than \$3 billion in constructing nine stadiums that will be used and renovating three new stadiums. Moreover, \$3 million will be used in running the stadiums when the events take place (Lee, 2016, p. 2). As a result, World Cup events will have a higher contribution to Qatar's G.D.P. As witnessed in South Africa, the country experienced economic gains by staging the 2010 World Cup finals. The event contributed approximately USD 509 to South Africa's Gross Domestic Product and USD 228 to low-income families.

Events are considered valuable if they contribute positively to a structural transformation, such as cultural value, political value, economic growth, urban restructuring, amongst others. Institutional engagements emanating from a neoliberal background must promote the formation of growth coalitions and the flourishing of public-private partnerships in the name of promotion and place-making (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 47). Qatar is expecting to benefit from the anticipated increased number of tourists who will visit the country to watch the finals and continue visiting the country after the events (Parent and Smith-Swan, 2013). The mega-sporting event will put the state in the international spotlight. In this regard, the country is concerned about the long-term economic gains that it will continue to be subjected to. Therefore, it views the World

Cup finals as the best opportunity to open opportunities for the region (Cotton and Welden, 2014, p. 8). Practically, the nation stands to benefit from the investment both on a short-term and a long-term basis.

3.7 International Human Rights and Labour Laws

When we refer to international human rights, we mostly think of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights from 1948, later transcribed into international conventions and covenants on specific aspects of human rights. There are two international covenants on human rights: the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights from 1976 (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) from 1976. The main difference is that under the ICESCR, human rights are linked to the economic, social, and cultural dimensions. States should ensure the progressive realisation of those rights and not ensure the complete realisation, as specified in the ICCPR.

In 1966, the right to work became part of the International Covenant of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), stated in article 6, where the Covenant prescribes that governmental parties undertake to ‘ensure the equal right of men and women to the enjoyment of all economic, social and cultural rights.’ The Committee of the Covenant note that as the principle of non-discrimination is set out in article 2.2 of the Covenant, and article 7 of the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families notes:

this should apply to employment opportunities for migrant workers and their families. In this regard, the Committee underlines the need for national plans of action to be devised to respect and promote such principles by all appropriate measures, legislative or otherwise (ICESCR Committee, 2006).

One of the essential prerequisites required when hosting a mega-sporting event is adherence to international human rights policies and labour laws before bidding, during the construction and preparation phase, and the event. The modern world has an increased focus on international human rights, leading to calls for accountability and transparency (Talus, 2014, p. 3). The preparation process entails considerable construction of stadiums, hotels, roads, stations, and housing units that require intensive labour, leading to human trafficking. There are significant concerns of instances of forced labour, poor pay, and the abuse of human rights in the construction process, an issue that has already been raised in Qatar. In addition, the construction workers of various facilities used during mega-sporting events are exposed to poor working conditions, live in labour camps that are highly crowded with unsanitary conditions, and have little access to healthcare, which is a significant violation of human rights.

The Institute of Human Rights and Business (2016, p. 6) explains that the world is becoming more connected and highly informed in this age of inclusivity. As a result, human rights are becoming a significant concern around the globe. Sport at this moment depends on the goodwill and support of the public. In recent years, several cities like Boston, Rome, and Hamburg have withdrawn their bids for staging mega-sporting events (i. e. Olympic Games), despite all the efforts they put in to win a chance. Their primary concern is the increasing costs of hosting these events and the unachievable legacy ambitions. A significant number of participants and attendees have raised their concerns over participating in events held in cities where the construction of the stadiums involved the abuse of human rights. Participants and attendees are increasingly organising themselves together to play a prominent role in the resulting debate. As the media continues to reveal the human rights challenges that have been linked to mega-sporting events, there are mount-

ing calls for accountability and transparency to be observed. This involves the human rights challenges experienced when the host countries are conducting the process of planning and delivering the mega-sporting event legacies that defy easy solutions (Talus, 2014, p. 3). Qatar is not an exception when discussing the concern of human rights. Since the nation stands in the middle of those countries with some human rights violations, it must prove that it has taken the initiative to ensure that things have changed. The country stands to lose more regarding sponsorship if it fails to ensure that human rights are protected. Brands only support teams where their image is presented in a positive light.

In addition to adherence to human rights and labour laws by hosting countries, other critical areas of consideration are human trafficking and forced labour, which mainly occurs due to a shortage of work to facilitate the event during the preparation period. The following section addresses the relationship between hosting mega-sporting events, human trafficking, and forced labour.

3.8 Qatar's Challenges in Hosting the 2022 World Cup Mega-Sporting Event

3.8.2 Financial Dimension and High Preparation Costs

The high cost of a mega-sporting event preparation for Qatar is estimated at around \$200 billion (Todd and Jewell, 2016, p. 3). Initially, when Brazil was preparing for the 2014 World Cup, the country invested a large amount of money in creating sufficient infrastructure for it (Haisley, 2015, p. 1). The government of Brazil invested about \$15 billion. Henderson (2014, p. 13) states that 6% of the cost was used for security purposes, 23% was used to construct stadiums, and 71% was used for public works.

The financing of these costs is derived from supranational organisations. For example, most of the money used to finance World Cup projects such as operational and promotional projects is funded by supranational organisations like the IOC and FIFA. However, these amounts of money represent a small fraction of the total amount that the host government invests (Barrios, Russell, and Andrews, 2016, p. 8). Secondly, sponsorship is derived from private stakeholders. For instance, the presence of mega-sporting events results in several private stakeholders investing in various projects that would not have been initiated in the absence of mega-sporting events. For instance, the Los Angeles Olympics, held in 1984, is the best example that illustrates this kind of reasoning as the events were privately funded. Thirdly, resources are derived from the government which hosts mega-sporting events (Barrios, Russell, and Andrews, 2016, p. 9). The additional support offered plays a significant role in the facilitation of the project.

According to Henderson (2014), the 2014 World Cup was the most expensive tournament Brazil has ever hosted. However, the arguments presented by the Brazilian government illustrated that these projects were expedited because the match was urgent, and that Brazilians would be able to reap considerable gains after the tournament (Morpurgo, 2015, p. 2). Though this is a fair judgment, the government has still been criticised for overspending, and there are several other allegations of human rights violations.

When it comes to Qatar, the cost dedicated to preparing for the 2022 World Cup finals eclipsed Brazil's by far. The nation has dedicated vast resources to various investment structures to ensure that it can host the events. According to Henderson (2014, p. 8), the projections are estimated to be \$200 billion in constructing the projects that will facilitate the events. The transformation of Qatar's infrastructure alone has been recorded as \$140 billion (Lee, 2016, p. 3). Lee explains further that this involves constructing new roads, new airports, renovation of the existing

roads, and constructing the metro systems. The primary concern is whether Qatar can generate sufficient revenue during the World Cup to cover all the expenses for the event's preparations. Sulayem, O'Connor, and Hassan (2013, p. 33) have cited that despite Qatar using large sums of money in its investments, it is still anticipated that the country will generate many economic benefits. However, most researchers have sufficiently provided clear coverage on the issue of economic benefits versus the number of costs used in the preparations of these events. The argument is that the local economies, in most cases, do not feel the economic gains that had been anticipated during the bidding process. As a result, the economic benefits generated have been overestimated without focusing on other issues, such as the legacy that these mega-sporting events will leave after the events are over (De Aragao, 2015). In this respect, there is a need for the countries staging mega-sporting events to have a cost analysis and proper planning to ensure that the country derives many benefits from the events.

According to Henderson (2014), unlike in Qatar, when the United States of America hosted the World Cup in 1994, France in 1998, and Germany in 2006, the countries did sufficient planning to construct their stadiums. Furthermore, they confirmed that the kind of stadiums built should be used in the future, after the end of the mega-sporting event. Therefore, these countries can use their fields used in the World Cup for their robust domestic leagues (Cotton and Welden, 2014, p. 10). In the case of the United States of America, the country is one of the leading in the sporting world, with its leagues being in the top ten regarding annual attendance. Moving on to Germany, the nation's league features in the top ten in the world. The Bundesliga League commands more than 13 million individuals that attend every year to support their clubs (Hague and Breitbach, 2011, p. 23).

Furthermore, France is a country that has one of the best leagues in the world. The leagues also feature in the top twenty globally, and command eight million attendants every year, with spectators averaging approximately 21,000 for every event held (Hague and Breitbach, 2011, p. 23). French and German stadiums have a significant advantage in that they are leading beneficiaries of the Champions League and the European Championship. These games are the most well attended in the whole world, as they command many viewers from different parts of the world (Hague and Breitbach, 2011, p. 24). These statistics indicate that some countries have made efficient use of the World Cup finals and continued to enjoy the economic gains linked with the staging of mega-sporting events for the host country. The countries illustrated above have strong leagues across the world. By investing in the construction of stadiums, the nations can still gain long-term economic benefits from the stadiums, as their home leagues use these stadiums.

There are concerns regarding using public money to pay for the development and redevelopment of the private sport team stadiums. The municipalities will have to finance these costs. Based on Hall (2015, p. 4), several of the cities that have previously hosted the mega-sporting event would not be able to pay the rising bills for their stadiums. The resulting maintenance costs will have to be paid annually and will come from taxpayers. This means that public resources will have to be spent on renovating the stadiums that are not in use. This further leads to economic waste and continual use of tax revenue that could have otherwise been used for other vital projects beneficial to the public (Viehoff and Poynter, 2015, p. 214). The evaluation defines the risks and the potential profits of the event.

The use of national funds has created another financial debate on whether the funds meant to provide critical services to the public are being misused to host international events. Funds from the public and taxes are extensively employed in supporting infrastructures that are not directly

profitable to the public, such as the stadiums. Events are used as boosting strategies to assuage de-industrialisation problems or lack of visibility around the globe (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 16). Based on the information presented by Schuessler (2011, p. 81), most of the infrastructure resources come from public funds because private investors are not willing to invest in facilities that are associated with mega-sporting events, because they are less inclined to benefit from these infrastructures directly. Most of this extra budget comes from the government, and as a result, the public bears these costs through tax (Müller, 2016, p. 23). The financial burden, unless distributed among different stakeholders, becomes a challenge to the government. Building stadiums that can withstand the high pressure associated with the international event are challenging. The probability of returns from the investments is not assured, thereby discouraging private investors. Therefore, unless the state has prepared and preserved resources for the event, it could be detrimental when evaluated from the perspective of economic gains or losses. Qatar needs to be assured that the funds spent will be channelled back into the economy. Proper evaluation of the situation needs to be conducted to avoid future problems.

3.8.3 Legacy Planning

Bramwell (1997, p. 213) illustrates that it is more prudent to ensure appropriate planning by reviewing activities before and after a mega-sporting event. He suggests that strategic planning ensures that significant issues associated with the events before, during, and after the events are all considered. The work of Bramwell and others in the 1990s was crucial in identifying key activities that occur during and after a mega-sporting event, which is critical to identifying possible benefits, risks, and uncertainties, and the human rights issues that may arise. It is essential for legacy planning to be part of the bidding to ensure that the mega-sporting event is sustainable.

Horne (2014, p. 4) provides the distinctions for the World Cup legacies. First, some legacies can be tangible. For instance, he considers changes that are related to the material infrastructure. On the other hand, intangible legacies can refer to, for example, the emotional response towards the World Cup finals. The second distinction concerning legacies is that they can be selective; they often serve the interest of influential people, especially those in political and economic positions. On the other hand, universal legacies exist whereby they are available to all in a collective and collectivist manner.

Horne (2014) explains that the legacy of the World Cup is to try and define the success of the event. In this regard, there is a specific outline given for every single player that is involved. Consequently, based on the arguments presented by Todd and Jewell (2016, p. 18), many countries trying to win the bid to stage mega-sporting events link these events to various economic gains; however, economists have criticised the events because of previous research on the implications of hosting the Olympic Games and the World Cup. The findings of the research indicated that nations hosting mega-sporting events gain minimal economic benefits. Moreover, the only financial benefit that the host nation can gain involves legacy. As a result, the economists cannot quantify the effect of the goodwill and legacy of the event.

Kahane and Shmanske (2012, p. 18) add that when it comes to the fans, the staging of a successful event is associated with a notion of well-maintained international standard services that promote the comfort of each participant and fan. When it comes to the governments, the success of the World Cup events can be measured through an increase in the amount of tax collected, the wealth generated, reputational gains, and visibility gains (Raed, 2014, p. 7). For the people of the host country, World Cup events can be regarded as successful if they were organised with less waste of public resources, especially if there was transparency in the management of the resources,

and the ability to leave legacies that involve sufficient investments involving infrastructure among many others (Horne, 2014, p. 8). Finally, for the organisers of the events, the World Cup finals could only be regarded as successful if all the stakeholders' goals were achieved. This involves the government successfully staging the events, the fans, and the society.

Legacy here means the various impacts that are expected to emerge because of hosting an event. This calls for countries hosting mega-sporting events to create sustainable event legacies (Holt and Ruta, 2015, p. 34). For this to happen, the host must understand what to include and what to avoid. One of the outcomes that the host country needs to consider have been discussed include the fact That resources disappear after the events have been held. According to Barrios, Russell, and Andrews (2016, p. 7), supranational organisations such as the International Organization Committee finance some of the operations that are involved when the host country is preparing to host mega-sporting events such as the World Cup. After the events have been successfully held, the resources are no longer provided. The country must incur the costs of maintaining the infrastructures used during the events. Consequently, based on the evidence presented by Holmes et al. (2015), these mega-sporting events are costly and exceed the budget estimated for the reparation of the events. For instance, every Olympic game that has been held since 1960 has exceeded the initial budget. As a result, more money is diverted from other projects to prepare the venues for the events. Furthermore, Müller (2016) demonstrates that mega-sporting events have been associated with event seizure. The seizure of the events has been classified into three dimensions.

3.8.4 The Legal Dimension

The nation's rules may no longer apply in a global event seizure, and the event requirements take pre-eminence. The primary requirements of the events commonly overrule the country's legal

procedures (Müller, 2016, p. 34). When the events are closer and demand some urgency of ensuring that construction and preparations are finished, it is more probable that the rule of law will be undermined by mega-sporting events (Holt and Ruta, 2015, p. 12). Furthermore, it takes substantial time to divert these venues into other significant uses and more time for the new service to generate enough income (Viehoff and Poynter, 2016, p. 218). Consequently, structures such as stadiums will require large amounts of money for maintenance purposes, which are costly to the nation.

Holmes et al. (2015, p. 38) provide a suitable example by illustrating that, in England, the organisers of the London Olympics analysed the game activities, analysed the most appropriate programs, and designed these programs to facilitate adequate employment opportunities from the event. They found that most of the programs they had implemented would not work after the events were over. However, the programs were suitable to be adopted by the private sector. In the case of Qatar, Brannagan and Giulianotti (2015, p. 707) illustrate that as Qatar is concerned with its global consciousness and its primary pursuit of soft power, significant issues revolve around how the stadiums will be used after the World Cup events. The term 'global consciousness' is a concept that refers to the way various states imagine being within a worldwide context. Global consciousness, for instance, underpins how various national governments get involved with international sport, especially when bidding to be given a chance to stage major mega-sporting events such as the World Cup. These events provide the host countries with suitable opportunities to construct new brand identities for global audiences. As a result, these events can be used by the host nations to achieve national and foreign policy objectives. For instance, when Qatar staged the 2006 Asian Games, the country was able to have a great demonstration of global consciousness through a celebration of national culture, the identity of Asians, and enhanced national creativity. Regarding the soft power pursuit, this term refers to strengthening the reputation in international society

through successful leadership. Through successful appeal and attraction, the country is, therefore, able to shape others' preferences. This is something that Qatar aims to facilitate through a suitable mechanism during mega-sporting events.

However, despite the anticipated global consciousness and the soft power pursuit, the countries expect most mega-sporting events to create what is regarded as 'white elephant' facilities. These facilities are not used, or rather, they are underutilised. In preparation for the 2022 World Cup events, Qatar is building nine new stadiums. Similarly, in Durban, South Africa, a major concern revolved around the sustainability of the ten stadiums constructed to host the 2010 World Cup (Alegi and Bolsmann, 2013, p. 16). The point is that these stadiums could become costly white elephants regarding maintenance, adding that the municipalities will have to bear the cost of financing these ventures. A good number of the cities that hosted the mega-sporting event would not be able to pay the rising bills for their stadiums in the next period of 30 years, and the costs of maintenance that are paid annually will have to come from the taxpayer (Rowe, 2011, p. 1). The former South Africa director of the soccer premier league posed a critical question when he asked:

“What the hell are we going to do with the 70,000-seater football stadium in the city of Durban when the World Cup events are over? Durban city has got only two football teams that can attract a crowd of a few thousand people. It could have been necessary if the country could have planned well and assessed the sustainability of these stadiums after the events. They could have constructed more minor stadiums nearer the heartlands known to be football-loving, and the surplus funds could be used to build the facilities used for training purposes in the townships” (Viehoff and Poynter, 2015, p. 214).

Viehoff and Poynter's report show that despite the goodwill to have stadiums that can accommodate the demands of the World Cup, further analyses are required to establish the viability

of such projects. The risks of having stadiums that are not useful are high since a country is only allowed to host the event once in a long time.

The Rugby Union President of South Africa, Reagan Hoskins, highly criticised individuals involved with the management of Moses Mabhida Stadium because they could not implement an appropriate plan before engaging in the construction of the stadium (Rowe, 2011, p. 2). According to the South Africa cricket C.E.O., that new stadium could have been used for the hockey games, but instead, it is too small, which meant that hockey games could not be played there. In this regard, the C.E.O. blamed the authorities for failing to consider other sporting activities that could have used the stadium instead of being idle after the 2010 World Cup games (Rowe, 2011, p. 2). In this regard, Qatar is prone to be exposed to that kind of danger whereby the stadiums will have no meaningful use after the mega-sporting event. As a result, Qatar decided to ensure that this inevitable problem should be facilitated through Qatar's soft power. Soft power is a conceptual term used to illustrate how the authorities in Qatar are looking forward to using the international importance of staging the first World Cup ever to be held in the Middle East to correct the negative aspects of their image within the international arena. The country aims to achieve this by showcasing itself as a state that respects human rights and is sport loving (Brannagan and Grix, 2014, p. 708). Through such positive images, the country will reasonably expect to host other events and improve global politics.

Through successful appeal and attraction, the country can shape others' preferences. This is something that Qatar aims to facilitate through a suitable mechanism during mega-sporting events and enhance power through the commitment of its authorities in the construction of modular stadiums. These stadiums can be constructed and easily disassembled at any convenient time. According to the respondents in Brannagan and Gulianotti (2015, p. 708) research, these stadiums

can be dismantled and presented to other nations, such as those in Africa, to aid in their development. Johnston (2014, p. 33) further notes that the principal aim of the construction of the modular stadiums was to ensure stadiums were semi-permanent. That means that they will be disassembled and taken to other parts of the world, especially in countries that are still developing to construct 22 stadiums that can be used for hosting the World Cup. Johnston (2014, p. 34) illustrates that this was a strategy to ensure that there is the balanced growth of football across the world with long-lasting positive effects. However, this has not practically been successful since most nations in developing countries do not have the capacity to stage these events in order to reap the positive benefits enjoyed in developed countries hosting these events.

Holmes (2015, p. 123) demonstrates that, during the bidding process, the benefits that are inclined to accrue to the hosting country are always inflated and do not materialise in the long run. Therefore, the forecasted benefits to the host country are an untrue science. For instance, the figure predicted in the World Cup events held in South Africa confirms that the forecasting science is not exact, because the estimations were never achieved. Based on the number of tourists estimated to arrive in South Africa, the number was less than one third. This led to low tourist revenues being experienced (3.64 billion Rand), far below the anticipated 8.9 billion-rand revenues (Holmes, 2015, p. 123). Accordingly, it is impossible to foresee all the profits and losses that can be incurred.

Based on Shand's work (2017, p. 9), the economic impact highly linked to the staging of mega-sporting events needs to be evaluated more carefully to determine whether benefits can be realised from the investments made. Shand (2017, p. 10) continues to show that studies have demonstrated that hosting mega-sporting events, such as the Olympic Games, may result in less economic impact than anticipated. Even though many jobs are created during the event, the effect produced on incomes is not detectable. Therefore, this suggests that the workers do not benefit in

any way. The impact that is likely to be experienced in hosting the events depends on the response of the overall labour market to the new jobs that the games have created.

Moreover, these impacts are inclined to not be positive. Therefore, the economic impact of these games on the host nation is more negligible (Wagner, 2015, p. 23). There is a lack of sufficient evidence to support the claims that definite economic impacts are derived from hosting mega-sporting events (Barrios, Russell, and Andrews, 2016, p. 12). The sparse literature conducted between 1990 and 2010 concerning the economic benefits of staging mega-sporting events outlined no meaningful, lasting economic benefits. One possible explanation illustrated that investing in mega-sporting events does not tackle the various binding constraints that limit the growth of the host nation. Consequently, the authors present their arguments that cities interested are anticipated to lose long-term benefits during the highly competitive bidding process. The investments required to win the bid and the costs incurred during the preparations of the events are possible to be larger than the benefits that have been purported (Barrios, Russell, and Andrews, 2016, p. 13). These events could, therefore, be associated with positive effects. For instance, one positive effect is improved road infrastructure which can result in improved transportation.

The use of mega-sporting events as an effective suitable cultural diplomacy tool is increasing (Wagner, 2015, p. 23). The government of Qatar engaged in a commitment to integrate cultural diplomacy which was driven by establishing an elite identity narrative for the country as a cohesive society, rightfully engaged, and future-oriented in international affairs locally and internationally (Sulayem, O'Connor, and Hassan, 2013, p. 34). That concept is well explained by Brannagan and Gulianotti (2015, p. 709) through soft power and soft disempowerment. The soft power concept is based on the ability of the country to attract what it wants rather than paying for it. For instance,

Qatar intends to use an attractive, incredible culture and desirable ideologies and policies. According to Eggeling (2016, p. 7), within the global context, culture is essential. It is an excellent representation of the pursuit of power that is highly notable through sport, media, and arts, among many others. When nations host mega-sporting events, the national governments are presented with suitable opportunities to increase their soft power (Cull, 2008, p. 121). This is achieved through the cultural showcasing which is done through television. This leads to tourist attraction, as well as augmenting the pride of the nation. For instance, the Beijing Olympics held in 2008 increased China's soft power through the mega-sporting events that were successfully held. The advancing messages that were used for advertisement purposes emphasised the culture of ancient China and its civilisation. This led to China gaining prestige and topping the table with its medals. This was an excellent opportunity for the host nation to show its willingness to support international cooperation through sport.

3.9 The Role of Event Owners in Influencing Mega-Sporting Events Bidding

According to Grix (2013, p. 4), there was a time when countries did not know the benefits that are associated with staging mega-sporting events. FIFA and I.O.C. had to take great responsibility in convincing different countries that were highly reluctant to try to host the events which involved the football World Cup, the Paralympic Games, and the Olympic Games. However, in the last 30 years, a revolution has been experienced. The political salience among governments has continually increased concerning the multiple benefits that mega-sporting events generate for the country. Developing nations such as Qatar, China, India, Russia, Brazil, Bahrain, and the U.A.E. have higher growth rates than their western counterparts due to the lack of democratic systems and the lack of social contrasts between the people and their leaders when legitimacy and resources are not a problem. Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson (2012, p. 15) further expound

that the bidding process in western nations undergoes a rigorous process that requires accountability, consensus building, and extensive consultation.

They regard mega-sporting events as a cheap means of improving the country's image in the global arena, enhancing the country's economic competitiveness, credibility, and stature (Grix and Lee, 2013, p. 4). The organisers of these events, therefore, play an essential role in trying to ensure that there is equity in their decisions concerning the country that must stage these events (that is, World Cup finals as well as the Olympics) (Sulayem, O'Connor, and Hassan, 2013, p. 36). In addition, members of the awarding Committee want to secure their legacy by awarding hosting rights not based on technical capacity but based on racial harmony, world peace, and international diplomacy (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 27).

Initially, the events were customarily held in states that are wealthy western nations. This has continued for an extended period until recently when mega-sport event organisations, that is FIFA and the I.O.C., decided to shift their focus and offer developing countries a chance to stage the games so that they are able to receive the development benefits that were received by developed nations (Zimbalist, 2016, p. 45). This has made a good number of developing countries enter the competition. Even those events regarded as the second-order mega-sporting events, such as the Commonwealth Games and the Pan American Games, have experienced a substantial number of states bidding to hold these games because they understand the prestige and benefits associated with the staging of these games.

Zimbalist (2016, p. 46) illustrates that the grappling has resulted in the situation being experienced today, involving competition between the developed states and the developing states to win the bid for staging the events. As demonstrated, the most popular states, for instance, the United Kingdom, were willing to offer £17 million to influence a win in the staging of the 2022

World Cup finals. However, contrary to expectations, Qatar was able to win the bid and accorded the privilege of staging the events. Qatar is a developing nation in the Middle East but won the bid against other developed countries such as the United Kingdom (Grix and Lee, 2013, p. 8). In this regard, the event organisations have devised an effective strategy that could see all nations, including those in the Middle East, compete for their chance to host the events and receive the developmental benefits that are generated to the host nation.

The neglected dimensions in the developing countries have been covered efficiently, and they are open to competition for staging these events. This is because there is an increasing rivalry due to the emergence of new players. This includes China which produced the Olympic Games in 2008; South Africa, which staged the 2010 World Cup finals; India, which directed the Commonwealth Games that were held in 2010; Brazil which hosted the 2014 World Cup, and Qatar, which has been given the privilege of hosting the 2022 World Cup. Those countries were given a chance because their various dimensions were covered and analysed within their level of development by the event organisers (Grix and Lee, 2013, p. 4). Therefore, they can understand that the developing states are experiencing some challenges, but this does not hinder them from hosting mega-sporting events. For this case, Middle East countries have a more significant privilege in securing their bids to host these mega-sporting events.

The best example is in South Africa. This country is one of the nations that was least expected to stage a mega-sporting event. The state had taken a considerable risk by inviting the media from different parts of the world to have four-week scrutiny of the country. It is well known that South Africa has 49% of its population below the poverty line, 25% of the South Africa population is not employed, they have a high rate of H.I.V. infection of 18%, and a higher rate of crime related

issues, among many other problems (Grix and Lee, 2013, p. 16). However, South Africa was still considered to host the 2010 World Cup games (Zeemering, 2013, p. 56).

Consequently, despite all the country's negative factors, the commentators in the World Cup bids gave kind remarks about the country. The state is put on the world map to fulfil one of their central foreign policy goals, and these presented South Africa as a global middle power. Furthermore, many research studies conducted in South Africa have indicated that among the visitors who come to South Africa, most allude that they had a successful socialising process in South Africa. As a result, the process changed the negative perceptions that they had about the country. According to Zeemering (2013, p. 58), 309,000 visitors could attend the 2010 World Cup in South Africa. 51% of these tourists suggested that they had never thought they would visit the country if not for the finals held there. Furthermore, these individuals agreed to return to South Africa as a tourist destination even after the events were over. There is some evidence, therefore, which suggests that the country has been able to attract a significant number of tourists as people are willing to visit the first African state to host the World Cup finals.

Brazil represents another example of a developing country that has had the privilege to hold several activities. It has managed to showcase itself by staging mega-sporting events such as the Pan African games held in 2007, World Cup finals held in 2014, and the Olympic Games held in 2016 (Glanville, 2014, p. 5). This has extended Brazil's exposure in a global context. Winning the bidding process for such mega-sporting events sends out several positive inclusion signals and a better acceptance rate within the international arena. Winning the bids in two short successions sends a substantial message to other developing countries, as it shows that FIFA and I.O.C. trust the country, and Brazil can put on several other successful events despite being a developing country. This has made the country move from the regional level to the global level by hosting mega-

sporting events (Grix and Lee, 2013, p. 15). The Middle East must keep in mind that the rise of Brazil is not in any way associated with its economy. However, this can be attributed to its political influence, as demonstrated in the examples observed with China and South Africa. The Middle East has several problems that can be regarded as a significant hindrance towards winning the bid for staging these events. However, these challenges are within their development levels, and critical analysis and scrutiny can still allow them to hold the events. Therefore, their efforts to champion the chance at the competition are growing. Event organisers involving FIFA and I.O.C. are always ready to consider them, bearing in mind that Qatar was considered against many other well-developed nations. Therefore, this can be replicated in Middle East countries.

3.10 Qatar's Positioning in International Human Rights and Labour Laws

The table below, presented in Figure 2, shows Qatar's ratification status for 18 international human rights treaties. Two international conventions were signed pre-2000: i) one for eliminating all forms of racial discrimination, ratified in 1976, and ii) one on children's rights, ratified in 1995. However, most of the international conventions and covenants on human rights were signed by Qatar within the 21st century in the post-2000 period. The leading international human rights covenants on i) civil and political rights (ICCPR) and ii) economic, social, and cultural rights (ICESCR) were both ratified with reservations upon accession, by Qatar, in 2018, thus becoming a party to nine international human rights documents, which imply the state's willingness to respect the provisions within them, including labour rights, among others. It is worth noting that the reservation made by Qatar under the ICESCR specifically touches upon the purpose of this thesis, because the reservation does not allow migrant workers to form trade unions:

The State of Qatar shall interpret that the term 'trade unions' and all related matters, as mentioned in Article 22 of the Covenant, is in line with the Labour Law and national legislation.

The State of Qatar reserves the right to implement such an article per such understanding (Qatar Declaration at the ratification of the ICCPR).

Qatar STATUS OF RATIFICATION of 18 International Human Rights Treaties

Human Rights <u>Instrument</u> : (Date into force)	Ratification Status	Declaration
International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination :1969	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 1976	
International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights :1976	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 2018	✓
Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights :1976	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
Second Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, aiming at the abolition of the death penalty :1991	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights :1976	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 2018	✓
Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights :2013	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women :1981	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 2009	✓
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women :2000	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment :1987	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 2000	✓
Optional Protocol to the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment :2006	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
Convention on the Rights of the Child :1990	Signature: 1992, Ratification/Accession: 1995	✓
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict :2002	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 2002	✓
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography :2002	Signature: NA, Ratification/Accession: 2001	
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on a communications procedure :2014	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of their Families :2003	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
International Convention for the Protection of all Persons from Enforced Disappearance :2010	<u>Signature</u> : NA, Ratification/Accession: NA	
Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities :2008	Signature: 2007, Ratification/Accession: 2008	
Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities :2008	Signature: 2007, Ratification/Accession: NA	

Figure 2: Qatar’s Status of Ratification of International Human Rights Treaties

The International Justice Resource Centre states that ‘although Qatar's accession to the ICCPR and ICESCR are positive advancements to promote and protect human rights within the country, the reservations and statements on interpretation will disproportionately affect women and migrant workers, who make up at least 90% of the working population’ (IJRC, 2018).

Another concern, despite the ratification of the international conventions, is that Qatar has

not accepted the individual complaint procedure for either of the treaty bodies, meaning that individuals are not allowed to file a complaint alleging that Qatar is not fulfilling its obligations under a specific convention. Hosting a mega-sporting event will remain in history, either in statistical yearbooks, in world records books, in international agreements, communication letters, tickets, and even people's living memory. However, Qatar may not necessarily be solely interested in one mega-sporting event. Other mega-sporting events can bring the same historical prestige to a host country. For example, Qatar was expected to host the Fifth United Nations Conference in March 2021, for the Least Developed Countries (LDC-V), but the conference has been postponed. This Conference is considered a mega-sporting event in the international political arena, as it will occur at the highest possible level, including Heads of State and Government. This fact shows us the interest of Qatar not only in mega-sporting events, but also in international political events. The Conference will adopt the following programme of action for Least Developed Countries (L.D.Cs) for the next ten years, 2021-2030. The United Nations Resolution A/RES/74/232, from 23 January 2020, pointed out that it 'welcomes and accepts with appreciation the generous offer of the Government of Qatar to host the LDC-V in Doha' (UN A/RES/74/232, para 45). Since the Conference will take place in Doha, the mentioned programme of action was called the 'Doha Programme of Action for L.D.C.s' and thus referred to in hundreds of international documents to follow. The political and historical impact of mega-sporting events is enormous. The exact effect is taking place at the historical, political, and cultural level, in the case of mega-sporting events, such as the 2022 FIFA World Cup. The Conference and its programme of action will touch upon such topics as trade, structural economic transformation, energy, environment, and decent work. Qatar shows international support towards the agenda that will be discussed at the Conference and implicitly supports international human rights by hosting such an event.

3.11 International Human Rights and Mega-Sporting Events: Positive Impacts

The organisation of mega-sporting events can be of benefit for national and international human rights. We have seen in section 3.6 that mega-sporting events can bring positive progress for women in sport competitions, including in Qatar, with the development of the 2001 Women's Sports Committee. Progress towards improved women's rights within sport competitions is also progressing towards the achievement of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), adopted in 1979 by the UN General Assembly, where provision (g) or article 10 stipulates that woman should have 'the same opportunities to participate actively in sport and physical education'. Heather Sykes' volume on *The Sexual and Gender Politics of Sport Mega-Events* explores the research on women in mega-sporting events. In *Roving Colonialism* (2017) Sykes scrutinises gender and sexuality in the arena of neo-colonial SME politics. Regarding the positive image of mega-sporting events in Qatar, it is noted that:

Qatar's emerging events strategy has brought it closer to its Western democratic counterparts, built, as it is, around a new emphasis on equality of sport participation for women and greater citizen rights (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, p. 101).

The Paralympics are also an example of mega-sporting events in response to international human rights conventions, such as the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination, adopted in 1965 by the UN General Assembly; and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD), adopted in 2006. The latter contains specific provisions regarding the right of persons with disabilities to access sporting activities and where the state parties need to take appropriate measures to promote such activities and allow for a unique setting to develop such activities (CRPD, Article 30 – Participation in cultural life, recreation, leisure, and sport). Amara elaborates on the roles of sport and education in the social inclusion of

asylum seekers and refugees, and that sport inclusion at local, regional, or community-wide levels contributes to the elimination of discrimination (Amara, 2005).

Furthermore, competition slogans become more and more attractive, maintaining the image of a celebration event. The mega-sporting events slogans seek to emphasise a positive image of global enthusiasm for sporting events. For example, 'A time to make friends' was the official slogan of the 2006 FIFA World Cup in Germany. Another positive slogan was also, 'Hot. Cool. Yours.', the official motto of the 2014 Winter Olympics in Sochi, illustrating that such events are not only about competing but also about coming together as friends.

3.12 International Human Rights and Mega-Sporting Events: Negative Impacts

Planning, organising, and hosting a mega-sporting event also implies that negative impacts may occur on human rights. However, we have seen in the previous section that positive outcomes from mega-sporting events are present. The following section will elaborate on human rights challenges and abuses reported in the past, which may happen during a mega-sporting event. For example, the fear of racist violence in Russian host cities at the 2014 Winter Olympics in Sochi, and the Circassian anti-Sochi protests received media attention and negatively impacted the competitions where social inequalities persisted.

3.12.2 Mega-Sporting Events, Human Trafficking, and Forced Labour

Based on the information presented by Hepburn (2017, p. 21), human trafficking and forced labour is regarded as modern slavery related to mega-sporting events and tends to follow a prescriptive pattern. The recruiters promise the workers outstanding salaries with suitable working conditions. However, when the workers reach the destination countries, their passports are withheld, and they are customarily underpaid. The workers cannot pay a large number of fees and therefore find themselves in the bondage of debt. They are left in very vulnerable positions; they

do not have the money or anything to identify themselves. Therefore, this gives the employers a large amount of power over the workers. Workers involved with the construction of various facilities used during mega-sporting events are exposed to poor working conditions, live in labour camps that are highly crowded with unsanitary conditions, and have little access to healthcare, which is a significant violation of human rights (Hepburn, 2017, p. 24). Employers continuously threaten the workers with deportation to make them comply with their demands. This results in the workers' rights being profoundly violated because the workers are pushed beyond their physical limits. According to Hepburn (2017, p. 25), countries are moving towards shorter enslavement periods. It usually affects the need for the victim's survival; killing a slave is cheaper than purchasing medicine for the slave. Therefore, the action is a significant infraction of human rights.

The risk associated with human trafficking and forced labour are issues found in almost every part of the mega-sporting events chain, including the supply chain and several other major business activities closely linked with the preparations that are put in place in trying to stage the event. It is possible to involve the private sectors, for instance, in providing the manufacturer's apparel and other equipment used in sport, the event-linked merchandise, and the hospitality delivery and several other services needed during the mega-sporting event (Jones, 2017, p. 2). A critical area with a higher level of risk lies in the contracts offered by the government when new stadiums are being constructed and, at the same time, building the supporting infrastructure and renovating the already existing infrastructure. That may come under scrutiny because there is the probability of human rights being violated through human trafficking and lucrative crime that is very complex. The global estimate of forced labour conducted in 2012 by the International Labour Organization (ILO) illustrates that 20.9 million individuals are in various forced labour situations across the world.

Moreover, a higher percentage of these people (68%) who are in the labour exploitation situation are in a broad array of economic sectors which involve agriculture, the apparel industry, the manufacturing industry, the mining industry, and the construction industry, among many others. Additionally, according to the report on *Profits and Poverty* that the ILO presented in 2014, the forced labour economics identified that the forced labour which is employed in the private economy results in an illegal profit approximated to be US \$150 billion every year (Institute for Human Rights and Business, 2017, p. 7). Such unlawful actions must be mitigated in a free world, and Qatar will prove its commitment to promoting world freedom.

Mega-sporting events involve the massive construction of infrastructure, with a more significant percentage of this infrastructure being the stadiums used during the events. This drives higher demand for highly effective labour, materials to be used in the construction of the stadiums and the venues where the events will occur. Unfortunately, mega-sporting events provide an opportunity to exploit labour from several unscrupulous employers (Chadwick, Chanavat, and Desbordes, 2015, p. 175). Human trafficking and forced labour have been experienced in constructing facilities ahead of the games being prepared for (Jones, 2017, p. 3). In recent years, concerns on the issue of human trafficking have been on the increase due to human rights abuses related to mega-sporting events. For instance, Greece experienced a high level of human trafficking, up to 95% during its preparations for the 2004 Athens Olympics. The case resulted in the death of 14 people, and more than 1,000 people were seriously injured within the construction sites where the Olympic Games were to be held. FIFA led a primary anti-trafficking campaign in the 2006 World Cup held in Germany, whereby women were victims of a higher chance of falling under human trafficking purposely for sexual exploitation.

The 2014 FIFA World Cup that was held in Brazil involved cases of sexual exploitation. Consequently, FIFA documented several cases involving forced labour which was experienced in the construction sites, and the human trafficking risk that the temporary and migrant workers were facing because of the preparations for the 2016 Rio Olympics. These claims are due to the increasing concerns that slave labour conditions were being used in constructing the Cyrela house that was meant for the journalists reporting on the Olympics (Institute for Human Rights and Business, 2017, p. 8). The issues raised implied that a free world was not promoted.

In Qatar, the situation of people trafficking is more subject to forced labour where ‘the foreign worker migrates to Qatar legally for low-and semi-skilled work but often experiences situations of forced labour, including debt bondage, and delayed non-payment of salaries’ (CIA Factbook on Qatar, 2015). It is stipulated that Qatar does not fully comply with the minimum standards for the elimination of trafficking. Still, it does make a significant effort to do so. For instance, Qatar’s ‘authorities visited worksites throughout the country to meet and educate workers and employers on trafficking regulations’ and investigated trafficking cases but did not prosecute or convict any offenders; ‘the primary solution for resolving labour violations was to transfer a worker’s sponsorship to a new employer’ (CIA Factbook on Qatar, 2015).

As well as adhering to human rights, labour laws, human trafficking and forced labour regulations, another critical area that countries hosting a mega-sporting event should consider is the protection of children’s rights from abuse, as evaluated below.

3.12.3 Mega-Sporting Events and Abuse of Children’s Rights

The documentation on child labour has been associated with mega-sporting events in several ways. The various supply chains of the event sponsors have been accused of child labour during construction and delivery. Children are regularly used and harmed in construction work

and therefore left with serious injuries (Akrivopoulou, 2017, p. 2). Consequently, Akrivopoulou (2017, p. 3) demonstrates that construction work has a significant impact on children as it also violates their rights to access and having good health and quality education. The worst kind of child labour involves commercial sex exploitation, and mega-sporting events have always exacerbated this through many visitors into the host country. Child labour is a serious issue as children are deprived of their childhood, quality of health and education, denying them the only opportunity to realise their full potential, and thus trapped in poverty for life.

For instance, there are several cases providing evidence on the issue of child labour. Before the 2012 Olympics held in London, there were increasing concerns raised about the factory in China that had secured a contract to supply mascot toys to the Olympic events. Four years earlier, evidence was revealed that children aged 12 years and below were involved in the production of Olympic merchandise used in the 2008 Olympic Games held in Beijing. Children were also part of the workforce manufacturing the Olympic logo goods that were used in the 2004 Olympic Games held in Greece. Minors were used despite the legislation against child labour. In India and Pakistan, young children were employed in hand stitching the soccer balls used in the 1998 World Cup hosted by France (Mega-Sporting Events Platform for Human Rights, 2017a, p. 9). The employment of young children is a violation of international standards and denies the children their fundamental human rights.

When mega-sporting events are held in the towns of the hosting country, it comes with a massive influx of people. Some of these people may pose a significant threat to the children in the host country. Evidence has shown that when mega-sporting events are held in countries with higher poverty and inequality levels, child abuse is extreme. Mega-sporting events organisers are under pressure to clear the streets to retain the positive image of the country. In an attempt at trying to

clean up the city, these children are displaced from the city. For instance, during the World Cup final held in South Africa, the preparations for the kick-off of the events saw street children being relocated to other camps 30 kilometres away from the streets of Cape Town. Several other reports indicated that the youths were arrested and charged with loitering, with onerous penalties that the authorities were sure they could not afford. In this regard, they were held till the events were over. In addition, before the 2007 preliminary draw that FIFA in which South Africa participated, the children in the streets were taken to Westville Prison, where they were housed. They were exposed to some form of violence and rape, among many other cases of abuse. The displacement of children from the streets has been a significant concern for child welfare advocates.

There are reports where children who participate in mega-sporting events are exposed to violations. For instance, child athletes have encountered several cases of violation and abuse. Children also face other risks related to sport and may involve overtraining, exploitation, and doping issues. The number of children whose rights are violated has increased in recent years and calls for a closer look at the situation.

The preparation process, hosting, and post-event activities of a mega-sporting event are constantly accused of corruption issues during the construction, tendering and contracting process, which is also linked with the abuse of human rights, as illustrated in the section below.

3.12.4 Mega-Sporting Events and Corruption Issues

Corruption is a significant issue that is linked to the abuse of human rights. Countries at the bottom end of Transparency International's Corruption Perception Scandal are customarily regarded as countries that do not protect human rights. If a state cannot guarantee the rule of law, it cannot in any way ensure the population their fundamental rights (Getz and Page, 2016). Consequently, Getz and Page continue to illustrate that if there are corrupt practices that a company

engages in, then the company reduces its ability to protect people's rights whenever it is carrying out its principal operations. For example, in preparation for mega-sporting events, individuals may become involved in taking bribes from the organisers of the events, which includes the officials who are members of IOC, and at the FIFA congress where the FIFA delegates are involved in examining the bids that countries have made. As a result of bribery, the officials are inclined to make choices that favour a particular country.

As illustrated by IHRB (2014, p. 6), corruption is experienced in companies trying to secure contracts and win tenders. In mega-sporting events, this typically involves the tenders to supply the sporting goods. Here, the officials influence the decisions made on the company to be awarded a contract due to influence. For instance, the Commonwealth Games held in Delhi in 2010 were surrounded by corruption issues. The result of this saw a pedestrian bridge that had been newly constructed breaking down during the opening ceremony. Also, during the Olympic events held in Rio de Janeiro, the tender for a track built for bicycle usage during the Olympic Games was faced with some bribery issues. As a result, the track collapsed, resulting in the death of two individuals. This demonstrated that the construction lacked quality because the contract had been awarded through corruption to a company that did not have the capacity of completing good quality work (Li, Macintosh, and Bravo, 2012, p. 4). The implication is that corrupt deals only enrich a few whiles destroying the vital part of the life of the majority.

One of the main activities, when a country is preparing to host a mega-sporting event, is construction. Construction ranges from stadiums, housing facilities, tourist sites, hotels, roads, metro systems, and even airports, as the country prepares to host millions of people from across the world. The section below reviews the relationship between mega-sporting events, land acquisition and housing issues.

3.12.5 Mega-Sporting Events, Land Acquisition, and Housing Issues

Regarding land acquisition and housing, the land is a significant resource that people use, both government and communities. When a country has been accorded the privilege of hosting a mega-sporting event, they need to access land. Host countries usually want to establish landmark monuments, particularly for the events, and at the same time, construct and expand public infrastructure. Individual developers have significant interests in establishing new facilities or building new residential homes (Frawley, 2016, p. 33). Despite all this, many families want a safe place where they can live. Therefore, they do not wish to have abrupt changes in their lives, particularly changes that negatively affect their lives. These kinds of demands between the developers and the residents always cause conflict. History illustrates that developments that occur because of the preparations being made for hosting the mega-sporting event typically result in land problems and housing problems due to possible evictions.

Frawley (2016, p. 37) illustrates that, in 2007, the Center on Human Housing Rights and Evictions released the impact report showing the impact that the Olympics, a major mega-sporting event, had on the housing rights of people. The information was published to ensure that the recommendations on the housing rights of people could be integrated into the various stages of a mega-sporting event, starting from the planning of the events up to the period when the events take place. Consequently, the rapporteur of the United Nations concerning adequate housing and several other organisations on expert housing rights have, over many years, consistently catalogued the abuses related to housing rights when it comes to the hosting of mega-sporting events. The industrial nations that are well established and several other growing economies have had experiences of such difficulties. For instance, 30,000 individuals were forcefully moved away from Atlanta when the 1996 Olympic Games were planned. During this period, 1,200 public housing units

were lost. The 15,000 residents who were within the class of low income were forced to leave the city because of the high prices of the new houses. In Beijing, during the preparations for the 2008 Olympic Games, 1.5 million individuals were evicted to ensure that the games were sufficiently prepared (Frawley, 2016, p. 35). The HRW illustrated that there was inadequate compensation during the process. Reports showed that the victims were subjected to usually unannounced night raids. The report on the 2010 Commonwealth Games that were held in New Delhi reveals that 35,000 families were forcefully moved from public lands, among many other examples (IHRB, 2014, p. 6). As a result, the negative implication of the massive extension of the infrastructure is noted.

To promote adherence to international human rights, laws, ethics, and best practices during mega-sporting events, FIFA and IOC, the organisers of the FIFA World Cup and Olympics games, respectively, have come up with regulations and procedures outlining various rules governing hosting of such events. The regulations relate to human rights, corruption, labour laws, children's rights, procurement and supply chain issues, and dispute resolution. In addition, the ethical considerations are evaluated in the section below.

3.12.6 Ethical Considerations

Sport has developed some practices after the increasing concerns of different bodies. The Olympic Agenda of the IOC 2020 reforms have seen new commitments being featured on the equality of gender and non-discrimination by sexual orientation. The IOC code of ethics that was revised in 2016 requires the international conventions to be respected, particularly in protecting human rights. Discussion is underway so that the ILO Declaration can be included in the new subsidiary strategy of the International Olympic Confederation. The Glasgow Commonwealth Games held in 2014 separately published a commitment, the first of its kind, regarding human

rights, and a human rights commission report post games, through an organising committee. Its strategy for procurement included paying a living wage, community clauses, and the highest child safeguarding standards. Despite that, mega-sporting events may not solve all the problems resulting from the abuse of human rights. It can respect the established criteria, recognise, and evade the various potential harms that may occur (IHRB, 2016, p. 6). Events can also create a necessary and suitable space that can facilitate dialogue with all the stakeholders that are concerned and therefore have considerable advantages for the greater good.

First, all states that want to host mega-sporting events must acknowledge the labour and human rights that are internationally recognised. This also includes the fundamental rights of an individual at their place of work. Second, other relevant principles and labour rights that provide guiding principles must be adhered to in the event lifecycle (Tavakkoli, 2016, p. 13). Third, every stage of the mega-sporting event must adequately take account of all human rights. This involves all the due processes involved, such as event bidding, evaluating the bids, planning for the mega-sporting event, delivery, and legacy, among others. These should be based on the principles and standards that have been established, the international instruments, the principles guiding businesses and human rights, the Multinational Enterprise guidelines developed by the OECD, the ILO and the IDFPBW, among several others that IHRB has covered. Fourth, the bodies involved in awarding, the host bidders and their various partners involved in the delivery must address the risks associated with human rights, whether they are inclined to be violated, and significant consideration is done by assessing the anticipated impacts with all due diligence.

Fifth, groups that have been affected because of their human rights being violated merit a voice in making decisions. In this regard, practical ways must be enabled to ensure consultation with individual athletes, workers, fans that have been affected, and the residents, at every stage of

the mega-sporting event, through meaningful and ongoing engagements (IHRB, 2016, p. 9). Sixth, highly effective remedies must be available to all individuals whose human rights have been violated at any given stage during the lifecycle of the mega-sporting event. Seventh, during the mega-sporting event, the lessons that are learned concerning the successes and failures of human rights should be shared so that they are used in improving practices and thus preventing undesirable practices regarding the violation occurrences from being repeated over time in other events (MSEPHR, 2016, p. 6).

The eighth regulation relates to the strengthened human rights capacity of the stakeholders. To determine and address the various risks available and that may result from the violation of these rights, the sports federations, the committees involved in the organisation of these events, and other significant stakeholders involved in foreseeing every stage of these events should have a well-developed knowledge concerning human rights and the different possibilities of violation. They should be ready to seek further advice where possible to avoid overlooking some of the issues that may appear as minor but are massive to the individual victims involved (MSEPHR, 2016, p. 6). Ninth, collective actions should be undertaken from every individual involved in the mega-sporting event to ensure that the events are successful and continue being an excellent source of inspiration for many years to come. Therefore, all stakeholders are accorded an enormous responsibility of ensuring solutions that consistently address the challenges that workers face beyond an individual stakeholder capacity.

The emerging groups noted below carry out several developing practices to create an impact on the various situations that people encounter during the games and take appropriate actions.

FIFA: Since the year 2015, FIFA has been active by being involved with several activities that strengthen its dominant approach towards the issue of human rights. This provides a guideline

on how the events are organised, how competitions are carried out, primarily when a World Cup is hosted. FIFA has added an additional article covering the issue of human rights in its statutes. This was approved on 26 February 2016 when the FIFA Extraordinary Congress was held. In April 2016, the article came into full force. Article three of the statutes that have been revised illustrates that 'FIFA is committed to respecting all internationally recognized human rights and shall strive to promote the protection of these rights' (IHRB, 2017, p. 13). Gianni Infantino, the FIFA President, made a two-day visit to Qatar, which is expected to host the 2022 World Cup finals, in 2017. He made announcements that an oversight body had been created with independent members to oversee the whole process as Qatar makes its preparations, to monitor, and to ensure that there are decent working conditions, and human rights are not violated in any way.

The International Olympic Committee: In December 2014, the IOC launched an 'Olympic Agenda 2020'. This is a strategic roadmap for the IOC for future Olympic events. The plan also includes a commitment to ensure that the Fundamental Principle of Olympism has been strengthened by mainly extending it so that it can provide sufficient cover on the issue of discrimination based on sexual orientation and included in the Olympic Charter. Furthermore, in 2015, a 'Host City Contract' was published for those willing to host the Olympic Games held in 2024 onwards. That was the first time that a contract had been published. There are some provisions that the contract includes, for instance, Principle 13.1 prohibits discrimination by a country, or an individual based on gender, sexual orientation, race, religion, and social origin, among many others. Furthermore, principle 25.1 requires that there should be no restrictions on the media. In this regard, the media should have adequate freedom to provide broader coverage of the mega-sporting event, and the various issues arising about human rights.

In addressing the abuse of children's rights, steps are taken in every mega-sporting event held in the host country. However, in general, Mega-Sporting Events Platform for Human Rights (2017a, p. 15) illustrates that the Ruggie report that FIFA had commissioned includes a special mention directly related to children, their rights, and how they must be respected. Here, children have been mentioned as a highly vulnerable group in mega-sporting events and, therefore, has a higher human risk. The Olympic Agenda 2020 provides an explicit discussion of the principles that the IOC should implement. Furthermore, the transformation 2022 of the Commonwealth Games Federation in partnership with UNICEF included the concerns of child rights in the mega-sporting events held, which require actions that are more concrete on individuals violating these rights. In addition to these measures that specifically targeted safeguarding the children, there is a growing body of learning concerning the various attempts to protect children's rights before and during the mega-sporting events.

Several matters are related to procurement and supply chain issues. Based on IHRB (2017, p. 14), FIFA has made some revisions on the governing statutes involving a reference explicit to human rights. That is the first time that FIFA has made this revision. For many years, FIFA statutes have dealt with rights about membership issues, voting, finance, broadcasting, the laws of copyright, matters related to marketing and competitions and events, among many other problems. An article that is mainly focused on ensuring that human rights has now been safeguarded within the general provisions which now reads that FIFA is highly committed to ensuring that internationally recognised human rights are respected, and it is dedicated to ensuring that it promotes these rights. An article that covers the issue of non-discrimination was also extended to include the issue of gender equality (WFSGI, 2017, p. 19). The inclusion was mainly aimed at reducing the existing forms of discrimination that exist in modern society.

WFSGI (2017, p. 19) illustrates that FIFA has paid attention to procurement and human rights, which has been ongoing for some time. Therefore, WFSGI demonstrates that FIFA is willing to set standards on labour rights that are mandatory. Companies that are willing to do business with FIFA must follow them. WFSGI initially introduced its pledge directed to the FIFA Quality Program, for the various entities that constituted its football manufacturers, in 1997. The scheme requires that the licensed brands of FIFA, together with all their suppliers, must sign a pledge of protecting and respecting human rights in their procurement processes and, the commitment must be renewed every year to confirm that it is compliant with the code of conduct that has been laid by WFSGI. When it started, the process was initiated to combat the issue of child labour that was being used in Pakistan and India. However, in 2010, the code of WFSGI was updated to cover the International Labour Organization's core conventions. This involves the standards set on child labour, people being forced to provide work, non-discrimination, and the issues of freedom of association and the rights on collective bargaining. Those who are involved in licensing FIFA must provide WFSGI with an audit that is done annually to provide evidence demonstrating that entities that are involved in supplying them are fully compliant with the code. The WFSGI pledge is mandatory for companies engaged in producing licensed footballs that FIFA uses in the tournaments. Therefore, before the companies proceed with the production of the balls, there must be confirmation of the pledge before the license is given to them.

Practical measures are being taken to combat the issues of corruption that affect mega-sporting events. Within the Salt Lake City Scandal and the 2010 incidents explained earlier, the IOC and the FIFA consecutively have jointly been engaged in working on the processes of decision making when it comes to the awarding of the mega-sporting events. The IOC has established a

code of conduct for the bidding cities, and FIFA is also developing the same framework. In addition, the bodies are considering the various standards that have been enacted on anti-corruption. For instance, the bidding committee is implementing a comprehensive complaint management system.

The literature documents further that, initially, Qatar had been accused of offering £3 million to FIFA officials to win the bid for the 2022 World Cup finals. However, these corruption allegations were recently cleared by the World Cup inquiry, which mandated Qatar to continue with its process of ensuring that it stages successful World Cup finals (MSEPHR, 2016, p. 11). That was a significant step for Qatar towards retaining its positive image. This is a great benefit and the economic development that is inclined to be experienced in Qatar.

3.13 Qatar and International Organisations: Labour and Migration Agencies

Although there are several international organisations focused on human rights (especially within the United Nations), this section focuses on two leading organisations that are important for this study: the International Organization for Migration (I.O.M.), and the International Labour Organization (I.L.O.). Since this research analyses migrant workers' rights, these prominent organisations play a significant role in the international political arena on this subject. Moreover, Qatar has a different status as an observer at the I.O.M. and as a member state at the I.L.O.

3.13.2 Qatar and the International Organization for Migration (I.O.M.)

The International Organization for Migration (I.O.M.) 'is the leading intergovernmental organisation in migration and is committed to the principle that humane and orderly migration benefits migrants and society' (I.O.M., 2020, non-paginated). The primary mission of I.O.M., as reflected on its website, is to:

i) assist in meeting the growing operational challenges of migration management, ii) advance understanding of migration issues, iii) encourage social and economic development through migration and iv) uphold the human dignity and well-being of migrants (I.O.M., 2020).

The organisation, established in 1951, is currently composed of 173 member states as of March 2019, and has 436 offices across the globe (I.O.M., 2020). However, it is worth noting that Qatar is not a member state of the organization, but it is an observer - the organisation has a total of 8 observers (I.O.M. Members and Observers, 2020, p.1).

The yearly flagship publication, the *World Migration Report*, presents data on migration across the globe, including Qatar. The *World Migration Report 2020* attested that 78.8% of the population in Qatar are migrants (such statistics were further elaborated in chapter 2 of this thesis). Evidence of cooperation between Qatar and I.O.M. includes, i) a cooperation agreement from December 2018 to implement the first Counter-Trafficking capacity building project in 2019, ii) the participation of Qatari officials from different ministries to several I.O.M. regional activities held in Kuwait, iii) the participation of the Chief of Mission of Kuwait at several Counter-Trafficking and Human Rights conferences held in Qatar. (I.O.M. Cairo, 2020, non-paginated).

The collaboration between I.O.M. and Qatar is mainly acknowledged via bilateral agreements focused on returning persons to the country of origin. Both agreements are part of the Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) concept, which aims at safely returning internally displaced persons and migrants; for instance, in 2007, I.O.M. signed two cooperation agreements (in Geneva and Sudan) with Qatari charitable organisations to allow 'for greater collaboration on humanitarian activities both in Qatar and abroad' (I.O.M., 2020, non-paginated). Additionally, in 2015, I.O.M. and Qatar signed a Memorandum of Understanding 'to provide voluntary return and reintegration assistance to stranded migrants [facing abuses] and will be of particular

benefit to the Nepali returnee migrant workers from Qatar (and other countries)' (I.O.M., 2020, non-paginated). However, this agreement does not include the two main nationalities of migrants located in Qatar, as noted in chapter 2 which stipulates the top two origins of migrants in Qatar: India, and the Philippines. Nepal, which is in third place, is covered by the agreement (Seshan, 2012, p. 158).

3.13.3 Qatar and the International Labour Organization (ILO)

The International Labour Organization (ILO) was established in 1919 'to set labour standards, develop policies and devise programmes promoting decent work for all women and men' (ILO, 2020). The ILO's mission is to:

i) set and promote standards and fundamental principles and rights at work, ii) create more significant opportunities for women and men to decent employment and income, iii) enhance the coverage and effectiveness of social protection for all, and iv) strengthen tripartism and social dialogue (I.L.O., 2020, non-paginated). Tripartism is the economic system of corporatism based on mixed economy and tripartite contracts between employers' organisations, trade unions, and the government of a country.

Within the (I.L.O.) Qatar is a member state (the previous section shows that Qatar is only an observer at the I.O.M.). Compared with the I.O.M., the I.L.O. portfolio in Qatar is vaster; it includes several projects and activities. Qatar has been a member of the I.L.O. since 1972 and 'has ratified six conventions including five of the fundamental conventions' (I.L.O., 2020, non-paginated).

The ratifications of I.L.O.'s conventions are exemplified in the figure below:

Figure 3: Ratification of I.L.O.'s Conventions by Qatar (as of July 2020)

Figure 3 shows that Qatar has ratified I.L.O. conventions countering forced labour, discrimination of the labour force, child labour, protecting the workers' minimum work age, and labour inspection. However, although Qatar has signed 5 out of 8 conventions on labour, the country has not signed any of the I.L.O.'s technical conventions (which amount to 178). The I.L.O.'s technical conventions are particular for issues such as hours of work (by sectors: road transport, sea, mining, textile industries, etc.), pensions of workers, accommodation of crews, medical examination of workers, wages, employment contracts and typology of contracts, night hours, paid vacations and annual leaves, maternity protection, invalidity, recruitment, harassment, and others. (I.L.O., 2020, non-paginated). The fundamental conventions are mainly political, for example general instruments like the covenants for human rights. However, the technical conventions remain

thematic specific and, in this context, could serve as good guidance for Qatar's human rights reforms, especially for migrants and workers on construction sites.

3.14 Conclusion

When a country hosts a significant mega-sporting event such as the World Cup, it can contribute to sport diplomacy and increase its soft power. Mega-sporting events are central affairs of the modern state, which provide an opportunity unique for the host countries to capture the global television audience gaze (Parent and Smith-Swan, 2013, p. 182). Parent and Smith-Swan (2013, p. 181) further demonstrate that the opening ceremonies become an embodiment covering public diplomacy purpose and content, including construction, various celebrations held, mass communications concerning the host country's historical accounts, and culture to the public of other countries. The recent developments come as a challenge to established nations that used to host global events to convince them that they can make a difference in terms of events policy and the advancement of liberal democracy (culturally, politically, and economically) (Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson, 2012, p. 47).

Hosting mega-sporting events facilitate the attraction of many individuals to these events. It also presents many commercial opportunities, with Qatar having an excellent opportunity within the Arab nations to demonstrate their potential for commerce and investment. The essential advantage to increasing mega-sporting events in the Middle East, especially Qatar, is that they provide a more significant opportunity for outsiders to experience Qatar, its culture, and its people. Such engagement enables other countries to gain greater insight into Arab cultures. The global community shares a similar appreciation for sport as in Qatar. It is these shared cultural values that can enhance global awareness and diversity. If Middle Eastern countries like Qatar rise to the occasion, and adhere to the shared values exemplified through human rights organisations, then

Qatar can strengthen its appeal to the global community by holding an increased number of sporting events and welcoming other economic opportunities of international engagement.

This chapter outlined the literature review on human rights theory, which showed that both negative and positive aspects could occur in organising a mega-sporting event. Presently, sport events are often used to spur developments globally. According to Tavakkoli (2016, p. 24), the prominence of modern sport in the international dimension has increased in recent years, and has had a subsequent impact on international human rights. However, human trafficking and forced labour have occurred in the construction of facilities in previous mega-sporting events worldwide. Other areas of concern include cases of sexual exploitation, as was widely reported in Brazil in 2014, and child labour that involves commercial sex exploitation (Hepburn, 2017, p. 24). Land acquisition and housing problems also arise as organisers try to establish landmark monuments particularly for the events and at the same time construct and expand the public infrastructure (Akrivopoulou, 2017, p. 3). Moreover, the demands between developers and the residents are regularly in conflict, which often leads to evictions to ensure that the games are sufficiently prepared.

The next chapter will discuss the methodology, a description of the study area, the research design, the data gathering and analysis, and ethical considerations and thesis limitations.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology

4.2 Introduction

This chapter discusses the philosophical foundations and the research approaches that underpin the study. The following section will explore the choice of the phenomenological approach and the development of interpretative phenomenological analysis with the consequent justification of why this process is valuable in the development of this study. There will also be a detailed explanation of the qualitative research methods that form the research design, emphasising the research methodologies such as interviews and participant observations. Finally, the integration of these two theories is applied by formulating the conceptual framework upon which I build the research questions of this study. I supply a framework for questioning Qatar's ongoing actions regarding its attempt to change its socio-political landscape to support its geopolitical ambitions (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006).

Interpretivism, or the interpretive approach, requires that researchers interpret the study's elements while integrating human interests into the research. Interpretive researchers make assumptions regarding the reality that is either given or socially constructed, and can be formed through social constructions such as language, consciousness, shared meanings, and instruments. In current research, the development of interpretivism philosophy considers the notion of positivism in social sciences as much as the philosophy's emphasis on qualitative analysis over quantitative analysis. This methodological approach is associated with the philosophical position of idealism, where it is applied to groups and diverse processes, including social constructivism, phenomenology, and hermeneutics. This approach essentially rejects the objectivist view considering that meaning resides within the world independently of consciousness. This method is essential for the

researcher as a social actor in appreciating the variations existing among the communities under consideration.

In the years since Rio de Janeiro hosted the Olympic and Paralympic Games in 2016, sport's governing bodies such as the International Olympic Committee (IOC), International Federation of Football Association (FIFA), and Union of European Football Association (UEFA) have taken some critical steps in collaboration with the hosting countries to integrate human rights as a due consideration when rolling out their processes. For instance, the 2022 and 2026 World Cup are all events in which framing documents, including the bidding criteria or host city contracts, must now include an explicit reference to the accountability of organisers to respect human rights while endeavouring to set up deliver the mega-sporting events. The countries hosting such events benefit from the economic boost that those in attendance bring forth with them. Mega-sporting events bring people together, where the hosting countries tend to address human rights issues such as freedom, protection, and equality. Qatar aims to promote adequate reconciliation with other countries within and outside the region, amid the consideration that the government will host one of the world's most significant mega-sporting events, which is the World Cup Final in 2022. Pan (2013, p. 24) argues that cultural diplomacy forms an appropriate analytical framework for promoting the country's soft power, which consists of positive interactions between Qatar and other parts of the world. In this regard, the research approach that I apply is to be able to employ the use of research interpretivism to identify the various strategies that are being put in place by Qatar, and how it makes use of the 2022 World Cup finals in addressing human rights issues as well as building positive diplomatic relations (Petty et al., 2012).

Interpretivism is a qualitative approach that depends on a trained researcher's observation and interview of human subjects to measure certain phenomena. According to Guba and Lincoln

(1994), interpretivism is an essential methodology for measuring socially constructed phenomena. It provides data relating to real-time observations and records the experiences of a specific group of individuals. Notably, this process helps eliminate misconstrued information emanating from unreliable sources. It also offers filters to the researcher's pre-determined opinions and paves the way for authentic and accurate information. Interpretivism is more relevant to this study than the other qualitative methodologies due to its human instruments and conjoined elements of communication and observation.

The interpretive approach applied in the current research is based on a naturalistic data collection approach, including interviews and observations. As well as this, secondary data research is essential, as it forms a popular mode of data collection alongside interpretivism philosophy. In current interpretivist studies, meanings usually emerge towards the end of the research process. The best variations of the interpretive approach include hermeneutics, phenomenology, and symbolic interactionism. Hermeneutics as a variation of interpretivism approach refers to the philosophy of interpretation and understanding. The concept strongly emphasises the application of biblical texts and wisdom literature, and as such, it has little relevance to business studies.

On the other hand, phenomenology is the philosophical convention that seeks to address the comprehension of the world through directly experiencing the phenomena under study. On another note, symbolic interactionism is a concept that accepts symbols as culturally derived social objects constraining the shared meanings. According to the idea of symbolic interactionism, symbols tend to act as a means by which reality is constructed.

The interpretive approach takes beliefs into consideration, including the relativist ontology and transactional or subjective epistemology. In terms of relativist ontology, the process perceives reality as inter-subjectively based on meanings and understandings of the social and experiential

levels. On the other hand, subjectivist epistemology considers that people cannot be separated from their knowledge, where there is a clear link between the researchers and the subjects. The interpretive approach to social research is much more qualitative, which is why it was selected in this current study which is based on methods including unstructured interviews and participant observations. The selection of such a methodology was also based on the consideration that human participants are intricate and complex. At the same time, different people often experience and understand the same objective reality in very different ways and have their own, often very different, ways and reasons for acting in a world where other scientific methods are not appropriate. The interpretive approach applied in the current research is derived from social action theory.

Unlike structural theorists, social action theorists consider that their social background does not essentially determine the behaviour of people and life chances. Instead, it believes that there is an emphasis on the role of the active individual and interactions between people, which shapes personal identity, which then impacts the wider society. This implies that understanding human action involves uncovering the individual's motives for such activities. The social interaction theory as a guiding principle for the interpretive approach applied in this current study considers that observation alone does not offer room for understanding human action, where there is a need to understand the main points of sociology. On the other hand, individual motives are critical while understanding the changes to the social structure. Consequently, the approach of this study looks at the reasons for action, where there are different motives for human activity, including instrumentally rational, value rational, traditional movement, and productive action. This research approach is also based on the notion that different societies and groups emphasise the importance of different types of general motives for activities within the society.

Most research that focuses on social constructions considers interpretivism as a qualitative design by maintaining the idea that they are the only channels that can access a reality. According to Atkinson, Delamont, and Hammersley (2012), interpretivism is merged continuously with the researcher's values, beliefs, and attitudes. The most significant advantage of this includes the capacity to shape research using practical views, while the reflexive interpretive approach can mitigate biases and preconceptions. Interpretivism relies on the human subject and the researchers being trained as an excellent instrument for analysing subjective data (Atkinson et al., 2012, p. 28). Elias' work on involvement and detachment plays a critical role in this current research because there is no complete abandonment of the participants' feelings in the study. Research that draws from a phenomenological philosophy makes it possible to look at different ideologies, assess the theme of the study, and use logical deduction to present study findings that are consistent and practical. Walsham further argues that the interpretivism approach holds that human knowledge of reality is a social construction, for instance, the aspect of human social interaction through human actors (1995, p. 376). Therefore, for one to obtain value-free data, they must disconnect their preconceptions from the study and use critical judgment to guide their inquiry process.

Even though interpretivism usually utilises the experiences and interpretations pre-established by the researcher, one should use this approach to interpret data without premeditated judgment. The choice for interpretivism results from the realistic social constructions that lead to consistency in determining variables with the help of just a meagre sample (Berg, 2004, p. 34). Interpretivism was found to be a form of qualitative methodology that depends entirely on the trained researcher's observations and interviews of human subjects to measure the phenomena under consideration, which is the influence of mega-sporting events in international human rights, with specific emphasis on the case study of Qatar. Most of this consisted of the capacity of shaping the

research using practical views, where a risk existed that the study could suffer from significant researcher bias (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Therefore, interpretivism was regarded as a principle that relies on human subjects and the researchers trained as a valuable instrument for the analysis of the subjective data.

Research that was drawn from a phenomenological philosophy made it possible to look at different ideologies during the analysis of the themes for this research. The interpretivism approach holds that human knowledge of reality is a social construction, and the aspect of social interactions was made through human actors (Wahyuni, 2012). This implies that if one had to obtain value-free data, the personality must disconnect their preconceptions from the study and apply critical judgement that guides the process of inquiry. In this regard, what has always counted as knowledge embraces two different philosophical positions composed of rationalism and empiricism. The philosophical position of rationalism claims that human knowledge can be unlimited, while empiricism affirms that the only source and limit of knowledge is a sensory experience. A range of research paradigms was found to exist. The most influential paradigm was found to be that of positivism. The approach, which appeared with Augusto Comte as the founder of sociology positivity, is based on the facts and the causes of phenomena independent of the subjective states of individuals (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). In this case, the only good knowledge was found to be scientific experience and induction, which obeys certain principles and unique methodologies as a way of overcoming all forms of speculation. This implies that human social reality must be scientifically understood while reaching out for the intention of arriving at the generalisations of observable verifications.

The interpretive approach to research is a form of manifestation of reality through human experience. It focuses on the study contexts and social situations that enable the researcher to understand the world from a subjective point of view. As a professional researcher with a unique lived experience within this capacity, I have come to understand that my commitment to completing this research has been comprehensively impacted by this sense of duality, which has not only impacted my potential interview experience with some of the interviewees, but which has also impacted my own experience with professional interviewees. Barnacle (2004) explains that researchers with unique personal experiences associated with their research topics can provide personal elements to their research processes that can help explain otherwise challenging areas of the topic's coverage. Similarly, Dieumegard et al. (2021) explain that lived experience and personal understanding can be so important within the research process that it may potentially make up an entirely separate unit of analysis within the explorative and evaluative research framework. The researcher's own lived experience and dual role, both as a researcher and as a professional in the field, is undeniably impacted by a number of responsibilities, commitments, and issues. However, it is firmly believed that the general dual-role is a much more advantageous position than it is potentially disadvantageous, mostly because of its potential for increased perspective, as well as its facilitation of immediate practical application and implementation of researched recommendations.

The approach for this study also seeks an explanation from the research participants, in this case, the communities in Qatar attached to mega-sporting events, including the 2022 World Cup finals (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). The paradigm rejects the positivist ideology that the same research methods can be applied while studying human behaviour, while human sciences aim to understand human actions. In this case, interpretivism is a paradigm founded on the premise that

knowledge of what people are doing or saying is directly correlated with the specific background of the people.

This study was based on a qualitative philosophical foundation, where it deployed an inductive approach. According to Gabriel (2013, p. 29), inductive research is associated with qualitative research and observations with theories and generalisations considered. In accomplishing this research, the inductive approach was preferable because this study aimed to look at a particular case study, seeking depth in the answers from elite actors. I was not seeking to generalise to a broader population. Essentially, this study focused on acquiring raw data from projected sources, to accumulate information that was analysed to reach a spontaneous conclusion (Petty et al., 2012). The research sample was comprised of twenty-six participants who were interviewed, including thirteen workers, eight government officials, and five officials from the private sector. The main interview questions were linked to human rights and sport events. I opined that combining these methodologies, human elements as instruments, and an inductive model would provide this study's accurate and relevant data.

In conclusion, because of the specific nature of the study's approach to understanding the relationship between mega-sporting events and human rights issues and concerns, I found it very important to develop a methodology that was closely aligned with the general goals and objectives of the study's humanistic angle. More specifically, the methodology was greatly influenced by the need to formulate, maintain, and continuously develop a human-centric approach to understand human rights issues, within a highly multi-cultural and multi-ethnic nation like Qatar. Given these considerations, the study mainly focused on a content analysis of numerous different study materials, including various laws, strategies, measures, procedures, and regulations. Outside of these materials, the study also relied on the utilisation of a number of different personal interviews and

on-site observations, all of which enabled me to develop a more diverse and personal understanding of the data being collected.

Content analysis is a conventional technique often applied within contemporary and traditional research spaces, and is very popular because of its ability to help the researcher in making inferences that are both replicable and valid, often by way of interpreting, and then coding various textual materials about the topic being discussed. However, content analysis was chosen as a specific approach to this research methodology because of how it can help uncover and analyse the unique mechanisms of human rights systems. For example, a content analysis approach allowed me to uncover research themes and data findings that were unique to Qatar's socio-cultural, political, and economic profile, as the findings section suggests. Moreover, this approach was able to provide incredibly important value in relation to understanding the global themes that affected Qatar's own improvement of its human rights standard and workers' conditions. For example, one of the themes that was commonly found amongst much of the pre-2014 data collected seemed to suggest that the nation's workers' rights systems were inadequate, unsafe, and potentially exploitative. After 2014, however, the change in Qatar's approach, coupled with the nation's increased commitment to ensure the protection and wellbeing of its migrant worker community, helped change the narrative of research discussing the event — a research trend that could not have potentially been uncovered if not for the specific methodology chosen.

4.3 Description of the Study Area

The study area of this research was Qatar, and the study attempted to include an analysis of the entire city, except the Old Town, in the investigation. Therefore, the research map covered the central business district of Qatar. Qatar is an Arab country that is located along the beaches and dunes of the Persian Gulf Shorelines. The sovereign nation is situated in Western Asia. Its

capital city is Doha. The country has a high-income economy power, most of which it derives from its vast oil and gas reserves and modest income per capita (ORR, 2008, p. 2). Such immense economic power gives the country a prominent regional political voice and thus Qatar can broker deals with global political forces. Their income is supported by the natural gas and oil reserves, estimated at 896 trillion cubic feet, which is a volume that only Russia and Iran can surpass. The country recorded the second largest per capita income in the world in 2017, according to the CIA (2018). Consequently, most economies profile Qatar as ranking higher and above all other Arabic states. Relative to its other neighbours, Qatar is among the major countries in the region regarding human development because there are significant developments in education, media, safety, trade, and environmental sustainability sectors.

In the Arab world, the country has a significant power (ORR, 2008, p. 2). According to Fromherz (2013, p. 14), the country's growing influence has received international recognition, making it win the bid to stage the 2022 World Cup finals and therefore become party to high profile geopolitical negotiations, leading to recently formed important alliances on the global stage. However, winning the FIFA bid has placed the country in the spotlight, and it has since received regular criticism of how it is preparing for the 2022 event, with claims that the rights of the workers have consistently been violated (Hughson, Moore and Spaaij, 2016, p. 94) Hughson, Moore, and Spaaij (2016) continue to demonstrate that human rights have been consistently abused during the preparations, as well as when the mega-sporting events are ongoing, in host countries. Therefore, this is a serious issue that cannot be ignored, because of the severe consequences and implications to the people whose rights are being abused, mainly casual immigrant workers who come in seeking low paying jobs (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006).

Several reports, including the Amnesty UK International, Institute for Human Rights, and the HRW (HRW, 2016, p. 13), have captured this issue and presented information concerning the impacts of these violations (HRW, 2016, p. 13). Additionally, several agencies, such as Amnesty International and several individuals from different countries, have been involved in producing these reports that have continually evoked debates as to why countries that violate human rights received opportunities to host international events of this calibre. Because of this, Qatar is in a significant state of evaluation because of the many challenges it faces in its bid to host the coveted mega-sporting event. In essence, the state must address all national and domestic issues to show that the host state is ready to handle the problems associated with such international events (Ponterotto, 2005). Another significant reason is that Qatar will become the first country to hold such an event in the Middle East, which is challenging because other nations from the region that wish to host the event in the future will rely significantly on Qatar's appropriate reforms and approach in organising such a mega-sporting event. Notably, its success or failure has a significant connection to the whole region (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Arguably, Russia experiences similar challenges, with most countries sceptical about its capacity to keep neo-Nazis at bay to provide a safe experience for people from around the world. In this light, Qatar is a good study because of its critical role in the region. The success or failures of the country in hosting the 2022 World Cup will largely influence the perception of the world on the region's ability to hold such an event successfully (Petty et al., 2012). This underlines the significance of the study, because the wider region, not only Qatar, depends on the right ambassadorship of the state in projecting their prowess in this way. For this study to be a success, the tools used in this research aimed at examining the approach of the reforms and improvements Qatar has put in place to ensure that human rights are not violated.

The selection of the study area and the method applied in the current research is justified since the country will be hosting the 2022 World Cup finals. On the other hand, the phenomenological approach is warranted in recent research because it involves the study of the subjective experiences of humans. The experiencing person, in this case, is regarded as the person or the self for purposes of convenience. In this phenomenological philosophy, experience is a considerably more complex concept than the usual use in daily life. Instead, experience is about the phenomenon, and it is defined by the qualities of directedness, embodiment, and worldliness, which are evoked by them being in the world.

4.4 Methods

Since the study uses a qualitative philosophical basis, quantitative features will appear only in evaluating respondents' overall opinions on specific themes, which were chosen to be presented in percentages throughout the thesis. However, this study is mainly focused on content analysis, and by this, we understand it as the close examination of national standards comprised of laws, regulations, policies, strategies, measures, procedures, personal interviews, and on-site observations, as the methods that will enable the researcher to collect subjective data. Content analysis as a technique applied in the current research is vital. It allows the researcher to make replicable and valid inferences by interpreting and coding textual materials regarding the topic under discussion. It has proven the potential of analysing social phenomena as it offers one advantage of being non-invasive while in contrast to simulating social experiences or collection of survey responses. Practices and philosophies of content analysis are varied between academic disciplines. This current research involves systematic reading or observation of texts which are assigned thematic labels (extracted manually), that can indicate the presence of engaging, meaningful pieces of content. Through the systematic labelling of the content of a set of texts, the researcher was able to analyse

patterns of content quantitatively by applying statistical methods or qualitative methods during the analysis of meanings within texts.

On the other hand, personal interviews are the preferred method because they allow for the collection of first-hand data. Interviews are also flexible, and they make it possible to secure more details as the researcher conducts a deeper examination. This study drew participants for the interviews from the Qatar population, focusing on professionals who experience the work environment to a sizable degree, and those who are found to have a good understanding of the workplace culture in Qatar (Petty et al., 2012). The first sample group consisted of workers (on-site workers, excluding public sector employees), whose selection was based on stratified random sampling. The other sample group was comprised of government officials from Qatar's Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs. The research also included members from the private sector, who provided information on the country's current economic status and the plans they have regarding mega-sporting events hosting of the 2022 World Cup Finals (Ponterotto, 2005). Through them, it was possible to derive content on the activities in the business sector, which is one of the biggest victors in the event. Since these two samples were selected depending on name and position, this study applied the purposive sampling method. To facilitate the sampling process, letters were sent to various departments to confirm staff availability, which was the foundation for the sampling process. Otherwise, without institutional support, this would have been difficult. Duncan et al. (2009, p. 18) note that this sampling technique offers an adequate representation of the target population, a view shared by Robinson (2014, p. 250).

Participant observations were also justified as the methodology used in the current research because they are an accessible data collection method. Observation does not require much technical knowledge, even though controlled observation requires some technical skills on the part of

the researcher. Therefore, observation was also considered part of the data collection methods that could be used to formulate the hypothesis for the current research. It is evident that through observation, the researcher can construct the social structure of the societies under study while analysing their perceptions regarding mega-sporting events. The observation was also regarded as a justifiable means of data collection because it does not depend on data provided by respondents and is thus free from objectivity caused by respondent bias. In this case, the observer can directly check the accuracy from the observed. At the same time, it is easy to apply the various devices to test the reliability of the behaviour of the participants within the context of the study.

Observation is also regarded as a universal method used in scientific research, whether physical or social. Observation, in this case, deals with the phenomena that are not provided through verbal information, namely regarding the behaviour of the participants, their feelings, and activities, where it was found to eliminate the language barriers to research. Observation is also independent of people's willingness to report. In this case, observations were found to be methods that could not depend on the willingness of the participants to provide information, where the researcher could make inferences regarding the research topic using other related cues such as the environment and the behaviour of the participants.

To record the best possible results and ensure study reliability, the sample group selected was comprised of twenty-six participants who were interviewed. This included thirteen workers (on-site workers, excluding public sector officials), eight government officials (working for the public sector), and five officials from the private sector. Additionally, a private interpreter was present to ensure that language was not a barrier when conducting the interviews. The interpreter spoke English, Arabic, Urdu, Nepali, and Bengali (which were the main languages used by the construction workers). The interpreter was not accredited for translations for other languages such

as Tagalog, Chinese, Tamil, and Hindi, which certain workers may have also used. However, the interpreter found workers willing to engage in the interview in one of the languages offered for interpretation. Addressing the ethical considerations required the translator to sign a confidentiality agreement before being part of the research (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). The translator was also instructed to stick to the fundamentals of ethical behaviour, including presenting information without alteration. The interpreter was given strict instructions to provide detailed descriptions of words and phrases to avoid possible contradictions. In addition, the interpreter was required to provide the information in complete detail as presented by the participants without any form of omission. The interviews were carried out in secluded places, and the data was safeguarded to limit any chances of exposure to third parties.

4.5 Addressing the relationship between the Survey and Interview Data Collection Process

The survey is a critical source of primary data and was done at the preliminary stages of the research to obtain the required data. According to Berg (2004, p. 34), a small number of participants allows consistency in determining variables. The study employed a sample size of 30-40 participants. The number was divided according to the most important groups. For instance, 65% of the participants were the workers who are the main stakeholders in the matter. Brinkmann (201, p. 65) notes that the use of research questions narrows the study scope, thereby informing the smaller number that supports the scope of the study. Again, the smaller number makes it possible to acquire information, particularly from those who cannot participate without raising the alarm. The smaller number is adequate in that it will allow the research to have a broader perspective without wasting time conducting irrelevant interviews. The schedules of the interviews and the background information were sent to informants of the study.

Other key details were also sent to the participants to ensure they were comfortable and

willing to undertake the research. The survey questions were divided into open questions and closed questions, with primary factors and secondary factors considered. The open questions were broad, targeted at obtaining the broader perspective of the participant regarding certain aspects of the study. On the other side of the dichotomy, the primary questions were the fundamental ones with the primary goals of the indicated research. Through secondary open questions, the survey allowed the participants to give their opinion regarding mega-sporting events and the promotion of human rights and stability in the region through peaceful cooperation as part of sport diplomacy, which will lead to better human rights. They gave their opinion on what should be done to promote human rights and stability.

Moreover, the participants also highlighted their opinion regarding the treatment of workers working on mega-projects because of human rights promotion. Generally, the survey gave an essential aspect of the view of the people in matters regarding peaceful co-existence, working conditions, and human rights promotion. The survey also provided a general and detailed perspective of the situation on the ground. The information was used to examine the effects of mega-sporting events regarding human rights protection and promotion.

The survey followed ethical considerations, and participants were informed that the information was to be used for an academic purpose and not any other. For informants who did not wish to be identified, anonymity was granted throughout and after the study, based on data protection rules.

4.6 Research Design

Integration of interviews, interpretivism, and the literature that the study uncovers in the review means that the study uses a qualitative approach instead of a quantitative research design. The qualitative method is most common in finding various trends and looking deeper into the

problem or existing situation (Maxwell, 2012, p. 19). Interviews will provide primary data for the study, while the literature review will be applied to acquire secondary data. Similarly, the researcher will employ critical observation methods to add to the primary data collected through the subsequent interviews. The research methodology used in this study is appropriate to eliminate all possible grey areas that would otherwise lead to misconstrued and misleading information (Petty et al., 2012).

The study design applied here is considered because it would support the research in general and at the same time ensure and facilitate the completeness of the study (Quinlan, 2011, p. 51). This implies that the researcher must ask a question that focuses on each interviewee's working relations with the employers, their current financial status, and their living conditions. Moreover, the study aims to find out the levels of job satisfaction among employees in Qatar, the possibilities of harassment, and possible violations of human rights. On the other hand, the interviews are conducted to obtain data regarding the government's measures to curb human rights violations and any other activities related to labour and hospitality relations. Therefore, the researcher must ensure that these interviews are organised freely and without constraints in identifying, exploring, and questioning potential areas that would provide relevant additional information (Petty et al., 2012).

The triangulation of data involves the use of secondary sources as well as primary research. This study uses secondary sources, mainly literature, to confirm the information available in primary sources about Qatar's 2022 World Cup finals and the issues of human rights surrounding these events. These two methods will validate the data and the data that would have been obtained during the research (Creswell, 2013, p. 3). Most of the data was obtained from books, peer-re-

viewed journals, and global human rights reports, especially those that captured information concerning the challenges of mega-sporting events and the abuse of human rights (O'Donoghue, 2006). Moreover, Qatar state reports and articles explaining the various reforms and measures to ensure that human rights are not violated were examined. The major reforms that the study dwells on include changes in remuneration structure, working hours, and working conditions (Thanh and Thanh, 2015). The primary data was collected as part of the research to establish human rights issues that arise during mega-sporting events. Preliminary research was also captured from interviews with officials from government departments, including the Labour department in Qatar (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). An informed consent form was handed to the interviewees where they were notified of the purpose, method of data collection, and the ethical measures being observed while handling personal data (O'Donoghue, 2006).

Government officials in Qatar participated in interviews to provide vital information regarding the status of the projects. The study involves in-depth research and is informed by semi-structured interviews. The choice of participants included the requirement that they were from the Ministry of Labour and the private sector. Semi-structured interviews refer to the inquiry qualitative method, which incorporates a set of open and fixed questions that are predetermined, giving an interviewer an excellent opportunity to explore various themes as well as responses (Leavy 2014, p. 31). In this regard, semi-structured interview questions were applicable in the deep exploration of the situation of the working conditions in Qatar as the country prepares to host the 2022 World Cup finals. A total of twenty-six interviews were conducted to reinforce the findings from secondary sources. There was no specific time for the interviews because each participant offered unique information (Petty et al., 2012). The interviews took place at different locations,

each selected by the participant to ensure maximum convenience. In addition, some of the responses were recorded via phone and later transcribed. Semi-structured interviews were carried out with influential officials in the Ministry of Labour in Qatar. Throughout this thesis, the interviewees have pseudonyms. They are all called Senior Government Officials (1,2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8) and fictive roles were attributed to them such as ‘Policy Advisor’, ‘Policy Counsellor’, ‘Policy Associate’, ‘Policy Assistant’, ‘Policy Officer’, ‘Policy Chief’, ‘Policy Expert’, and ‘Policy Head’. It is noted that the government officials are high-ranking employees (female/male) that agreed with a semi-structured interview only if their name and ranking (which is easily recognisable in case of research) would be confidential within the scope and outside the scope of this thesis. Additionally, the high-level officials are also my professional superiors and conflict of interest may arise (and employment sanctions) if the names are divulged. Considering this, the study sought to answer the following questions (which are presented in the introductory chapter of this thesis):

- How important and effective are some of the reforms in payment policy and working conditions that the government of Qatar is trying to put in place in ensuring that human rights are protected?
- (sub-question) Are the reforms translated into normative approaches, i.e., national laws, policies, legislations, strategies to ensure post-game compliance and post-2022 applicability?

The data that was obtained from the research questions above will be analysed through a classification method. This method allows the researcher to group responses to come up with cohorts that have consistent themes. In this regard, classification by method involves descriptive research that offers information concerning the conditions and situations that are currently occur-

ring. (Jajuga, Sokolowski, and Bock, 2012, p. 11). In this regard, a descriptive method offers critical information concerning the state of working conditions for the workers in Qatar as the country prepares to stage the 2022 World Cup finals. After the classification, a conceptual framework is suggested to implement the changes. The changes made helps to identify missing data and re-establish interviewees' comments regarding the coming 2022 World Cup finals (Petty et al., 2012).

4.7 Data Gathering

The study gathers qualitative data using interviews. Of the twenty-six participants, twenty provided 100% response rates with limited additional data (no comments or explanations on why a specific rating was given); the participants answered all questions; hence these proceeded to the data analysis phase. To ensure the reliability and validity of the data used by the study, each interview response is considered and counted within this study. Some of the surveys provided answers declaring the government's measures as 100% relevant and satisfactory, without any complaint to add. This response was also counted, but a critical view should be kept as some workers could have been intimidated to respond to a survey. Some of them may not be familiar with research surveys. They may not trust its entirely academic scope, thus may see the survey as a possibility way to lose their job by showing unsatisfactory responses. All respondents were reassured that the survey is confidential and that there is no hidden purpose behind the academic survey other than to serve the definition of a personal dissertation thesis.

To ensure the reliability and validity of the data used by the study, each interview response was scrutinised to eliminate extreme responses from the data that moved on to the analysis phase. Three of the prospective interviewees were technically unavailable for the study, and efforts to reach them were futile. Those responses were not considered because respondents were not responding directly to the questions, were playing on their mobile phones, were rude in responding

(i.e., asking consistently how long the survey will last). Therefore, those three responses were considered incomplete interview responses and thus did not constitute a final analysis (as per the methodology provided by Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006).

The choice of the sample size in qualitative research has been an important area of conceptual debate and experimental uncertainty. The researcher developed the sample size according to principles, guidelines, and tools to justify the acceptability of the sample size and indicate that the issue constitutes an important marker of the quality of quantitative research. The current research is a qualitative analysis, where it typically requires a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. The current sample size for the qualitative study is, therefore, enough, where it can help to obtain enough data to sufficiently describe the phenomenon of interest and address the research questions. Since the goal of qualitative research is to attain saturation, additional participants were not found to result in other perspectives or information. At the same time, they were regarded as representative of the whole population under study. Therefore, the concept of saturation was used for the achievement of the appropriate sample size for the current qualitative analysis.

4.8 Data Analysis

Since some of the qualitative data was collected from non-English speakers, all interviews were translated into English. This study had to address the complexity of the translation overall with the interviews. After the interviews were transcribed in full, the obtained data was analysed using the thematic analysis method, which was focused on gaining insight and knowledge from the data gathered. The thematic analysis involved identifying patterns and themes within the qualitative data, where the themes were analysed both at the semantic and latent levels. The semantic level helped search for the surface meanings from what the participants had to say, while the latent level of theme analysis is where the researcher concentrated on interpreting anything beyond what

the participants had to say to identify the underlying ideas, assumptions, and conceptualisations theorised as shaping or informing the semantic content of the data. Firstly, codes were generated from the interview responses, and then themes were developed to identify the similarities existing in the patterns of data using Microsoft Excel. The themes were then used to generate theories on the subject under consideration.

4.9 Ethical Considerations

Phenomenology is acknowledged as the most suitable methodology for gaining an insight into the essence or structure of lived experiences. Informed consent comes into play in the sense that participants should have adequate information and have the power of free choice. The current research ensured that the participants could comprehend the data in addition to signing the consent form. The process of having the power of free choice was embedded within the principle of respect for autonomy and included providing participants with information regarding the benefits and risks of research. Despite the efforts to predict all risks at the outset of the study, it was not known for certain what the interviews would uncover. This implies that consent was viewed as an ongoing transactional process, known as consensual decision making, or continuously informed consent in qualitative research. The researchers were always informed by asking the participants' permission to conduct the study, which established the needed trust to ethically progress further.

The essence of the interview will be to determine their take on human rights considerations in Qatar. This topic is slightly controversial and will require the study to obtain adequate consent from the participants. Thus, each of the participants selected went through the questions and signed a consent form that shows that they will fully participate in the interview and that the submitted information will be confidential. To promote confidentiality and alleviate ethical concerns, none of the participants was required to provide personal data. Respondents were informed that the data

to be provided would only be used for an academic purpose and not otherwise (including that the data will not be communicated to any public/private employer, to reassure them that no consequences will follow). Each of the interviewees had an opportunity to respond to the questions based on their own employment experiences in Qatar. As a result, there were no response limitations (O'Donoghue, 2006). Additionally, the comments from the public sector officials are presented throughout this research by their roles, not by their names, with the consent of all the representatives that participated in the interview.

Another aspect that is important to mention is that throughout the thesis and its references, the Ministry of Labour from Qatar is presented under different names because, during the past ten years, the Ministry changed its name as follows: 1) The Ministry of Labour, 2) The Ministry of Labour, and Social Affairs, and 3) Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs (the most recent official name as per the Amiri Decree No. (6)/2016). Those three names refer to one single 'Ministry of Labour'; however, the official names mentioned in the sources may be different, depending on the year.

Finally, since the research involved human participants, I applied for ethical approval that was granted by the University's ethics committee.

4.10 The Researcher's Dual Role as a Researcher and Professional

It is incredibly important to understand that this research has largely relied on a specifically interpretive approach to undertake data analysis. As such, it is particularly necessary to identify, examine, and explain the specific characteristics of the researcher's role, as one that is dually influenced by its commitment to non-bias as a researcher and academic professional, as well as one that is influenced by its professional commitment to the organisation it operates within. Although this dual role can potentially result in a number of research and ethical considerations, it should

also be argued that it has allowed for an incredibly unique research experience. For example, as a professional individual whose personal and socio-cultural attributes are greatly linked to the experience of Qatar's society, government, and culture, I was able to closely understand, mend, and potentially innovate certain aspects of the research and data-collection processes. This was especially true within my role as an interviewer of some of the migrant workers, who are almost always respectful and polite, but who are often hesitant, as most vulnerable immigrants are, to voice some of their complaints and concerns. In general, the interpretive approach undertaken throughout the research has undoubtedly been impacted by my dual role as a researcher and as a professional in the field. Within this dual role, the interpretive approach undertaken has often had to accommodate for a number of human-centric elements that are unique to the economic conditions of the Arabian Gulf, as suggested above.

Expanding on this specific point, it should be understood and explained that the relationship between many, if not all, of the construction workers, and their Qatari professional superiors, is often highly impacted by a degree of expected hierarchy and respect. Most of Qatar's organisational structures, both public and private, are often socioeconomically indicative of wider ethnicity-based socioeconomic systems. Whilst Qatari citizens are often appointed in senior and executive positions, migrants from developing nations are often much more likely to assume roles within manual labour positions at the bottom of the organisational hierarchy. In turn, this often completely eliminates the direct communication channels between the upper-most and lower-most organisational levels, meaning hierarchal respect and authority is not only directly prevalent through workplace positions, but also indirectly through structural organisations.

Qatar, much like many other nations in the Arabian Gulf, possesses incredibly high-Power Distance (PDI) levels, indicating that the country's work structure operates within a greatly hierarchal structure, where respect and authority are often required, and where further justification is not expected (At-Twajri & Al-Muhaiza, 1996). As a professional and researcher with a unique lived experience within this capacity, I have come to understand that my commitment to completing this research has been comprehensively impacted by this sense of duality, which has not only impacted my potential interview experience with some of the interviewees, but which has also impacted my own experience with professional interviewees. As it is more carefully explored in some of the following sub-sections of this chapter, this notion of possessing a dual role provides an incredibly high number of opportunities for personal experience to ensure increased empathy, closer understanding, and potential hands-on examination (Barnacle, 2004). Also, although it is explained that the insider-researcher notion can potentially lead to misrepresentation and deception, it is argued that researchers with integrity will instead move towards genuine improvement and development through research, thus creating a generally more wholesome assessment and overview.

However, this sense of hierarchal authority and power distance is not exclusive to the nation's ethnic categories, but is also prevalent within solely Qatar's economic and social circles. For example, much like the vast majority of the migrant workers who initially refused to explicitly voice their concerns and complaints, I often also found myself needing to approach certain subjects with caution and sensitivity when discussing them with government and private sector officials. The notion of hierarchal authority, therefore, is certainly not race-based, and any potential examination of it in such a manner would fail to understand and appreciate the unique socio-cultural attributes of Arab culture, and in many ways, South-Asian and South-East Asian cultures, where

most of the migrant workers come from. With that said, the aforementioned duality is almost entirely expected within spaces of research in nations with incredibly high levels of Power Distance, and this constituted an important research consideration. As such, I have taken it upon myself to improve the interviewing process by ensuring the anonymity of the interviewees. In spite of this, the degree to which this consideration has been effective cannot be effectively measured.

4.11 Thesis Limitations

This thesis, like any other, has certain limitations. One limitation is that this thesis focuses on analysing only the 2022 World Cup mega-sporting event in Qatar. Thus, although general connections are made to other mega-sporting events, this thesis is not a place for comparative analysis. Additional limitations include the following. First, my dual role as an employee in the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs, and a researcher, made my position challenging to express my knowledge precisely as it is. The access to the information within the Ministry was an exclusive opportunity for conducting this research, however as most documents were confidential, there were considerable limitations on using that information within this thesis. Secondly, pictures that were taken from second-hand sources and not directly on-site (unfortunately this section was carried out during the blockade on Qatar where access to sites was restricted and severe time constraints were imposed. Additionally, the work could not have been carried out recently due to the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown). Thirdly, many laws, regulations, and monitoring reports need further analysis from a legal perspective. This would be a good starting point for elaborating an additional research project. Fourthly, there are still a few months until the 2022 World Cup, and national authorities might still amend laws and regulations in Qatar. It would be interesting to do another research project after the mega-sporting event to assess if the modifications remain in place after the 2022 World Cup (and, if not, to determine why).

Aside from the space limitation that a thesis is required to respect, the research findings are not definitive facts, as the thesis is based on several non-exhaustive lists of matters. Furthermore, changing the number of case studies and the timeframe of this analysis could also change the outcome of the thesis.

4.12 Conclusion

The study deploys a qualitative framework that seeks to build on secondary sources alongside data from an interview survey. To obtain results that have significant practical implications, the study elects to work with an interpretivism research philosophy to allow adequate room for the incorporation of social constructions to a notable degree. Further, the research topic has presented a broad array of methodologies available to complete the research. The introduction of the study has provided an overview of the prospective research methodologies. The description of the study area has provided an overview of the country since the research is in Qatar. The research design has significantly demonstrated its significant support for the analysis. The research implications have provided an informed action on how the findings merged with the research project. On top of selecting a methodology framework consistent with the research aim and context, the study observes ethical standards that will promote reliability and validity.

The next chapter assesses the case study as described in the introduction and methodology chapters. It is thus providing the findings and critical analysis of the survey conducted. Finally, I will assess Qatar's reforms for the 2022 World Cup in terms of protective measures for works and the potential benefits and challenges of such reforms.

Chapter 5: Findings and Analysis – a Case Study of Qatar's Reforms for the 2022 World Cup Mega-Sporting Event

5.2. Introduction

The content analysis was performed by critically evaluating key documents. International, national, and local papers were selected based on a mega-theme/sub-theme and their potential contribution to the topic at hand. The following table provides an overview of what content was analysed from the primary documents reviewed within the content analysis.

Content analysis overview		
International/other non-national frameworks		Purpose/findings
Mega-theme International Human Rights documents		Qatar's involvement and positioning in international human rights issues
	Sub-theme 18 Human Rights treaties related to civil and political rights (ICCPR) and economic, social, and cultural rights (ICESCR) Fundamental conventions, governance conventions, technical conventions (I.L.O., I.O.M., W.H.O., OHCHR, etc.)	Showed status of Qatar's ratification/signatory status on human rights issues
Mega-theme External/Non-national actors		Qatar's mega-sporting event as positioned by the civil society
	Sub-theme NGOs report on the human rights situation in Qatar (Amnesty International, HRW, etc.) NGOs reports on Qatar's mega-sporting event/construction overview (fact-finding reports)	Showed allegations of Qatar's human rights violations in the context of the FIFA mega-sporting event

Content analysis overview		
	Reports external committees (FIFA, IOC, etc.)	Showed Qatar's structural changes/evolutions/efforts in the context of the mega-sporting event construction sites
	Soft power international reports ranking (Soft Power 30 reports from the past five years, Cervantes Institute (Spain), British Council (UK), Institute François (France), Confucius Institute (China), Indian Cultural Institute (India), etc.)	Showed Qatar's positioning as a soft power and cultural diplomacy
	Brand identity, sponsorship reports (Qatar Airways, Network of Sport Sponsorship Transactions, etc.)	Showed Qatar's implications in sport via brands/sponsorships
Mega-theme International press articles		Qatar's mega-sporting event reflected in the press
	Sub-theme Press articles on Qatar's human rights violations/mega-sporting event construction news (CNN, Al Jazeera, The Guardian, New York Times, CNCB, etc.)	Showed news on Qatar's human rights violations and mega-sporting event construction issues through investigative journalism
National/local frameworks		Purpose/findings
Mega-theme National reports/strategies on sport		Status/relevance of sport in Qatar
	Sub-theme The Ministry of Culture and Sports and Emiri Decree No. 4 of 2016, Qatar Youth League, Qatar Sports for All Federation, etc.	Showed Qatar's national strategies for sport/youth sport and their relevance

Content analysis overview		
Mega-theme Mega-sporting events construction sites		Qatar's construction sites for the mega-sporting events: overview and evolution
	Sub-theme Accommodation sites/construction facilities (reports, pictures, regulations, locations, etc.)	Showed Qatar's working conditions offered to the migrant workers
	Compliance reports/construction approvals by the Ministry of Labour; Audit-based reports by HWC, Global Union Federation, the Supreme Committee, Qatar Football Association, etc.	Showed Qatar's capability to monitor and hold accountable the construction companies
	Financial Reports on construction sites/legal permits/legal registration number (example of companies: Doha Zone Company, Aspire Zone, SC-Projects, etc.)	Showed the costs of the preparation for the mega-sporting event
Mega-theme Welfare and health		Qatar's regulations for the welfare of migrant workers
	Sub-theme Equipment for workers (reports, pictures, regulations, mechanisms, modalities of distribution of the equipment to the workers, etc.), protection equipment, cooling technologies, etc.	Showed Qatar's ability to protect workers
	Welfare rights of workers (Worker's Charter, Welfare Forums, Grievance Hotline, wage, etc.)	Showed workers' rights and their ability to complain/resolve/mitigate conflicts
	Health facilities for workers (number of doctors per accommodation/construction site, medical equipment, number of rooms, emergencies, transportation to hospitals, regular check-ups, medical insurance, etc.)	Showed the ability to protect the right to health of migrant workers

Content analysis overview		
Mega-theme Labour laws and administrative labour instructions		Qatar's labour regulations, especially related to migrant workers
	Sub-theme Statistics/data Ministry of Labour-on-labour laws, administrative instructions, wage/employment regulations, <i>Kafala</i> system, etc.)	Showed Qatar's reforms on labour and migrant workers positioning under Qatar's labour laws
	Qatar migration reports, Qatar National Development Strategy, Reports from the Planning and Statistics Authority, Qatar Population and Expat Nationalities, etc.	Showed Qatar's overview on migrant workers and other demography facts (origin of workers, salary differences between Qatari and non-Qatari, etc.)

This chapter examines Qatar's reforms to protect human rights (such as labour rights and migrant rights) in the context of the preparations for the 2022 FIFA World Cup mega-sporting event. This chapter also elaborates on several sections combining critical analysis and survey-based data on areas such as the *Kafala* system (meaning Qatar's employment system of migrants), the working conditions of employees working on construction sites, the payment and reduced number of working hours, cooling technology, accommodation facilities, the establishment of the workers charter, welfare and health regulations, compliance and audit procedures, transparency and reporting procedures, as well as information on stakeholders, contractors and individual perceptions of surveyed persons.

Within this chapter, content analysis of data will be put into perspective together with the findings from the interviews. This study consists of an interview sampling of twenty-six persons

involved in the 2022 FIFA World Cup work plan (thirteen construction workers, eight public/governmental employees, and five private sector representatives). The findings are measured in percentages throughout the thesis, and they showed that respondents believed that specific measured reforms were enormously appreciated, usually in a 90-95% proportion.

The development of the economy in the whole region of the Gulf Cooperative Council questions the workers' treatment and the migrant workforce that sustains Qatar. The country has attracted attention because of the poor treatment of its migrant workers. The State has tried to avoid its primary responsibility of protecting them by excluding them from the labour legislation (Arif, 2015, p. 183). The so-called Qatar Labour Law has been in existence since 2014, touches upon the private sector and the public sector, and was promulgated by the Ministry of Labour & Social Affairs. However, Arif illustrates that Qatar's focus has been directed to winning the bid to stage the 2022 World Cup final. As a result, the increasing concerns on human rights violations when preparing for and during the events has placed the country at a focal point.

Global attention is focused on Qatar to specify how its employment regulations (as provided within Law No. 14 of 2004) are being implemented by various stakeholders involved with the events to eliminate human rights violations, particularly labour rights. The labour law system of Qatar is among the most restrictive in the region, using the *Kafala* employer method, detailed in section 5.4 of this chapter. This system restricts immigrant employees from accessing the essential aspects of national labour law. Here, the workers work in a highly enclosed private setting; therefore, those violations are not readily observable even if their rights are violated (Arif, 2015, p. 184). In this case, the Government should strive to prevent breaches in private settings.

Based on the illustrations presented by Black, Gibson, and Booth (2016, p. 16), Qatar has been known as a country that violates individual worker rights. When it won the bid to host the

2022 World Cup, the outcry increased internationally concerning the rights of those people involved in the construction of the stadiums, which came from international press (especially in 2019 from the Guardian, France 24, BBC, and others), and NGOs such as Amnesty International. Allegations of workers' abuse are presented in Figure 4, where Amnesty International states that certain factors may lead to the infringement of human rights, such as the *Kafala* system, late or non-payment of wages, prohibition of workers' organisations, weak enforcement of laws, and barriers within the justice system. Due to being accorded the bid of staging these significant events, the State decided to respond to the international outcry arising from different parts of the world. The nation has acknowledged that it will honour human rights during its preparations for the mega-sporting event held in 2022. The country has made promises of scrapping the press allegations (including the abuse of workers' rights that leads to death, as stipulated by the World Politics Review on 15 October 2019) which are contained in its controversial labour laws to improve the conditions of the immigrant workers as it prepares for the finals (IHRB, 2016, p. 14). As detailed in the methodology (chapter two), through interpretation of the questionnaire and data from the secondary source, the study identifies potential issues Qatar will face in hosting the mega-sporting event. The nation may successfully host the event without a notable violation of human rights, addressed by the international community and NGOs. In that case, Qatar has an opportunity to become the sporting hub of the region. Other international tournaments could be held in the state since it has demonstrated its ability and improved global perception of the nation. In this view, the study will focus significantly on the reforms of Qatar that can protect workers' rights and how the country commits to providing a successful global event. Through such evaluation, other states can develop an awareness of the proper action needed to prepare and have the event held in their countries at a future date.

Figure 4: Factors Leading to Abuse of Migrant Workers

5.3 Reforms of the *Kafala* System

The Head of Labour Inspection Departments' statement illustrated that 'the *Kafala* system that was abusive to workers' rights has been replaced by the job contract system which consists of major reforms that safeguard human rights'. Amnesty International insists that the *Kafala* system is problematic for workers, as explained in Figure 4 above. Further information provided reveals that the job contract system has been greatly modernised and increases job flexibility. The Ministry of Interior and ADLSA officials held a press conference whereby several plans were unveiled concerning the reformation of the previous system of Qatar. The Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs of Qatar is now responsible for approving all workers' contracts from foreign countries before granting visas. Based on the information given by the Head of the Labour Sector, 'Initially, many workers from foreign nations were entering Qatar only to realise that their employers in the country had changed their working contracts without their consent... wages and bonuses...lowered.' In this regard, this was the first step of an extensive process that

was significant in reforming the labour system, which later saw the establishment of the contract system.

Additionally, the contract system brought about changes that improved the working environment for the immigrant workers through increased efficiency. Consequently, it ended the visa selling practice and prevented several counterfeit companies from misusing visas' laws. The Head of the Labour Sector noted further that Qatar is grateful and has concerns for the millions of workers involved in ongoing construction activities as the country prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals. They are also crucial to Qatar in facilitating rapid change, especially during this period of infrastructural development. The implementation of the new law was a significant step in improving working conditions for and protecting the expatriate workers that are in Qatar. Wang & Bao (2018) referred to this in the literature in regard to denying workers' rights and forcing them to endure unfavourable working practices, but Qatar have now reversed this policy. The respondent continued to explain that the country is making substantial reforms in improving working conditions. Therefore, it welcomes any criticism, which of course, remains subjective with every survey undertaken. The government believes it is doing the best that it can do for the migrant workers and can, therefore, provide these expatriate workers with tangible benefits (visible good working conditions such as accommodation, health insurance, etc.). As we have seen from the literature, this is a significant improvement, when previously immigrant workers were in slum areas, that hosted poorer domestic communities thus exacerbating the human rights abuse and inequalities. Qatar have demonstrated that they have addressed issues of previous criticisms of the Beijing Games (Shin, 2009) and of their housing of workers to ensure that is improved (Müller, 2015). Consequently, the country has increased its national monitoring capabilities to ensure that the law is followed efficiently. The increased hiring of compliance contractors to supervise the various

companies that violate the law has achieved this. The enforcement of law number 21, established in 2015, is a significant priority for the government of Qatar.

According to Kemp (2016, p. 1), the officials involved in overseeing the implementation of the plan that has been laid by the government of Qatar stated that the contract systems improved worker treatment compared to the *Kafala* system, which previously tethered workers to one employer. Kemp (2016, p. 2) highlights that this kind of system works by simplifying the jobs handled by immigrant workers. Consequently, the Shura Advisory Council was contacted to change the rules that govern the 'exit visas' allowing individuals to exit the country and find other jobs within global markets. According to the director of human rights in Qatar's Interior Ministry, under the rules established via the new system, a contractual relationship between the employer and the employee is allowed (Kemp, 2016, p. 2). Kemp (2016, p. 2) further explains that the employee is free to leave the country with the new rules and regulations. If the employer has any objection, they would be required to show 'highly compelling' proof of why they do not want the worker to leave the country. Any disputes that might arise during the work would be attended to and resolved within fewer than three days. Other changes included the employee welfare contracts, mandatory for every employee. However, sanctions are available for employees who cannot honour their obligations and regulatory links relatively close to the immigrant worker's country of origin. However, this pertains to the legal system and requires an investigation of how many sanctions apply to employers and how many were raised by employees; unfortunately, this is not closely examined within this thesis.

Under the new system, the authorities believe that freedom of movement is guaranteed. The workers have the right to leave the country but only after the worker has notified the employer, including when one wants to go or respond to an emergency (Al-Assaad, 2017, p. 1). Additionally,

workers are allowed to permanently leave the country (Al-Assaad, 2017, p.10). This is possible regardless of whether the duration of the contract has been completed or not. However, this is only permitted if notification is given to the employer based on the terms stipulated in the contract. For example, if an employer is seeking a leave request and the employer declines, in that case, the migrant worker has the right to appeal by sending his grievances to the Exit Permit Grievances Committee. The Committee provides a response within three days to all requests presented by a worker. If they have no additional restrictions in place, such as an ongoing criminal proceeding or an outstanding debt to settle, the applicant will be allowed to leave the country (Al-Assaad, 2017, p. 1). It is unclear what happens if the debt represents unpaid or delayed wages. The workers will no longer require the approval of their employers to change jobs once a fixed-term contract has been completed.

Additionally, individuals operating within an open contract do not require employer approval to change jobs if they complete a service year period of five years. Employers found guilty of confiscating their employees' passports will be subject to a fine of up to QR 25,000 per worker. Employers are only allowed to keep employee passports if a written approval by the employee is provided. (Al-Assaad, 2017, p. 13). These measures have been put in place to reduce employee enslavement cases, as witnessed previously.

The reforms implemented by the government of Qatar were based on the recommendations initially presented by DLA Piper, a London law firm. The firm was commissioned to make significant reviews of the state's legislative and enforcement framework. Reports published in the media (Guardian, 14 May 2014) investigated the workers' conditions while acknowledging previously published reports (Lemon, 2016). According to Lemon (2016, p. 1), reports published by the

Guardian, Amnesty International, and the HRW outlined several cases about employees working under challenging conditions, low wages, and delayed payments.

Additionally, Black, Gibson, and Booth (2016) note that some workers were not allowed to leave the country, while others experienced withheld wages for no apparent reason. To escape the brutality of their employer sponsors, hundreds of workers faced death and found themselves in a situation described as a 'Kafkaesque nightmare' (Black, Gibson, and Booth, 2016, p. 19). The International Trade Confederation Union warned that if the system continues without appropriate measures to protect workers' rights, four thousand workers could lose their lives before 2022. (Black, Gibson, and Booth 2016, p. 16). The firm DLA Piper employed a working crew of ten people. A colleague shared this information detailed in the 140-page report; however, I have not read the report.

Following increasing international pressure to reform the *Kafala* system, the government of Qatar demonstrated a solid commitment to updating labour laws. Sepp Blatter, past President of FIFA, and a major facilitator in awarding Qatar the mega-sporting event hosting contract, pointed out that Qatar's reforms were a significant step, and that the country was headed in the right direction. He asserted that workers could experience a positive change that is highly sustainable and maintains the welfare standards of the workers in Qatar (Black, Gibson, and Booth, 2016, p. 20). However, it is essential to note that FIFA launched legal action against Sepp Blatter to approve an untrustworthy payment, leading to the gain of illicit funds (BBC, 16 December 2019). Consequently, by the laws eliminating the *Kafala* system, it is no longer referred to as 'Sponsor' but rather a proper relationship between an employee and the employer.

Those in charge in Qatar understood not only the need for reforms on a human rights basis, but also, as we can see from the literature (Kassens-Noor, et. al., 2015), the suggestion that mega-

sporting events can have long-lasting economic implications, secure foreign investment, and create platforms for international cultural, economic, political, and social exchange. These are important both in the region and beyond for Qatar and thus setting the example of labour law reform and doing the correct thing in human rights terms was high on their agenda.

The law reforms were a significant relief to the many foreign workers residing in Qatar. These workers account for 85% of the population, meaning only 15% of individuals in Qatar are citizens (World Report, 2017, p. 13). With an estimated size of around 500,000 individuals, the Indian community in Qatar in particular benefited greatly from these laws (World Report, 2017, p. 13). Doha, the capital city of Qatar, has also benefited from the immigrant workforce. Immigrant labour has contributed to the successful construction of elaborate buildings, large scale projects, and immense wealth for the city. The published report provided insights to the government of Qatar on what measures employers need to initiate to improve working conditions (World Report, 2017, p. 13). If the recommendations are taken seriously by the government, immigrants will be treated with the same dignity as other people in Qatar, and the immigrants' contributions to the improvement of Qatar will be acknowledged.

Legal changes were continually being scrutinised. However, Osman (2017, p. 2) demonstrated conditions of the workers improved despite the reports intending to spoil Qatar's image. Qataris were ready to enhance their image despite reports revealing the poor conditions of the workers, the death of the immigrant labourers, and many other issues that surrounded immigrants. According to Black, Gibson, and Booth (2016, p. 18), the changes embraced by Qatar were described as 'market reforms that were far-reaching', and the announcement of the changes was made by two ministries that had jointly come together to address this issue. The Interior Ministry and the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs were involved in a press

conference updating the global community. The government wanted the entire world to be aware of its positive initiatives, so they held a conference in one of Doha's luxurious hotels. Journalists were invited and welcomed with high-level protocol before the conference (Laghani, 2014, p. 2). Laghani (2014) explains further that the senior officials of the government represented the country. After the announcement, many foreigners involved in the law pointed out a general improvement in cooperation levels. Qataris have now changed their attitudes towards foreigners and engage openly with foreigners (Osman, 2017, p. 1). This new law may eliminate the word 'sponsorship', but it leaves the same basic system intact. It is a positive sign that Qatar has accepted that its laws were fuelling abuse, but these inadequate changes will continue to leave workers at the mercy of exploitative bosses. Consequently, Qatar allows their press to criticise them for pointing out their weaknesses as it gives them a chance to improve before the 2022 mega-sporting event. However, Qatari's attitude towards migrant workers and foreign business partners may not be the same.

Qatar's Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs has taken significant steps to adhere to international human rights law by eliminating the *Kafala* system (Lemon, 2016, p. 2). This study has examined the ratification of Qatar of international human rights in the literature review. Subsequently, through the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs, the government is trying to inform workers of their rights by publishing a booklet containing pertinent information for workers (Human Rights, 2015, p. 15). Additionally, the Ministry requested local embassies to translate the brochures into the native languages of immigrant workers so that they would be able to understand their rights.

Furthermore, officials notified HRW after conducting a series of educational seminars. These seminars were intended to inform workers of their rights. By informing the media, the government tried to demonstrate to the global community that Qatar was making significant steps towards

enforcement of human rights (HRW, 2016, p. 12). These actions are an essential step as they further demonstrate Qatar's willingness to abide by international standards.

According to the HRW (2016), Qatar's World Cup local organising committee, namely the country's 2022 Supreme Committee, was accorded the responsibility of oversight and coordination concerning the various constructions that are related to the 2022 World Cup and is striving towards achieving the best conditions for the workers across Qatar's sectors, which are being developed in their efforts to accomplish the 2022 World Cup infrastructure. Based on the Emiri decree, established in 2011, the primary task of the Supreme Committee involves creating a suitable environment for all those involved in facilitating a successful mega-sporting event (HRW, 2016, p. 19). In the bid for the 2022 World Cup, all associated processes must be legal (this remains subject to analysis). In 2012, the Secretary of the Committee, Hassan Al Thawadi, acknowledged the existence of several labour issues in the country. Still, Qatar was actively reforming the law to ensure all working conditions would meet international labour standards (HRW, 2016, p. 20). Furthermore, through press conferences and interviews with international news sources, Hassan Al Thawadi continued to publicise the government and organising Committee's commitment to adhere to the international principles in all its affairs (BHR, 6 April 2017; Al Jazeera, 22 August 2017; Guardian, 17 December 2019).

According to the HRW (2016, p. 20), obtaining contractual guarantees for the workers' rights was the first step in ensuring better protection for the people. Therefore, amending of the law clauses was actioned to ensure they were comprehensive, easy to enforce, and that well-upheld fundamental labour rights were internationally recognised. The HRW researched by writing a letter to Qatar's Supreme Committee and the company that had been contracted to oversee the constructions (CH2M HILL), to make inquiries on the necessary steps that had been taken to ensure

that the rights of the workers were not being violated in any way. The entities wrote a letter demonstrating that they were working to ensure that the working conditions exceeded the established international standards. A strategic plan had been established and was ongoing to improve the working conditions that the workers are exposed to (Sophia, 2014, p. 13). Sophia explains further that the companies were working towards enhanced payment for the workers, ensuring good health, and ensuring safety conditions. The Supreme Committee illustrated that it had already drafted some policies on the rights of the employees and determining the rights that the worker is entitled to, and the kind of commitments that must be made by any company that Qatar has contracted to carry out the various developmental projects for the 2022 World Cup.

Based on HRW (2012, p. 9), the response given by CH2M HILL Company illustrated that the company had emphasised its commitment to ensuring that the workers' rights are respected. This was in respect to the ethics that the company upholds, on the virtue of being human, and its business principles, which involve a zero-tolerance policy when it comes to the issue of human trafficking, as well as or instead of using forced labour. According to the company, they had worked jointly with the Supreme Committee to develop a contract language (an appropriate contract wording understandable to both parties, which remains an issue that needs further investigation in another study), mandatory for both the employer and the employee. In addition, an assurance protocol was put in place that had to be followed to address the significant issue of working standards for the employees at Qatar construction sites (HRW, 2016, p. 23). The comprehensive work policies and measures played an essential role in reducing the cases of employee abuse by any firm working in the construction of the facilities.

FIFA became interested in Qatar's activities to ensure the requirements before allowing Qatar to host the 2022 World Cup mega-sporting event. Through the influence of FIFA, Qatar

started to show corporate social responsibility actions which demonstrated its capability of positively impacting football businesses (Hong and Lu, 2016, p. 11). It has also been illustrated that Qatar is working to ensure that conditions that are established by contracts which the World Cup offers are fulfilled, because this is an assessment that will determine if the country will be awarded the benefit of hosting other mega-sporting events, such as the Olympics, among many others (Hong and Lu, 2016, p. 12). Moreover, the country will always work towards ensuring that these conditions have been met and fulfilled. The Mega-Sporting Events Platform for Human Rights (2017c, p. 13) shows that Gianni Infantino, the FIFA President, made a two-day visit to Qatar, and made further announcements that an oversight body had been created with independent members so that it can oversee the whole process. The oversight body is expected to be an independent committee to monitor working conditions for the World Cup sites in Qatar. This means that as Qatar prepares for the event, the oversight role ensures fair working conditions and that human rights are not violated.

Human rights watchdogs have made efforts to contact the firms that had been given some responsibilities in constructing various facilities for the 2022 World Cup, to ascertain where several media had initially reported abuses. This involved the Doha Zone Company and the Doha International airport. According to the information presented by Sophia (2014, p. 1), it had initially been reported that the company had hired several contractors to operate in the construction sites. However, the company responses proved that the firm had included clauses that significantly protected the workers' rights. Sophia (2014, p. 2) further described that Aspire Logistics Company, which is involved with the management of the Aspire Zone, explained that it had included several clauses that provide some coverage on the protection of the workers' rights in the contracts. In this

regard, the company has employed another third party as a project manager, responsible for monitoring whether the contractors and the subcontractors are adhering to the provisions of the law and that any violations that the workers report are heavily penalised through legal sanctions.

The *Kafala* system was transformed in 2016 via the 'contractual agreement'. However, substantial changes only happened in the second phase of this reform, in 2018. For instance, in 2016, the legislation still had restrictions on employees (such as a five-year contract term and restrictions on movement). In October 2018, Qatar abolished the exit permit entirely, meaning that all construction workers can leave the country without the employer's permission. Qatar's reforms may still have room for improvement. However, when we look back, it is the first time that the *Kafala* system has received so much attention in being reformed, and it is essential to note that it was revised twice in a short period with considerable improvements towards migrants' workers that were previously non-existent, in 2016 and 2018.

5.4 Working Conditions

5.4.2 Payment and Reduced Number of Working Hours

Qatar has regularly been criticised by the international press, as presented in the previous section and Figure 4. It pays low wages to the staff on construction sites as it prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals. However, the Amnesty Report shows that low payments were delayed over prolonged periods. This raised pressing questions about the position of Qatar in trying to protect the rights of these workers. Primary research was conducted, which involved interviewing Qatar State officials. As a result, according to Senior Government Official 4, in their role as Policy Assistant within the Ministry of Labour, “the government of Qatar has put several measures in place to ensure that the rights of workers are upheld. These measures include a set of policies established by the country, adequate safeguarding, and timely payment” (quote from an interview, conducted

in December 2018). Additionally, as documented by the Ministry of Labour, Qatar has established applicable rules aimed at paying workers involved in constructing the various facilities used for the 2022 World Cup finals. According to the Senior Government Official 1 in their role as Policy Advisor within the Ministry of Labour, “Based on the new payment legislation, all individuals who have been given contracts must ensure that there are bank accounts set for the workers so that an auditable transaction system can be created. Additionally, all the workers are paid through an electronic system. This allows the authorities to determine and verify whether the payments have been delivered to the workers at the appropriate time based on the regulations provided in the new charter” (quote from an interview, conducted in December 2018).

These are only one aspect of the several labour policies that Qatar has introduced to protect workers' rights, and achieve its foreign policy objective in demonstrating to the world that the country is working to continually improve the conditions of the workers as the country heads towards FIFA 2022.

The information is in harmony with the secondary research conducted by Atallah (2017, p. 1). Atallah says that, after Qatar secured the bid to host the 2022 World Cup finals, the country received much criticism in several NGOs reports, such as Amnesty International, which thoroughly covered issues related to the violation of human rights. The reason is that the country subjected individuals to harsh working conditions and low wages. However, Qatar made significant reforms to address some of the criticisms that were presented in the reports to create a positive image. The question that arises here is the positive image matching the reality on the ground, which we will investigate within this chapter. One of the significant reforms that the state adopted is an improved Wage Protection System (WPS) (I.L.O., 2019, p. 2). Based on HRW (2015), the country initiated its significant initiatives on reforming the payment system to ensure that the thousands of

workers constructing the 2022 World Cup venues are made in a timely fashion. Qatar's Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs successfully implemented the Wage Protection System. The new law was approved and therefore saw the workers being paid through direct bank transfers. The law stipulates that the employers who are not able to implement this system can be subjected to a one-month prison term and, at the same time, a payment of a fine of \$1650 (HRW, 2015, p. 3). Such repercussions may seem severe to the employer, but the penalty is relatively small to pay for a wealthy employer. The imprisonment of employers can only be guaranteed if the government plays its role well, then it will be possible to reduce the issues of workers abuse significantly.

According to Ataullah (2017), the Wage Protection System law requires that all the companies prepare payment sheets for their employees, with all the details, including the employees' wages and the overtime that every employee was subjected to the whole month. Based on the Business Times (2015, p. 2), the employees could be paid once or twice every month under the Wage Protection System. The Wage Protection System presents a transparent payment method by the various managers heading the construction companies in Qatar. However, the company must not tamper with the payment sheets, and if this happens, the system that was put in place will reveal this. The company involved will be blacklisted, which will theoretically affect their ability to obtain another contract. Ataullah (2017, p. 2) shows further that the construction companies in Qatar are profoundly afraid of being blacklisted if they go against these new rules and regulations and, as a result, be banned from recruiting more workers.

From the primary research, the Senior Government Official 5 in their role as Policy Officer within the Ministry of Labour, who is involved in overseeing the general process of recruitment illustrated that:

“There have been concerns on issues related to the number of working hours for immigrant workers. Some of the reforms that have been linked to the worker's payment system are about the number of working hours. One of the conditions that the wage payment system has outlined is that the employees are not subjected to long work hours”.

He added further that “the number of working hours has been reduced to 8 hours” (quote from the interview, conducted in December 2018).

From this argument, the Senior Government Official 5 justified that overworking exploits workers' rights. When workers work for long periods, they are exhausted without pay for these extra-long hours. The companies awarded work on the construction site of the 2022 World Cup are Nakheel Landscapes and Gulf Contracting (Business HR Centre, 2017). In this regard, the companies that have been given tenders in various sectors as Qatar prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals have been forced to employ additional workers to lower the working hours and stop the exploitation of the workers on their construction sites.

The payment reform follows some of Qatar's labour law provisions that were amended to lower the working hours that people are subjected to. The law outlined that; people are supposed to work for a maximum of 8 hours/day. Additionally, if there is overtime for any work, then this should be two hours at max. Therefore, if they are not able to recruit more workers, then they will not be able to complete their work by the 2022 World Cup events because the present workers are not allowed to work beyond their maximum hour or instead the two hours dedicated for overtime (10h/day).

Based on the secondary research presented by Atallah (2017, p. 5), a manager in one of the construction companies illustrated that they had hired some 20%, additional workers as a strat-

egy to lower the overtime hours that the workers used to work so that they can meet the requirements of the law. According to Atallah (2017, p. 6), the manager illustrated further that the extra workers made it possible for the company to complete a work site which was shut down on a Friday and thus give the workers a week off. It is worth mentioning that Friday shutdowns are common for religious reasons in most Gulf states. Initially, companies were forced to make their workers attend work at the site during their off days because of the high workload.

SC-Project is a world leader in the construction of motors systems. According to AECR (2017), the SC projects steadily raised the number of workers on their construction sites. For instance, in 2010, the SC projects increased its number of workers by over 80%. From the 5,200 workers in January 2016, there were 9,600 workers by December 2016. Consequently, the Supreme Committee expected numbers to increase by approximately 36,000 in 2017 and 2018 (AECR 2017, p. 13). In this regard, the Supreme Committee believes that more resources are needed to ensure that it facilitates its compliance program (AECR, 2017, p. 14). This goes beyond measuring the performance of the contractors as it tries to ensure that there are significant improvements in meeting the workers' welfare standards and thus protecting human rights. In this regard, according to the Labour Ministry of Qatar, every worker is entitled to at least one day off that is paid for every week.

Based on an external neutral source (Impact Limited), the *Annual External Compliance Report of the Supreme Committee for Delivery & Legacy's Workers' Welfare Standards (2017)* shows that people do not work on Fridays unless there is an emergency. Moreover, if they work, they will be compensated in the following two ways. First, they will be paid 150% of their reasonable wages due to working on a Friday. Alternatively, they can be awarded another day of the week off to compensate for the Friday that they worked. However, no employee will be allowed

to work consecutively for two Fridays. That is per article 75 of Qatar's law which states that 'The worker shall be allowed a weekly paid rest which shall not be less than twenty-four consecutive hours and Friday shall be the weekly rest day for all workers except for the shift workers [...]' (Annual External Compliance Report, 2017, p. 29). The international standards apply to all sovereign states. Due to the improved working conditions, it is noted that there is a significant improvement when it comes to the productivity of the employees. The lowered overtime and weekly mandatory rests enhance the employees' lives and working conditions (Ataullah, 2017, p. 5). The same source continues to explain that the manager illustrated that improved working conditions have led to continually fresh and healthy workers and, thus, more productive than when they are tired and restless.

Consequently, the same manager illustrated that his company is rigorous in implementing the established rules and regulations that govern the time off that is given on Fridays and overtime duties. As a result, the company has only two hours of overtime, and workers are not taken to the site on Fridays unless an emergency needs to be attended to. Black (2015, p. 39) also highlights that some workers wanted to work on Fridays, which is supposed to be their day off, to earn more money. Still, they were not allowed to, and were forced to rest, because the management had realised the challenges of going against the rules and the benefits that result from workers having some rest. This is somewhat debatable because Friday prayers are important in religious states.

According to Black (2015, p. 41), the contracted workers expressed that they were delighted with the new laws and the companies to ensure that their rights have not been violated. They claimed that they are exhausted from when they used to work for so long without rest and walk up to the job sites when they are completely worn out. With the improved wage payment system rules and improved work conditions, the manager demonstrated that some of the workers

were willing to work overtime hours to earn some extra money (Ataullah, 2017, p. 6). The workers' commitment was motivated by the reward provided, thereby showing the importance of proper remuneration. This is shown as a challenging factor to balance between the right to voluntary overtime and the right to rest in a working environment.

5.4.3 Cooling Technology

According to the Senior Government Official 1, in their role as Policy Advisor within the Ministry of Labour, in response to the interview that was conducted in December 2018:

“I am pleased by some of the ongoing improvements and measures that Qatar is making to improve the working conditions of the workers, especially in protecting them from being exposed to the excess heat on their respective construction sites. I understand that no sufficient cooling technology can eliminate the challenge experienced by the workers during summertime; however, the helmets designed will help lower the temperature the workers are exposed to, which has eased their working conditions”.

The helmet technology assists with an air breeze to cool the head and protect against the direct light of the sun. In Qatar, the climate is desert, with very mild winters and sweltering and sunny summers (June-July-August). Temperatures in summer times can reach up to 42 degrees Celsius (Weather Atlas). These helmets are an example of excellent efforts showing that, as Qatar continues with the construction of the 2022 World Cup facilities, it continually improves the working conditions of the workers. In his statement, Senior Government Official 1 illustrated that the country has also adopted some other measures besides cooling technologies, especially during summer. He explained that, at times, Qatar is in a desert region. Therefore, the country experiences an increase in heat by over 100 degrees (Fahrenheit, which means approximately. 37 degrees Celsius), especially between 11.00 AM and 3.00 PM. During these hours, no cooling technology is

sufficient to keep the workers safe in their construction sites. Therefore, all construction works are stopped from 11.00 AM and resumed at 3.00 PM. This ensures that the workers are not exposed to harsh working conditions in the excessive summer heat.

Based on Krug (2016, p. 10), the Supreme Committee is trying to ensure that several initiatives can facilitate the cooling of the workers. In this regard, cooling helmet technology was identified. This was an excellent opportunity to enhance the daily lives of the construction workers at the construction sites during the summer months (Krug, 2016, p. 10). Consequently, several other types of cooling products have been identified in the market. Their effectiveness and suitability are assessed for use in the various construction sites as the country prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals (Leung, 2017, p. 1). In August 2016, after an intensive market assessment, shortlisting consisted of several products such as cooling helmets or solar helmets, cooling towels, cooling vests and ice packs tested to assess how effective they were during hot periods.

According to Leung, one of the products chosen were cooling towels (cooling fabric materials), which are towels used to lower temperature. According to Leung (2017, p. 1), after the towels have been immersed in water, they can cool down the temperature for four hours. According to the organisation involved in overseeing the construction works as Qatar prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals, these towels will be provided to the workers across all the construction sites so that the workers can wear them on their necks and around their arms so that they can experience suitable cooling effects without their movements being restricted. Leung explains that the feedback concerning the cooling towels has been positive as it makes the workers at the construction sites more comfortable. According to Mahmoud Qutub, who heads the Workers Welfare Division, by addressing the pressing needs of the workers, such as excessive heat stress during summer periods,

they are achieving some extensive improvements in improving the working conditions of the workers (Leung, 2017, p. 1). As a result, 10,000 cooling towels were procured in 2017 for the workers, and cooling vests (pumping air on the upper part of the body) were bought in 2017 from various selected stores (Sky Sports, 2017, p. 1). The towels were primarily meant to improve the working conditions of the employees by offering a supportive environment.

Secondly, innovation in Qatar allowed for the development of cooled helmets, as mentioned above. The invention was brought about by the University of Qatar, a leading research university. The helmet has an excellent capability to lower the skin's temperature by ten degrees (Sky Sports, 2017, p. 1). Cooling towels facilitate safer working conditions, especially in the summer months. The scientists based at Qatar University designed a suitable hard hat that is solar powered to improve the condition of the labourers constructing the stadiums. The helmet has a fan that helps lower the temperature by blowing air into the individual's face. Construction workers have continually suffered abuses, as they represent one of the vulnerable population groups (France-Press, 2016, p. 2). Therefore, it is critical to ensure that workers have a conducive environment for working as it improves their work ethic. Solar-powered helmets have been undergoing adequate testing and production by a group of Doha-based scientists cooperating with Qatar University (see Figure 5). These helmets are being produced explicitly for the workers involved in constructing the Khalifa International Stadium and the Al Bayt Stadiums (France-Press, 2016, p. 3). During the last testing phases to produce the helmets for the other stadiums being constructed, detailed research was done in Qatar. The study involved the testing of the climatic chamber systems, analysing the amount of sweat that is produced by the wearer's head, and the weight of the helmet, to ensure that there is as little weight as possible so that the workers will be able to work comfortably with them on (WWPR, 2017, p. 33). Figure 5 below illustrates an example of the

developed cooling helmet to ensure that workers are protected from the harsh climatic conditions during summer periods.

Other cooling devices developed to lower heat stress involve cooling vests and specialist ice packs, among others, which are selected for employees working in various construction sites (Leung, 2017, p. 1). The market analysis that can facilitate the identification of suitable technologies that can be used for cooling purposes is still ongoing, together with plans for ensuring that the newly formed Qatar innovation community lobbies to establish specialty products tailored to the environment of the state. The primary goal of the Qatar innovation community is to try and create a practical solution that is highly sustainable for the FIFA 2022 World Cup finals and beyond (WWPR, 2017, p. 33).

Figure 5: Example of Cooling/Solar Helmets for the Workers on Qatar's Construction Sites

5.4.4 Accommodation Facilities

Based on the Head of Inspection Section's response, 'several contractors have constructed accommodations based on the standards that had been set by the welfare associations' (CS News-

.Content redacted due to GDPR restrictions

room, 2017, non-paginated). He further argued that 'the contractors started building the accommodation facilities near the construction sites. Having these places near the construction sites lowers the worker's time to travel to the sites and thus creates time for their leisure' (CS Newsroom, 2017, non-paginated). But one may argue that having such relaxation areas within the construction site itself can be a measure to ensure control over workers and close monitoring, including the blurred line between work and leisure time. That information is supplemented by the second Annual Worker's Welfare Progress Report (p. 11), which illustrates that the accommodation facilities were constructed based on the contractors' Workers Welfare Standards. These houses have recreational facilities for the workers and are very comfortable. In addition, several new computers were installed, mainly at the Teyseer Security Services building, to facilitate connection programs as a requirement of the worker's welfare association is workers being provided with computer rooms and free Wi-Fi. Thus, an accommodation facility was constructed based on the worker's welfare standards.

Figure 6: Illustration of Accommodation Facilities to be Constructed, Based on the Worker's Welfare Standards

The following section elaborates on the accommodation for construction workers of the Khalifa International Stadium. According to WWPR (2015), the accommodation facility known as Midmac houses approximately 1,200 workers. The facility is located within the industrial area of Qatar. The facility has been fitted with the required specifications established in the Workers' Welfare Standards and, therefore, creates an environment that is healthy and safe for the workers involved with the construction of the Khalifa International Stadium. The accommodation site has free laundry services and catering services that deliver food prepared by an in-house caterer for the workers in the stadium, where they are served fresh hot meals within the dining hall, located within Midmac. In addition, there are cleaning services within the accommodation bedrooms and common areas, shaded resting facilities, a medical doctor that is present (full time) to cater for the workers, indoor recreational areas, several TV rooms, free Wi-Fi for the workers, and a barber-shop. Figure 6 is a picture illustrating an example of improved Midmac accommodation housing.

Galfar Al Misnad was allocated the responsibility of housing workers involved in the construction of Lusail Stadium (Dávalos, 2016, p. 1). The Galfar Al Misnad workspace is situated in Umm Salal. The facility was an old one that contained single-level porta cabins which were renovated to house the workers. The Workers Welfare Unit (WWU) was established by the Government's Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy. The WWU performed an audit on this housing facility, which had been nominated to house workers. It was discovered that there were several areas of non-compliance that were raising concern. The non-compliance aspects included the hygiene conditions in the kitchen, the bedrooms, and safety measures, among other requirements (Dávalos, 2016, p. 2). Dávalos (2016, p. 3) continues to explain that the WWU and the contractor then agreed to terms on a rectification plan to make sure that all the requirements had been put in

place to ensure that the living conditions for the workers in this accommodation facility are suitable. In addition to the rectification plan, the contractor installed a sewage treatment plant, and the clean water that resulted from the treatment was mainly used in the green areas and flushing toilets. Several points were raised in the rectification plan, and for all the issues to be addressed, the contractor followed the recommendations. The renovation ensured that a complete fire-fighting system had been installed throughout the accommodation. All the facilities within the housing facility had been upgraded; a shade was provided; individual cupboards were installed with lockable storage; the living units have some laid aggregates between them; there is a full-time doctor present at the facility's registered clinic to ensure that sick cases arising within the facility are attended to. The clinic has a full emergency room and different rooms separated from the clinic, with several beds used for out-patient care (Dávalos, 2016, p. 3). Figure 7 represents illustrations of the Galfar Al Misnad housing conditions before and after implementing the improved Workers Welfare Standards.

Figure 7: Illustrations Before and After Improvement of Workers' Accommodation in Qatar

5.5 The Establishment of the Workers Charter

Based on the opinion presented by Senior Government Official 6 in their role as Policy Chief within the Ministry of Labour, the establishment of the workers charter is a suitable measure to protect the health and safety of the workers, among many other measures, in safeguarding the well-being of the workers in various construction sites in Qatar. Furthermore, another respondent, Senior Government Official 7, in their role as Policy Expert within the Ministry of Labour, confirmed that establishing the workers charter is an excellent measure that will allow the Supreme Committee to continually monitor and enforce these principles, to ensure that all the workers are safe. In this regard, the charter is deemed an enormous step forward that will guide the Supreme Committee, which proves that the workers' rights are not violated.

According to the Supreme Committee, all the workers engaged in various projects and those individuals in other infrastructure development roles have the right to be treated appropriately, by ensuring their human rights are not violated (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2016, p. 4). Under the Supreme Committee, the Workers Charter is an extensive document of 111 pages, adopted in 2013, describing regulations and providing definitions for accommodation, accommodation site, worker, contractor, and so forth (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2013, p. 4-6). In addition, the charter includes references for 'worker in the sense of employer of a contractor' and 'worker in the sense of contractor selected in tenders.'

Through the charter, the Supreme Committee affirms its commitment that all the contractors involved in the delivery of the various projects must adhere to the principles established in the charter. This affirmation is well shown in Qatari law as well. Therefore, the guides will always be part of the contracts that the Supreme Committee offers. The contractors will have to sign these to

ascertain that they clearly understand what they need to do to ensure human rights are not violated (Gibson, 2014, p. 2).

The Supreme Committee further illustrates that the selection and retention of contractors and sub-contractors will be based on Qatar's laws and the charter principles. The charter provides several positive elements such as training the workers so that they can gain appropriate skills that are necessary for accomplishing various tasks, including how to avoid injuries that may affect their health; free transportation on the work-accommodation route; documents available in several languages, i.e., Arabic, Bengali, English, Tagalog, Hindi, Nepali, Tamil, and Urdu, etc. However, looking closely at the charter, we can also remark upon some questionable aspects: medical centres do not have a resident nurse unless there are more than 100 workers on the working site or within the accommodation provided. (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2013, p. 74). Furthermore, below 100 workers on-site/within the housing, there are only 'fully trained first aid officers', with at least one for fifty persons (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2013, p. 6).

Additionally, Al-Thawadi stated “this Workers’ Charter is our pledge to ensuring a lasting positive legacy on the wellbeing of workers in Qatar” (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2013, p. 2). Therefore, establishing the Workers Charter is an appropriate measure that can minimise the chances of abuses and human rights violations. However, such a Charter does not mean the complete eradication of human rights abuses, and it is only a normative aspect. Therefore, progress under the provisions of the charter should be carefully measured.

5.6 Welfare, Health, and Safety Regulations

From the interviews conducted, Senior Government Official 1 stated that “many contractors have dedicated their efforts to developing and implementing individual standards for their

workers to ensure health and safety are adhered to”. He further noted that “most of the medical facilities are well equipped and at the same time, centrally situated so that workers can easily access health care services, especially during the emergency responses”. Thus, those might provide a good option for emergency responses; however, it is essential to note that temporary placements cannot replace appropriate transfers to a hospital if the patient needs surgery or long-term treatment.

This information is consistent with the information provided by the Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy (2016, p. 4), which asserts that some measures have been put in place to ensure that high medical standards have been implemented for workers to access sufficient health care. The best example of this is Bin Omar Trading and Contracting (BOTC) that has 5,000 workers in Qatar of which, 540 of its workers have been taken to aid the construction of Al Bayt stadium. The BOTC has fully licensed medical facilities at its accommodation, with three licensed doctors, ten registered general nurses, and the support manager. The operations are available 24/7, with rotational shifts. However, we have seen in the previous section that accommodation sites or work sites with below 100 workers do not have a permanent nurse on location, but only trained first aid officers. The image below illustrates the treatment of patient workers (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2016, p. 4). Figure 8 is an illustration of the BOTC medical facility room for the treatment of patients.

Figure 8: Illustration of BOTC Medical Facility Room for the Treatment of Patients

The BOTC maintains a medical record room dedicated to medical files well documented for the over 5,000 workers, under anonymity (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2016, p. 4). When health screening is done, the individual workers who are diagnosed with hypertension are put on a specialised nutrition programme. The identification involves ID cards that are colour-coded and identify patients by their specific dining area to be provided with food based on their dietary nutrient requirements (Sophia, 2014, p. 1). Consequently, workers diagnosed with diabetes have their food delivered to the sites where they are working based on their identification colour code. Also, in Al Bayt Stadium, the first-aid units have been licensed by the BOTC during working hours. In addition, an employee handbook has been developed by the BOTC to offer some guidance on general health and safety information and raise awareness concerning the potential hazards that can lead to medical incidents. The handbook contains the health policies and the legal regulations required to ensure that workers access appropriate health care. However, manuals and guidance books do not ensure compliance on the ground.

After the publication of the Workers Charter by the Supreme Committee, a publication of the Workers Welfare Standards was published in 2014, and in 2016 an updated Workers Welfare Standards version was published by the Supreme Committee, after undergoing several consultation processes with civil society organisations. According to Senior Government Official 2 in their role as Policy Counsellor within the Ministry of Labour, “the publication of the Worker's Welfare Standards is a measure of ensuring the well-being of the employees is well catered for, bearing in mind that these standards are based on the principles laid by the Workers Charter” (quote from a conducted interview in December 2018). In this regard, the standards translate the principles in the charter into specific contractual requirements. Moreover, they cover the worker's journey from the time of recruitment up to the moment of the worker's departure back to his home country.

In 2013, the Workers Welfare Division was created by the Supreme Committee. The WWD falls under the secretary general's office (Impactt, 2017, p. 13). Therefore, workers in the WWD report directly to the secretary-general. Impactt (2017) continues to show that the primary vision of the WWD is to ensure that Qatar achieves the 2022 World Cup events through best practices in its preparations by promoting the welfare of the workers and supporting social wellbeing as well as human rights in Qatar.

The interview which was conducted with Senior Government Official 3 in their role as Policy Associate within the Ministry of Labour reveals that the establishment of the WWD is significant and highly efficient when it comes to safeguarding workers' rights. Senior Government Official 3 illustrated that “the WWD is therefore responsible in ensuring that there is some good development of governance that is highly effective, as well as ensuring that there is the compliance of the WWS through various enforcement mechanisms” (quote from conducted interview). The

statement from Senior Government Official 3 was confirmed by Senior Government Official 1, who added that:

“The WWD ensures that effective audits and inspections are conducted to ascertain that contractors comply with the guidelines established by the WWS. These inspections are done in the accommodation and various construction sites in Qatar” (quote from a conducted interview in December 2018).

The WWD evaluates the workers' welfare tenders, delivers training activities, and engages in research to develop guiding policies that easily facilitate decision-making based primarily on the issues arising concerning the abuse and violation of human rights.

The Supreme Committee also mandated the establishment of the Workers Welfare Forums for each of the accommodation sites. The workers' representatives ensure that the forums are held regularly (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2016, p. 5). Figure 9 shows how these forums work: some workers are nominated as candidates in elections (no details of proposed candidates are based on voluntary, workers, or contractor proposals). Then, workers vote for the candidates (there is no information on the voting procedure, and if it is conducted as per the international human right to vote provisions). An elected worker may represent up to 200 colleagues under the title of Workers' Welfare Officer. The elected Workers' Welfare Officers meet monthly to address the issues of their colleagues. Problems can be addressed, such as challenges at the sites of accommodation, the working conditions in the construction sites, food being served, the health and safety of the workers, issues related to the payment of salaries, and several other social activities. The WWD typically attends the meeting to ensure that every detail has been captured, and that sufficient information is shared with the team involved with compliance and enforcement so that they can take appropriate actions (Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, 2016, p. 5).

The Supreme Committee strives to ensure that the employees' rights are guaranteed, especially those of foreigners, who are prone to abuse. However, we do not know if colleagues and the elected worker have special sessions to discuss challenges, or if colleagues must discuss 'as friends' with the selected worker (meaning a formal or informal approach modality). We also do not know how many workers' representatives meet (if only contractors or representatives from the Supreme Committee are present). There is also no record or presented decision/report of raised issues that were rectified.

Figure 9: How do Workers' Welfare Forums work?

Also, in the attempt of trying to improve on the grievances of the workers that are typically raised during the welfare forums of the workers, the WWD made a partnership with the 'Qatar Behavioural Insights Unit', that had recently been launched by the Supreme Committee of Qatar to conduct some behavioural experiments for the various welfare forums of the workers that were being undertaken (WWPR, 2015, p. 20). The report continues to illustrate that the joint venture

team that is responsible for overseeing the construction of the Al Bayt Stadium did complete six meetings for the welfare forums of the workers; however, we are not informed about the timeline or duration and outcome of these meetings. According to Adil (2016, p. 1), several issues were raised during the sessions, and among them, 98% have been addressed through appropriate action being taken. Some of the issues raised in these meetings related to the quality and variety of the food, accommodation conditions, the amenities in the construction sites, the laundry facilities, and the arrangements for transports during their visits to the nearby markets and other recreational facilities. Consequently, the workers' representatives are encouraged to attend the meetings and partake in a leadership role by creating suitable programmes and events for the workers they represent.

From the interviews conducted concerning the effectiveness of the Workers' Welfare Forums, the following results show the level of agreement with these reforms, illustrated in Figure 10: 90% of the interviewees strongly agreed that this reform is highly effective in ensuring that human rights are protected. 10% of the respondents said that they agree that the reforms are effective. The difference between 'strongly agrees' and just 'agree' is notable, meaning a very firm opinion, for whatever reason. The respondents perceive the forum's existence as an effective measure to ensure human rights, with a high percentage of agreement. According to Senior Government Official 6, in their role as Policy Chief within the Ministry of Labour, 'I feel...there is the need to increase some external monitors in the forum meeting who will continuously ascertain that indeed, the grievances that had previously been aired have been fulfilled and if not, an action plan is given on what was going on.'

Generally, the ultimate point is that, as Qatar prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals, the country has put in much effort in ensuring that there is a forum for the workers where they can air

their queries on issues which are disturbing them. A more significant percentage (90%) feels that this measure is effective in ensuring that the wellbeing of the workers is maintained.

Figure 10: Level of Agreement of Respondents with the Workers' Welfare Forums

5.7 Compliance and Audit

The Supreme Committee is highly committed to ensuring that the employees are healthy and living in a safe place (WWPR, 2017, p. 18). The WWD monitors compliance with the WWS through impromptu accommodation inspections and other ethical recruitment audits. The inspection cycle is often repeated to avoid issues of evasion. During the process, the WWD frequently audits and inspects all the contractors and several other parties that are involved with contracting. Consequently, WWD receives and evaluates a report that comprehensively covers the compliance with the worker's welfare level of the contractors. According to the Business and Human Rights Resource Centre (p. 3), the welfare standards for the workers are mandatory for all the contractors that are leading the Supreme Committee projects. The Supreme Committee established a four-tier auditing system that enables them to determine whether the companies comply with the established rules to ensure that workers' rights are not violated. They involve the Supreme Committee, the

contractors' WWS, the External Compliance Team, and the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs (Impactt, 2017, p. 13). The groups were specifically targeted to ensure that the welfare of the employees is maintained, whether domestic or foreign workers. FIFA strongly commended the four-tier auditing system, encouraging the following structure of auditing: 'quarterly self-audits by the contractor of itself and other contracting parties; SC audits; external monitor audits by an independent third-party auditor; and Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs (ADLSA) inspections' (FIFA, 2019, p. 27). The sanctions of a contractor in case of non-compliance with the WWS or the laws of Qatar include suspension of payment, rectification at the contractor's cost, listing the contractor as a banned supplier, blacklisting the contractor, reporting the contractor to ADLSA or the State of Qatar Central Tenders Committee, contract termination, or suspension of the contractor's work and demobilisation from the project (FIFA, 2019, p. 27). It is important to note that those sanctions do not include imprisonment or admissions to legal procedures in court. It is considered that the contractor would immediately rectify any violation of an obligation, and in case of persistence, there will only be a contract termination.

Accommodation inspection is also carried out to ensure that the workers live in the right conditions. The auditor sends a message that auditing will take place within 24 hours, and other contracting parties are advised to ensure that their documentation is up to date. The auditor selects an individual to be interviewed (Wells and Fernz, 2016, p. 8). Wells and Fernz (2016, p. 9) note that the auditor of the WWD completes a report with a clear checklist that explains if the contractor is abiding by the worker's welfare standard or not, based on the requirements of the WWS. For instance, the enforcement team that is involved in ensuring there is compliance evaluated sixty-eight tenders. Of these, twenty-two tenders were found not compliant with the WWS, especially

with regards to accommodation, time of travelling from the places of accommodation to the construction sites, and several other critical non-compliances (WWPR, 2017, p. 18). Therefore, this led to the disqualification of the companies' tenders.

From the primary research conducted, Figure 11 illustrates the results on the respondents' views concerning the effectiveness of the compliance and audit reforms that the government of Qatar has put in place to ensure that human rights are not violated. The results are the following: when it comes to the effectiveness of the compliance and audit reforms, 85% of the interviewees strongly agreed that this reform effectively ensures that human rights are protected. 10% of the interviewees agreed that the reforms effectively ensure that human rights are protected. Again, as in the section evaluating the welfare workers' forums, the difference between 'strongly agrees' and 'agree' is notable, meaning a very firm opinion, for whatever reason. One of the explanations provided is that the people involved in compliance and audit may be faced with some external pressure from some companies, who may decide to intrude and interfere with the auditing. This might compromise the results. However, these are only speculations on what could possibly happen, but it has not been evidenced so far.

Only 5% of the interviewees were not sure whether these reforms were sufficient. According to Senior Government Official 8, in their role as Policy Head within the Ministry of Labour:

“I cannot say whether the reforms will be effective or not; all I can say is that the Government of Qatar is trying to ensure that the worker's wellbeing is safeguarded. However, we cannot rule out that creating reforms is one thing and implementing them is another. Therefore, let's give them time to see whether they will work” (quote from an interview, conducted in December 2018).

Generally, from the results, this is a clear indication that a significant percentage (i.e., 85% of the interviewees strongly agreed, and 10% agreed) of the officials believe that the compliance and audit measures put in place by Qatar will be able to protect human rights.

Figure 11: Effectiveness of the Compliance and Audit Report (level of agreement of respondents)

Due to the number of challenges that were identified during the investigations carried out at Al Wakrah Stadium (detailed in section 5.8), because of the accident that had taken place, the Supreme Committee designed a suitable incident investigation procedure that is standardised and applicable to all the Supreme Committee projects (Qatar Report, 2017, p. 28). Methodologies were established on how the incident investigation procedures could be carried out and were immediately implemented following the Khalifa International Stadium fatality. The international investigation procedures cover three significant elements: the notification of the incident, the investigation of the incident, and the reporting of the incident.

Consequently, the international investigation procedures involve several sub-elements, such as assigning a team to conduct the investigations, collecting adequate evidence, carrying out

witness interviews, analysing the available evidence, and drawing conclusions based on the causal analysis (Qatar Report, 2017, p. 28). The Qatar Report (2017, p. 28) shows that the primary objective of conducting the international investigation procedures is to ensure that the needed continuity has been provided for all the stakeholders, which enables them to understand their roles and responsibilities clearly. Furthermore, the measures enable them to work together to achieve the common objective of identifying the primary cause of an incident and to prevent another incident from taking place. This is done by ensuring that appropriate health and safety measures have been reinforced across the various working sites. Consequently, contractor capacity building and having staff who are well-trained for handling emergency responses are essential for all sites. In this regard, the Supreme Committee demonstrates that they are dedicated to ensuring that this incident does not happen again. Through procedures, the Supreme Committee will be able to identify the root causes of incidents, which will guide them in making policies that protect the workers from fatal incidents.

When looking at the international instruments to ensure labour standards on occupational health and safety, I.L.O. adopted more than forty standards and over forty codes of practice in health and safety at work (I.L.O., 2020, non-paginated). However, when it considering Qatar, it is essential to note that despite national procedures to ensure safety at work, the country has not ratified the International Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers and Members of Their Families from 1990 (as seen in chapter 4). In addition, the country has also not ratified the I.L.O. Safety and Health in Construction Convention, 1988.

5.8 Transparency and Reporting

The Supreme Committee for delivery and legacy, continually strives to improve the programmes by identifying suitable opportunities to provide grievance mechanisms to the workers.

Among the best options that were identified, one involved the establishment of a convenient dedicated grievance hotline (Business and Human Rights Centre, p. 1). Following a detailed market analysis, a hotline was obtained. The hotline and the various websites associated with it were launched at the beginning of 2017 (HRW, 2016, p. 6).

Figure 12: Supreme Committee Factsheet of the Hotline Grievances (as of June 2020)

Figure 12 demonstrates the latest updates (as of June 2020) provided by the Supreme Committee (as a fact sheet) regarding the grievance hotline. It operates 24 hours a day, seven days a week. The support is provided in 11 languages (mostly the languages used by migrants). When last consulted, in June 2020, the number of grievances lodged via the hotline amounted to 619, where 97% were declared as solved cases. However, we do not know why the 3% of the remaining cases were not yet solved, what they contain, or if they are still open cases for discussion. The main grievances lodged pertain to ethical recruitment matters (473 cases), accommodation (84 cases), and health and safety (62 cases).

Initially, the workers can provide their grievances in the most confidential way for providing the required feedback to the Supreme Committee. Secondly, the workers can also register on the website and post on the issues that are affecting them. All the grievances that are raised are received by the Workers Welfare Division's senior members are handled effectively (WWPR, 2017, p. 20). The workers can follow up their grievance status through the system until they are comfortable with the solution provided. The grievance hotline enables the workers to raise their concerns and issues that disturb them regarding accommodation, processes associated with recruitment, and conditions arising at the construction sites (HRW, 2016). The Workers Welfare Division has high expectations that there will be a significant utilisation of the hotline in trying to improve the working conditions of the workers.

From the interview, the respondents were able to agree on the effectiveness of this reform, which has been illustrated in Figure 13. From the interviews, 95% of the workers strongly agree that the grievance hotline is an effective measure that has resulted in considerable improvement in ensuring that workers' rights are safeguarded. Consequently, 5% of the respondents agreed that the reform effectively proves that workers' rights are not violated. The respondents mentioned that they had some issues registering on the websites before posting about some of the problems. When an individual decides to post a problem on the website, they can plausibly be traced and known. Therefore, this raises an issue of the confidentiality of the worker's grievance. However, despite this, the workers have a direct link to the Supreme Committee in raising their issues, which illustrates that Qatar is making progress in introducing reforms which protect workers' rights.

Figure 13: Effectiveness of the Grievance Hotline (level of agreement of respondents)

Figure 13 illustrates the results obtained from the interviews concerning the effectiveness of transparent public reporting and the continual development of procedures. The findings are that 95% of the respondents strongly agreed that transparent public reporting and continuous development of procedures effectively protect workers' rights from violation. Additionally, 5% of the respondents agreed that the reform is compelling. A more definitive explanation which was given by Senior Government Official 4 is that:

“I cannot deny Qatar is trying to implement several reforms to ensure workers' rights are not violated. However, although the transparent reports may prove to be effective in providing human rights are not violated, the continuous development of procedures is anticipated to be slow, and we had some doubt about its effectiveness. However, it is noted that even though those are slow, continuous development of procedures has already been achieved” (quote from an interview, conducted in December 2018).

Procedures and changes of regulations may be slow. National strategies always need to pass through several voting procedures, debates, and amendments, which take time. For example,

it was only in 2018 that Qatar ratified the two international human rights covenants, as seen in the literature review discussing Qatar and international human rights.

*Figure 14: Effectiveness of Transparent Public Reporting and Continuous Development of Procedures
(Level of agreement of respondents)*

While speaking of reporting procedures, according to the AECR (2017), public reporting has been made transparent. In 2014, the Supreme Committee published its first *Workers Welfare Compliance Report*, which has continued to be conducted annually in 2015 and 2016 (p. 4). All these reports have provided coverage concerning the activities that the Supreme Committee is committed to, which ensure that the workers' welfare programme is a success. For instance, the Supreme Committee released highly detailed statements concerning significant events that involved workers' fatalities. This involves the 2016 Al Wakrah site fatality and the Khalifa site fatality which happened in 2017. The 2016 Al Wakrah site fatality involves an accident where a Nepalese worker, who was 29 years old, was struck on the head by a water tanker which resulted in immediate death due to severe head injuries. A team was established to shed some light on the

possible causes of the accident. On 29 October 2016, a formal report was released by the investigating team, illustrating that the deceased was crouched by the water tank's passenger side while using his cell phone, and the driver of the vehicle was not aware of the proximity of the worker because of the blind spots that are linked to the large water tankers. What followed is that several gaps in health and safety procedures were identified in the report. The gaps involved a lack of stringent policies and procedures that govern mobile phones at work. As a result, the Supreme Committee established suitable policies and procedures which involves: enforcement of strict rules governing mobile phone usage; provision of education to the workers concerning the blind spots of the vehicles; the dangers associated with using areas that are highly shaded as places of rest; raising the frequency of checks of the driver's competence to ensure that workers are not prone to injuries resulting from preventable accidents; and the implementation of the health and safety hot-line system for ensuring that workers who have suffered from accidents are given sufficient first aid, as well as adequate medical care (AECR, 2017, p. 5). The care taken with the investigations ensures labour sustainability and removes the ill-feeling from the workers when they feel as though they are not wanted.

The second fatality at the Khalifa International Stadium in January 2017 involved a British male, who was a 40 year old rope access technician, falling from a height of 39 metres from the roof when installing the catwalk system at the roof of the stadium. Despite receiving urgent first aid and medical attention, the victim did not make it because of the multiple chest injuries he had received because of falling from a high height. An investigation was immediately initiated and by 29 January 2017 a detailed report had been issued, illustrating some of the possible actions that can be undertaken to prevent other workers from experiencing a similar occurrence. Another method of installing the catwalk system was developed. However, further investigations are still

ongoing concerning other suitable methods, with a review of the continuous assessment of the equipment used for height activities (AECR, 2017, p. 6).

The above two examples illustrate some of the public reports that have been delivered transparently, trying to demonstrate that some ongoing procedures and policies are being used to ensure the elimination of predisposing factors that might expose the workers to accidents and injuries. As Welden (2014) and Todd and Jewell (2016) attest, mega-sporting events can either build or ruin your global reputation and image, affect brand identity and sponsorship, and in turn affect a country's soft power. Arguably, Qatar have recognised the value of the global soft power indexes and watched the impact on Brazil, with the bad publicity from the Rio de Janeiro Olympics in 2016. Seeking to avoid a repeat of those effects, Qatar have sought to increase their global soft power rankings and regional rankings in competition with their neighbours. They have also sought to set an example to their neighbours with their new labour laws and approaches to workers health and safety, even though neighbouring state are not wholly happy that Qatar secured the sole rights to the Games (AFP, 2017).

5.9 Stakeholders and Contractors

Awareness sessions are carried out to ensure that the contractors clearly understand their important role in ensuring that the workers welfare standards are implemented and adhered to (Lemon, 2016, p. 3). From January 2016 to February 2017, the Workers Welfare Division held three awareness sessions to inform over 100 staff members and contractors of their responsibilities. The selected staff and the contractors undergo some training under the Verité Organization, which is highly specialised in improving the working conditions of the workers and assessing social compliance (World Report, 2017, p. 12). Additionally, the World Report (2017) illustrates that they were trained on issues related to the requirements of reporting, and the rectification plans that are

continually needed whenever non-compliance issues arise (p. 13). The existence of awareness training allows the reiteration of certain aspects of laws and measures that are not fully understood or wholly put in practice. However, the awareness training should be complemented by inspections and audit systems (as detailed in the above sections of this chapter).

From the interviews conducted, Figure 15 is a clear illustration of the level of agreement on the effectiveness of the contractor capacity building as a measure that has been put in place to ensure that human rights are not violated. The interview results show that: 85% of the interviewees strongly agreed that contractor capacity building is an effective measure for ensuring the workers' rights are not violated. The interviewees presented several reasons as to why they strongly agreed. One of the reasons presented by Senior Government Official 5 is that “I have a strong belief that the contractor capacity building will create awareness among the contractors concerning their major role in continuously ensuring that the Workers Welfare Standards are not violated in any way”. 5% of the interviewed officials agreed that the contractor capacity building was effective, ensuring the rights of the workers were not violated. According to Senior Government Official 8: “I agree because, despite the workers being aware of their responsibilities, they are expected to be aware but may be under pressure to finish a given task and meet the deadline, with this regard, the rights of the workers are inclined to be violated”.

10% of the interviewees said that they did not know if contractor capacity building is an effective measure that can ensure workers' rights are not violated. However, despite some issues raised by the respondents concerning the effectiveness of contractor capacity building, a high percentage strongly agree and believe that contractor capacity building is an effective measure in trying to ensure that the wellbeing of the employees is safeguarded. Therefore, it seems that respondents believe in Qatar's efforts to minimise human rights and workers' rights violations.

Figure 15: Level of Agreement of the Effectiveness of the Contractor Capacity Building
(Level of agreement of respondents)

The welfare associations are mandated to examine various conditions that the workers are exposed to. This involves inspecting drinking water, sanitary facilities, and the various medical facilities and mess areas (Wells and Fernz, 2016, p. 15). Consequently, Wells and Fernz explain further that health, safety, and accommodation inspections involve the prevention of fire, infrastructure, transportation facilities, medical health care, and traffic and security management. In addition, these inspections are an approach that results in the prevention of accidents. Therefore, they are necessary measures for ensuring that the workers' rights are protected by ensuring that there is an established health and safety culture that is highly sustainable.

From the interviews conducted as primary research for this study, the respondents gave their opinions on the effectiveness of the construction welfare inspections in protecting human rights. Figure 16 illustrates the views of the respondents on the efficacy of the construction welfare inspections. As indicated in the figure above, 95% of the respondents said that they strongly agree that the reform is very effective in ensuring that workers' rights are not violated. However, 5% said that they do not know if the reform will be able to protect workers' rights. One of the reasons given

is that, despite the programme being practical, they are not sure whether it will be regularly done and proven effective through its regularity. However, most respondents seem to have faith in Qatar's reforms and its efforts to minimise workers' human rights violations.

*Figure 16: Level of Agreement on the Effectiveness of the Construction Welfare Inspections
(Level of agreement of respondents)*

From the interviews that were conducted on the effectiveness of the stakeholder engagement, in ensuring that human rights are not violated, all the 24 respondents strongly agreed on the efficacy of this measure in ensuring that human rights are continuously upheld and respected (this represents a 100% strong agreement of all the respondents, and it is the only section rated at its fullest). In this regard, the explanation that was presented by most of the respondents is that stakeholders usually facilitate communication. Of course, this leaves room for interpretation, but respondents perceive stakeholders' representatives as easy to talk to or easy to approach.

Based on the information presented by the WWPR (2017, p. 20), the Supreme Committee continues to engage a wide range of stakeholders to prioritise some of the issues, shares several practices that are regarded to be the best, and develops policies that are highly effective in trying

to address the challenges that workers face. The discussion of the welfare of the workers is regularly done by engaging the contractors with other construction partners involved in ensuring that the work at various construction sites is safe. The WWWR (2017, p. 21) proves that the Supreme Committee regularly engages multiple governing bodies, organisations concerned with workers' rights, NGOs, and delegations from the international arena. Since 2016, the engagement of stakeholders has continued to be a primary focus for the Supreme Committee.

At the beginning of 2016, as part of the second edition of workers welfare development, the Supreme Committee had several consultative meetings with NGOs, such as Amnesty International. Moreover, this also involved the I.L.O., the BWI organisation, the sustainability team of FIFA, and others (WWWR, 2017, p. 23). In March 2016, the Supreme Committee appointed Verité to assist, who offered advice on the tendering processes, and offered some guidance on the Independent External Monitor appointment, which was to facilitate the completion of the third layer of the Supreme Committee's four-tier process of auditing. In addition, the Supreme Committee appointed the Impactt Limited Company as an External Compliance Monitor in April 2016. The role of Impactt is to monitor and ensure that the contractors and the sub-contractors adhere to the standards established for the welfare of the workers. The Impactt Report was also provided in section 5.2, elaborating on working conditions.

Consequently, Impactt provides advisory services to the Supreme Committee. In April 2016, the Supreme Committee was also involved in the UN regional forum held in Asia concerning business and human rights. The Supreme Committee was represented by General Hassan Al Thawadi, the Supreme Committee secretary, alongside the panel of the world's leading human rights experts. The primary aim of attending this event is to facilitate sufficient crafting of policies that

will promote measures that can sustainably protect workers' rights in construction sites and the sector in Qatar.

The BWI is a Global Union Federation formed of independent, democratic trade unions who represent workers in the Building, Building Materials, Wood, Forestry, and Allied sectors. The BWI was founded in December 2005 in Buenos Aires, Argentina. The BWI brings together around 351 trade unions, representing about twelve million members in 136 countries (Supreme Committee-BWI joint-report, 2019, p.14). A Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) was signed in November 2016 between the Supreme Committee and the Building and Wood Workers' International (BWI), which saw the foundations being laid for the health and safety inspections to be regularly carried out through the Supreme Committee-BWI partnership, which incorporates both organisations' representatives (WWWR, 2017, p. 25). The MOU demonstrates further that the commitments of the Supreme Committee are to ensure that the health and safety protocols are well followed to guarantee that the workers are consistently safe and in good health.

The Supreme Committee and BWI published a joint report in 2019 to elaborate on the progress of workers' rights. The report demonstrates that six inspections were carried out on sites in 2019 by the Joint Working Group (JWG), which is mandated to carry out inspections on behalf of the Supreme Committee and the BWI. The assessments are described in the joint report, including challenges and good practices.

Figure 17 represents the findings of the inspection conducted in April 2019 at the Al Bayt Stadium. Issues included the need to install a fire alarm in the chemical storage area, showerheads and privacy curtains being broken at the accommodation site, and the room temperature being registered as high. Good practices included screening urinals in the upper levels of the stadium, good housekeeping, and good protection of workers to prevent accidents.

Impact	Issue	Status
Site	Opportunity for improvements to temporary scaffolding arrangements was observed.	Addressed by Contractor
	Opportunity for improvements to surface preparation activities prior to internal surface painting works was discussed.	
	Projecting steel bar was observed being used to temporarily suspend electrical cables.	
	Chemical storage: provision of secondary containment beneath all stored containers was required, a fire alarm system needed to be installed in the chemical storage area, and eyewash stations needed to be provided.	
Accommodation (Al Bayt Workers' Village)	The shower heads were broken.	Addressed by Contractor
	The rods and hooks of the privacy curtains were broken.	
	The fire extinguisher signs displayed throughout the accommodation were only displayed in English.	
	Due to worker congestion in the mess hall, the room temperature was very high.	
Good Practice	The contractor put in a series of temporary, screened urinals in the upper levels of the stadium.	
	Good standard of housekeeping was observed on site, as well as in the accommodation.	
	Provision and maintenance of edge protection to prevent the accidental fall from height of persons, materials or components was observed.	

Figure 17: Findings from JWC Inspection in April 2019 at the Al Bayt Stadium

5.9.2 Identifying and Explaining Qatar's 2022 World Cup Stakeholders

Throughout this section, Qatar's 2022 World Cup stakeholders will be examined and discussed in terms of two specific areas pertaining to the mega-sporting event itself - the World Cup stakeholders as a major general event, and the mega-sporting events relationship to human rights. By understanding how the event's stakeholders differ from one another when being assessed in terms of the event itself, as well as in terms of the event's human rights measures, a closer assessment of its different implications on a more diverse level can be realised.

First and foremost, the Qatar 2022 World Cup possesses several different major stakeholders when being considered as a general sporting event, which includes some of the country's largest political, economic, and socio-cultural institutions. As such, the World Cup events stakeholders

include not only government institutions such as the Civil Defence Authority, the Qatar Foundation, the Qatar Museums Authority, the Ministry of Public Health, and Qatar rail, but also includes the semi-privatised subsidiaries of these governmentally managed agencies. Msheireb Properties is an important stakeholder within the scope of the event, and has consistently played a significant role as a contractor for many of the event's construction and real estate developments. The properties agency operates as a subsidiary of the Qatar Foundation and is committed to the primary objective of ensuring the nation's forward development towards the 2030 vision. Much like this specific organisation, many of the other mega-sporting events stakeholders are similarly influenced by Qatar's 2030 vision, and within this scope, have prioritised the 2022 World Cup as an incredibly important event leading to the nation's forward-looking progress.

Other major stakeholders affected by the event include Qatar Airways, who plays an important role in developing collaborative partnerships, sponsorships, and marketing projects alongside the mega-sporting event. Two other organisations which operate within the same capacity, albeit to a much lesser extent, include Mosanada and Mowasalat. The first of these two companies is a facilities management specialist organisation that has played a significant and leading role in shaping the workers' changing conditions throughout the course of the mega-sporting event preparation. The second organisation, Mowasalat, is one of the nation's leading public transportation services, and is increasing its capacity and infrastructural network to serve the surge potentially better in people due to the popularity and demand to be expected by the time of the event. Ashghal, another major stakeholder, is the nation's public works authority, which like most of the other organisations listed here, is greatly committed to ensuring that the mega-sporting events infrastructural developments are aligned with the nation's commitment towards its 2030 vision.

Figure 18: Qatar's 2022 World Cup Major Stakeholders

Outside of these stakeholders, Qatar's preparations for the 2022 World Cup have also been greatly influenced by another group of stakeholders, which are specifically shaped by the event's human rights trajectories. This was suggested by Hepburn (2017) in response to the criticism of modern slavery, and Qatar wanting to distance itself from that accusation and demonstrate that it takes human rights seriously. Although these stakeholders could also have been embedded within the primary stakeholder map, they have instead been emphasised in a network of their own because of their specificity within the scope of this study. These stakeholders are primarily influenced by Qatar's own Workers Welfare Standards, established in 2014, as 'robust principles that ensure that every worker on FIFA World Cup Qatar 2022 projects receives the highest standards of health, safety, wellbeing, and security throughout their time with us' (Workers Welfare Standards, 2021).

The standards themselves are influenced by several different domestic and international stakeholders and collaborating partners, including Verité, an independent non-profit organisation that sheds light on labour rights violations in supply chains, the I.L.O., the Centre for Sport & Human Rights (CSHR), the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs (ADLSA), the National Human Rights Committee (NHRC), and finally, the Institute for Human Rights and Business (IHRB).

Figure 19: Qatar’s 2022 World Cup (Workers Welfare) Stakeholders

5.10 Individual Perceptions

The primary research obtained mixed results from the twenty-six interviewees concerning their perception of Qatar’s staging of the 2022 World Cup finals and whether the reforms would continue after the events. The perception of people on the reforms put in place by the government of Qatar has been illustrated in figure 20. The results show that 80% of the respondents agreed that

the reforms that were being put in place would continue after the 2022 games, while 20% disagreed. Disbeliefs included the idea that hosting such a mega-sporting event needs more reforms as the number of workers are unusually high, and human rights violations are more likely to happen within such a protracted timeframe. On the other hand, individuals who agreed with the effectiveness of reforms stated that Qatar's contract for a mega-sporting event needs to reflect human rights to the international world.

Individuals also noted that such a contract shows Qatar's positioning in the Middle East region; therefore, it needs to send a positive image to obtain other regional agreements in the future. This is highly compatible with the information presented in the literature review based on the explanation offered by Cotton and Weldon (2014, p. 7). The authors illustrate that Qatar has a high priority agenda of demonstrating to the world that it has great potential. Ideally, it is already being viewed as an economic power that is emerging in the world. In this regard, it is aiming to gain prominence both regionally and nationally. According to a Qatar government spokesman, the chance given to the country of hosting the mega-sporting event is a catalyst for positive change for the country in the Middle East region. This event will significantly improve the understanding between the countries that are within and beyond the region.

Figure 20: Perception of People on the Reforms Put in Place by the Government of Qatar

Respondents acknowledged that the country is putting measures in place to safeguard people's rights, especially immigrant workers. However, researchers believe that there is still a long way to go to ultimately call Qatar's reforms fully protective towards workers' rights, pointing out especially issues about the *Kafala* system, national trade unions, and migrant's rights (Graham, 2019, pp. 205-211). Therefore, this conforms to the information presented in the literature review that, when Qatar won the bid to host the 2022 World Cup, the outcry increased internationally on the rights of those involved in constructing the stadiums.

Other research conducted in Qatar was trying to assess the Qataris' attitudes and that of various expatriates concerning the staging of the FIFA 2022 World Cup by Qatar, and whether it could improve the conditions in Qatar and enhance the protection of human rights (Osman, 2017, p. 3). In Osman's study, a total number of 2,163 individuals were involved, all aged above 18 years. The study was trying to examine some of the changes that were taking place in society as the country was preparing for the World Cup events. In contrast with this present research that focuses on the event, rather than the changes in society outside the event, which Osman does, both studies show that Qatar's regulations and normative approaches changed towards a more democratic system capable of improving the living conditions of people (these normative approaches seen both internally and externally to the 2022 World Cup).

According to the Social Economic Survey Research Institute's senior research assistant, Buthaina Al Khelaifi, at the University of Qatar, the research indicated that 97% of the people of Qatar believe that the mega-sporting event will foster pride amongst the people of Qatar and among the residents and promote the country as a great multicultural destination (p. 4). The information presented in this research shows that Qatar has made and is still making several other signs of progress in protecting human rights as it prepares for the 2022 World Cup finals (Osman, 2017, p.

2). The research mentioned above was conducted jointly by reputable organisations that are internationally recognised. This involved Qatar University, the tourism department of Qatar, the Social Economic Survey Research Institute, Recreational and Sports Management, and two senior research officers from the University of Florida. All interviewed individuals believed that the mega-sporting events are meant to introduce the culture of protecting human rights worldwide. Therefore, Qatar ought not to be regarded as a country whose culture does not care about protecting human rights, as tourists are less inclined to tour the country if they fear their rights being violated. It is of major importance to Qatar to show the world as it improves the worker's conditions and creates a positive image. Also, Osman (2017) continues to illustrate that, from the research that was conducted, 94% of the individuals that responded indicated that the mega-sporting event held will mainly provide the residents with an in-depth knowledge concerning the various cultures within the communities as there are communities and people from different cultures.

5.11 Conclusion

This chapter focused on the thesis case study has highlighted some of the reforms that the government of Qatar has put in place to diminish the probability of human rights violations and increase workers' rights. Attention has been directed to the payment of the workers, working conditions, including the reduced number of working hours, the reforms of the *Kafala* system, accommodation, health, and safety. The results have also shown some of the measures that have been put in place and their effectiveness in ensuring that human rights are not violated. That includes compliance and audit, the welfare forum of the workers, a grievance hotline, contractor capacity building, construction welfare inspections, stakeholders' engagement, transparent public reporting, and continual development of procedures.

In sponsoring the development and insurance of human rights systems within mega-sporting events, the World Cup often plays an incredibly important and influential role. For example, as it has been previously suggested, the World Cup can help shed much-needed light on human rights issues within a certain country or jurisdiction. In other instances, mega-sporting events can help encourage new systems and frameworks of development and co-ordination that are more closely aligned with the values, norms, beliefs, principles, and traditions of contemporary society, and of ethical and sustainable interdependent growth (Heerdt, 2018). Within this framework of sustainable growth and human rights development, both FIFA and the Supreme Committee have played immensely valuable roles in ensuring multi-faceted forms of collaboration, information-sharing, and raising awareness (Duval & Heerdt, 2020). It is therefore essential for these organisations and institutions to continue to operate collaboratively in creating new and innovative systems wherein human rights are continuously prioritised alongside the facilitation of some of the world's largest sporting events.

All figures illustrated within this chapter have shown that respondents 'strongly agree' or 'agree' with a very high percentage: the lowest is 80% in agreement with Qatar's reforms capability to ensure human rights, and the highest was a complete agreement of 100% when it comes to the level of understanding on the effectiveness of the construction welfare inspections. This latter might be because inspections reports are publicly reported by the joint report of the Supreme Committee and the BWI (as we saw in this chapter, six inspections were carried out in 2019, where the findings were elaborated).

This chapter also shows that Qatar's changes are being made over a long period. After winning the right to host the 2022 World Cup in 2010, it was in 2013 that Qatar adopted a workers' charter, and in 2014 that the Supreme Committee established the Workers Welfare Standards.

Then, in 2016, Qatar changed the *Kafala* legislation into a new employment status called ‘contractual agreement’, however since the legislation still had restrictions on employees (such as a five-year contract term and restrictions on movement), Qatar reformed the system once more in 2018, to abolish the exit permit entirely, meaning that all construction workers can leave the country without the need for their employer’s permission.

This chapter shows how the other reforms came into place during the past ten years: the grievance hotline, welfare forums, inspections, four-tier auditing systems. These took place over a long time until 2020 (and more reforms may still follow until 2022). It is important to say that the progress is visible but represents a lengthy challenge for Qatar. This might be due to the significant implications that require the hosting of a mega-sporting event. However, it is essential to note that even if reforms are not perfectly developed, the mega-sporting event marks for Qatar the beginning of visible reforms that can be even more strongly developed post-2022, with a willing and committed government.

This chapter also shows Qatar’s steps in reforming the dialogue with the workers, the reforms and the regulations, and the efforts to conduct audits, monitoring, and reporting missions directly to the accommodation and work sites. It is also important to note that looking within the reforms, downsides are also visible, such as the fact that doctors are only present permanently when the accommodation or work sites include a minimum of 100 workers; otherwise, there are only first aid officers present. Another example is that when private contractors are breaching the laws and infringing human rights, they are removed from the contract and cannot participate in the mega-sporting event. Still, there are no legal procedures undertaken in court. As we can see from the literature, this continues to be an issue, and monitoring under the watchful eye of pressure groups and the press continues to ensure countries do more to address such issues (Tavakkoli,

2016; Hepburn, 2017). Thus, for every reform that Qatar is putting into place, it represents the start of potential growth in protecting human rights. Still, it does not represent a finalised regulation that protects workers' rights at the highest level. Finally, Qatar's 2022 World Cup stakeholders were examined and discussed.

The following section is the concluding chapter that allows for a brief thesis overview, findings, recommendations, and my original contribution to knowledge. I conclude with my contribution to meaning and human rights theory, including suggestions for future researchers' perspectives for the years to come.

Chapter 6: Conclusion and Recommendations

This chapter concludes the thesis and its findings. It presents an overview of the case study based on the evidence and offers recommendations to be presented to Qatar's Ministry of Labour after the thesis approval. In addition, this chapter identifies and explains Qatar's FIFA World Cup stakeholders, and lastly describes this thesis' contributions to knowledge and to literature, its limitations, and possible alternatives to how this research could have been done.

6.2 Overview

Within this thesis, I aimed to conceptualise the influence of mega-sporting events concerning international human rights. As the aim of this study is to critically evaluate the influence and pressure of hosting the 2022 World Cup in Qatar on respecting human rights, I intend to respond to the research question, as presented in the introduction and its detailed rationale within the methodology: 'How important and effective are some of the reforms that the government of Qatar is trying to put in place in ensuring that human rights are protected?' This comes with a sub-research question: 'Are the reforms translated into normative approaches, i.e., national laws, policies, legislations, strategies to ensure post-game compliance and post-2022 applicability?'

The three main objectives of this thesis, as detailed within the introduction and methodology chapters, were as follows:

1. Evaluate the policies and reforms of Qatar, both governmental and non-governmental, in protecting human rights.
2. Analyse the effectiveness of the measures put in place by Qatar to ensure that human rights are protected.

3. Evaluate people's perceptions on the importance and effectiveness of the reforms and their applicability after the 2022 World Cup finals and how others can embrace these best practices in the region.

This thesis is guided by one research question and one sub-research question, which are as follows:

- Research question: How important and effective are some of the reforms that the Government of Qatar is trying to put in place in ensuring that human rights are protected?
- Sub-research question: Are the reforms translated into normative approaches, i.e., national laws, policies, legislations, and strategies, to ensure post-game compliance and post-2022 applicability?

Since December 2010, when Qatar won the bid to host the 2022 FIFA World Cup, a set of allegations from the international press and NGOs, such as Amnesty International, attested that Qatar is infringing the human rights of workers at construction sites, especially their labour rights. The thesis has evaluated a positioning case of Qatar vis-à-vis its reforms and measures to protect the human rights of workers. This was made through critical discourse analysis (of Qatar's laws, policies, strategies, reforms, and normative approaches) and conducted interviews, leading to methodological triangulation of data.

The interview sampling consisted of twenty-six participants in the 2022 FIFA World Cup work plan (thirteen construction workers, eight public/governmental employees, and five private sector representatives). The findings are measured in percentages throughout the thesis, and they showed that respondents believed that specific measured reforms were enormously appreciated, usually in a 90-95% proportion. The interviews rated respondents' opinions on the level of Qatar's particular measures to protect human rights. The steps discussed included: the Workers' Welfare Forums, capacity-building exercises, inspections, public reporting/transparency, the grievance

hotline, and compliance and audit systems. The overall rating of the reforms to protect human rights was enormously appreciated, at 80% accuracy.

Additionally, respondents could also add comments allowing for qualitative analysis. The interviews show that respondents tended to comment more when something positive was mentioned. However, disbeliefs and challenges were discussed briefly, but not described in lengthy comments like the positive ones. This may be because of their steadfast belief in the positive effects of the reforms. Still, it could also show reluctance to freely discuss the challenges for fear of repercussion, even though I guaranteed anonymity. However, the findings illustrate a favourable opinion of Qatar's reforms. From the interviews alone, I can deduce that in the respondents' perception, Qatar's reforms can protect human rights or diminish the possibility of human rights abuses (with no overall rating measure rated at below 80%, and even one measure placed at 100% agreement).

Within the content analysis (described below in section 6.4 related to the study of the findings), I have seen that Qatar replaced the *Kafala* system in 2016, transforming it into a 'contractual agreement.' However, the legislation still had restrictions on employees, such as a five-year contract term and restrictions on movement. Two years later, in October 2018, Qatar abolished the exit permit entirely, meaning that all construction workers can leave the country without the employer's permission. Qatar's reforms may still have room for improvement. However, when we look at the past ten years, the country has shown only progress and no sign of regression. When measures were not fully responding to the workers' needs, the government did not hesitate to revise specific standards a second time, such as the measures under the *Kafala* system which were adjusted in 2016 and 2018.

Qatar introduced new measures to protect the human rights of workers, such as the Workers' Welfare Forums, capacity-building exercises, inspections, updating working and living conditions (including cooling technology and renovation of accommodations), reporting exercises, the grievance hotline, and compliance and audit systems including four-tier systems. I have also seen that Qatar's World Cup body, the Supreme Committee for Delivery and Legacy, published the 'Worker Welfare Standards' in 2014. This is a significant achievement as the standards are applicable to the country's construction workers. These were all detailed in chapter five, and the main conclusion is that each measure has positive aspects and challenges. Nevertheless, there is room for improvement, although the steps are seen as a 'first in Qatar's history regarding their treatment of construction workers (migrant workers)'. Some of the recommended improvements that can be deduced from this thesis are detailed below.

I have seen, for instance, that health measures have been put in place. Every accommodation/worksite with more than 100 workers has a permanent doctor available, together with a facility appropriately equipped to respond to medical emergencies. But, of course, the medical facility is not fully prepared to respond to chronic diseases and other health issues that need long-term treatment. For that, the workers need to be transported to a hospital, as the Workers' Charter stipulates. However, the medical facility responds to work emergencies such as injuries, fatigue, and so forth. Also, it is important to note that there is no permanent doctor in places with fewer than 100 workers, but there is a first aid officer.

6.3 Personal Limitations

This thesis is also unique because it comes from my perspective with a dual role: firstly, I am an employee responsible for change and reform measures regarding human rights within the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs of Qatar. Secondly, I am a

researcher with the role to uncover evidence of the functionality and meaning of those reforms, and their capacity to be resilient towards human rights beyond the FIFA World Cup held in 2022. While I had access to material such as statistical data, internal reports, internal monitoring mechanisms, and other information, including dialogue exchanges between policymakers and contractors for the FIFA World Cup preparations, the work as a researcher was not easy. As an employer in the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs of Qatar, the documents accessed in my capacity did not allow me to use most of them because of internal confidentiality regulations. Therefore, even if the documents were to be used for research purposes or reflected Qatar in a good light, the data could not be replicated in any form, not even as a reference. It is important to note that much more can be said, however, this issue has substantially limited my research capacity.

This thesis also has other limitations from my part, as mentioned within the introduction chapter, these include the fact that: firstly, pictures that were taken from secondary sources and not directly on-site (unfortunately, this section was carried out during the blockade on Qatar where access to sites was restricted and severe time constraints were imposed. Additionally, the work could not have been carried out recently due to the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown). Secondly, many laws, regulations, and monitoring reports need further analysis from a legal perspective. Thirdly, there are still a few months until the 2022 World Cup, and national authorities might still amend laws and regulations in Qatar. It would be interesting to do more research after the mega-sporting event to assess if the modifications remain in place after the 2022 World Cup (and, if not, to determine why). Changing the case study and the timeframe of this analysis could also change the outcome of the thesis. I believe that there are also a few actions that I could have done differently during the research phase. These could be considered as alternatives, such as extending the

conducted interviews outside Qatar to international experts, members of sport commissions, and even members from FIFA directly; and having a section on analysing reforms and regulations from a legal perspective, in discussion with a jurist/lawyer to give the thesis a different perspective.

As mentioned above, out of the twenty-six interviews conducted, eight were possible with government officials. With those eight government officials, semi-structured interviews were also conducted. In the methodology, I have explained that for confidentiality purposes, for employment purposes (as I am also employed at the Ministry with the same government officials), and in line with the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), those eight persons are referred to as Senior Government Officials 1, 2, [...] and 8. All of them have fictive attributes as following: Senior Government Official 1 - Policy Advisor, Senior Government Official 2 - Policy Counsellor, Senior Government Official 3 - Policy Associate, Senior Government Official 4 - Policy Assistant, Senior Government Official 5 - Policy Officer, Senior Government Official 6 - Policy Chief, Senior Government Official 7 - Policy Expert, Senior Government Official 8 - Policy Head.

I plan to use the findings of this thesis and present them to the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs, in a briefing session, including expressing the recommendations as a way forward for the Ministry's work for the years ahead. On the academic side, I plan on using parts of the thesis for publication, significantly to demonstrate the power of mega-sporting events in reforming a country's national and international actions towards the protection of human rights, and to prove that sometimes improving human rights regulations at national and international levels can come from a completely different context (non-political sphere of action), such as sporting leisure events.

6.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The uniqueness of this thesis lies in its timely opportunity to discuss the reforms regarding human rights protection towards the mega-sporting event in Qatar, the 2022 FIFA World Cup, ahead of the event, meaning that there is still time for improvements and a careful analysis of what has worked so far. Therefore, the academic research that I have conducted in the literature review on human rights in mega-sporting events is usually performed after such a mega-sporting event, aiming for other countries to absorb the lessons. However, in relation to events, each country, and region, is a different territory with specific contextual and administrative procedures. Therefore, knowledge sharing is crucial, but only if that knowledge has been correctly adapted into each country's national context.

I have presented the theory in the literature review that Qatar is aiming to benefit from being the regional sporting hub in the Middle East, bearing in mind that it has already successfully hosted several other mega-sporting events such as the FIFA U-20 World Cup, which was held in 1995; the Asian Games, which were held in 2006; the AFC Asian Cup, which was held in 2011; and the recent 2019 IAAF World Athletics Championships. All these combine with the Aspire program that Qatar has put in place, and the ownership of KAS. At the same time, Qatar will be able to secure and expand the influence it has on football all over the world, in terms of the country's ability to boost FIFA's image, to demonstrate its reliance on the international sport clubs, and to show its capacity to create a mega-sporting event. All these could only be successful if Qatar can ensure that human rights are respected, protected, and that the reforms are sustainable.

The literature-based space where studies of mega-sporting events are discussed in relation to human rights notions is relatively limited. As such, identifying and finding potentially diverse forms of literature for this study was an especially challenging task. Although this study's literature

review helped draw from a number of existing studies addressing some of the intricate notions attached to mega-sporting events in relation to human rights, the range and diversity of these studies was greatly limited. With that said, an important benefit associated with this study relates to how it could contribute to the literature, especially in terms of its contribution to the geopolitical elements of mega-sporting events in relation to human rights. For example, as it has been mentioned, the vast majority of the literature utilised aims to examine the relationship by way of evaluating specific countries that arguably already possess reputations for certain human rights abuses, namely China and Russia. Thus, most of the existing literature discussing how mega-sporting events can impact human rights does little to explore the relationship outside of some of these countries. In this regard, by exploring the above-mentioned research in relation to the state of Qatar, this research is not only helping to build a necessary component of the literature gap, but more importantly, is ensuring that dialogues can be held with regard to how notions of human rights are managed in relation to mega-sporting events within nations of very high human development.

Also, by exploring the research topic with regards to how it relates to Qatar and the 2022 World Cup, this research thesis' contribution can also be examined in terms of how it allows nations with somewhat limited experience in mega-sporting event management to develop these events more effectively without disregarding the need for applying human rights systems. Although countries like Russia and China have both been discussed throughout this thesis for their human rights abuses when managing separate mega-sporting events, both nations already have extensive experience with modern mega-sporting event developments, dating back decades (Müller, 2015). For a relatively new economic power such as Qatar, this research study helps address how initial experience with mega-sporting event development, especially in countries made up of

diverse and hierarchic economies, can be especially challenging, and can require an immense amount of continuous improvement and evaluation.

As many of the countries of the Arabian Gulf continue to further build on their roles within the world of global football and sport, the need for more effective forms of management and infrastructural development will remain immensely important. As has been suggested, most of these nations rely on particularly complex and intricate economic and financial systems which are mostly staffed and managed by migrants (Ramadan, 2015). Thus, by the availability of other studies, such nations can strive to become more active members of the global sport community without infringing on the rights of their migrant populations. Overall, the diverse implications associated with this research study are largely multi-faceted and can impact a wider array of knowledge-based spaces. The primary research goal of this study was to develop a closer understanding of Qatar's simultaneous experience with mega-sporting event management and human rights protections. The study addresses several economic, socio-cultural, and geopolitical frameworks that are rarely discussed within existing literature, and that is uniquely applicable to Qatar.

My contribution to original knowledge is that I have added to, and demonstrated how, the immense power of a mega-sporting event could influence internal and external efforts, meaning internal reforms and ratification of treaties, in favour of the progression of human rights. My unique contribution and position have allowed the exposure of my research in this area and helped change the country's labour laws. My role also gave me a prominent position to have my research considered by the authorities. It is important to note that Qatar is a Muslim country. Since the Asian Games in 2006, where some reforms were visible on human rights (and women's rights as pointed out by Foley, McGillivray, and McPherson in 2012), the organisation of the 2022 FIFA

World Cup goes beyond some minor reforms, as it also includes the ratification of the two international covenants on human rights. From the reforms, I can observe that the 2022 FIFA World Cup marks for Qatar a new change in policies, introducing new systems that can be seen as ‘a first’ in the history of Qatar’s international and national measures towards human rights. It may be that these changes are more profound compared to the Asian Games in 2006 because of the international pressure coming from FIFA, but also from NGOs, such as Amnesty International.

From all the above, and the critical analytical conclusion presented, this thesis concludes that Qatar's national measures and actions towards international human rights standards can diminish and limit human rights violations within the 2022 World Cup mega-sporting event, and even after the event, if those measures will be further improved and will show sustainability. It is important to note that Qatar's efforts have demonstrated only signs of progression; however, this was a prolonged process, over ten years. Therefore, it may be premature to anticipate if Qatar's measures will last post-2022 World Cup, but this leaves it open as a new potential research topic for the future. To conclude, that whilst I do believe Qatar firmly wish to influence their neighbours and believe ideologically they are doing the right thing, the pragmatism of running a mega-sporting event and having the world watching and judging has ensured they embraced the principles beyond tokenism and have radically changed laws, policies, and practices for migrant workers to ensure their human rights are met.

6.5 Recommendations

From the content analysis described above, I can deduce that Qatar has shown good progress on measures and reforms, advancing towards compliance with international human rights protections, but it still has amendments and steps to consider. Nevertheless, these measures can be summed up with appropriate recommendations, as follows:

- Qatar has made international progress towards compliance with human rights: Qatar ratified the two international human rights covenants (civil and political rights, and economic, social, and cultural rights) in 2018. However, Qatar approved the ICCPR with a provision on the recognition of trade unions. In 2017, Qatar introduced a legal protection of domestic workers' labour rights, including paid holidays and a limit to working hours. However, there are other downsides to consider. For example, there is no card system registering the working hours (in/out of work monitoring), and there is no monitoring if workers are asked to stay overtime. I stated in chapter five that the Supreme Committee is collaborating with NGOs representing trade unions (such as BWI, which is a Global Union Federation established in Argentina) in conducting on-site inspections to both accommodation and construction venues. However, when discussing the rights of workers, migrant workers have limited freedom of bargaining for their salaries; it is vital to acknowledge that the government initiated several measures, such as the number of working hours should be a maximum of 8 hours per day without a break, and 10 hours with break. The government also put forward a minimum salary threshold, to support workers' rights. Consequently, workers have not been able to negotiate for better payment terms. The workers have not been guaranteed work security and freedom of expression to negotiate a collective bargaining agreement to receive better pay. They fear losing their jobs and being deported to their countries of origin. For instance, the Sporting Chance Forum may be a suitable place for Qatar to participate. It is a pivotal platform to discuss solutions and vital human rights issues, especially as I.L.O. and OHCHR co-host the Forum as part of the United Nations (UN) compound in Geneva. The forum emphasises the 'Sporting Chance Principles,' which includes

the human rights of workers, including having a choice in decision-making processes, which should be guaranteed.

Recommendation 1: One of the thesis' recommendations would be to put a mechanism in place to give some freedom for collective bargaining of workers' salaries and even promotion/professional growth opportunities. If the laws of liberty for collective bargaining could be included within the clauses of the rules, then it would be better because the workers could have the rights to negotiate better pay than the low wages that the workers receive in Qatar. This links to the I.L.O.'s efforts in protecting workers' and migrants' rights. However, Qatar did not ratify the I.L.O. Convention on protecting the rights of all migrant workers, or the I.L.O. Safety and Health in Construction Convention.

- From this analysis, I can observe that there should be mechanisms to channel their grievances and any other complaint to the labour management without fearing victimisation. From the interviews that were conducted, despite the fact that 95% of the workers strongly agreed that the grievance hotline is an effective measure that has resulted in remarkable improvements in ensuring that workers' rights are safeguarded, 5% had issues concerning the fact that individuals had to register on the website before posting a query where their names appear. The concern is paramount; it is inclined to expose a worker to further intimidation if they raise a critical issue, especially of their employer.

Recommendation 2: Another proposition inferred from this thesis would be for the Supreme Committee, which is involved in ensuring that the worker's welfare standards are upheld, to develop several other ways that are more secure and confidential for the workers, for instance, to ensure the anonymity of the complaint that also leads to discretion and freedom from retaliation.

- Accommodation facilities for workers have been improved, as several contractors have built accommodations based on the standards that welfare associations had set. Consequently, accommodation facilities have been constructed near building sites to reduce the workers' time travelling to the places and thus create time for their leisure. However, this issue without appropriate inspections may also lead to workers being closely monitored or even called in by private contractors to work late hours.

Recommendation 3: A critical recommendation that I can make is for the workers to be asked in surveys what they prefer: accommodation close to the working site or further from the working site. This may leave out the speculations on the benefits and challenges of those accommodation sites.

- A list of contractors and subcontractors approved by the Supreme Committee is prepared to determine those still violating the laws established by the government of Qatar. Fair and transparent vetting is a necessary procedure that is essential for rehiring, because those subcontracting firms with poor track records will be avoided during the rehiring process. Contractors and sub-contractors that are found to violate human rights are blacklisted, meaning that they are immediately removed from their positions, and their contracts are cancelled without any right to a new agreement in the future. It is essential to say that this does not go through legal procedures to be resolved in court, and has only contractual consequences. The evidence I have found demonstrates that vetting fails to provide the essential information on the accountability concerning the present and past abuses made regarding human rights.

Recommendation 4: For full accountability to be provided, there is a need for the contractors who have been identified to be hiring subcontractors that abuse the workers' rights to also be penalised in courts (not only to be excluded from contracts).

- There is a need to amplify the voices of the workers. This will ensure that the workers' voices can inform several efforts of improvement and a system of four-tier auditing. This four-tier auditing can involve the MADLSA Audits, the Supreme Committee Audits, the Independent Monitor Audits, the BWI audits, and self-audits to amplify the voices of the workers. The workers' feedback should not be termed as being beyond the compliance activity or, instead, an action to be conducted once various emerging compliance issues are resolved. The workers' feedback should be regarded as a significant part of the compliance assessment process, supported by the workers' satisfaction. This will enable the Supreme Committee and the contractors and subcontractors to have a clear understanding of the issues affecting workers that matter most, need more attention and whether the workers can see any positive changes that the Supreme Committee makes and the contractors to their welfare. Secondly, there is a need to develop building management skills to ascertain that the managers involved with accommodation, supervisors, and Workers' Welfare Officers have sufficient skills to manage people, based on the mutual respect associated with managing a diverse workforce. For instance, management skills can be improved by developing modules on leadership and positive management skills. Thirdly, there is a need to ensure that the contractors run a suitable worker representation system that is highly effective, such as the Workers' Welfare Forums, as well as other mechanisms for airing grievances. From the analysis, the grievance mechanism used by the workers is suitable for the workers in raising their grievances. However, they do not have communication

loops to verify to what extent the immigrant workers feel that they have been given appropriate working conditions that operate fairly and drive some positive changes. Therefore, there is a need for grievance mechanisms to have efficient and effective communication loops for verification purposes. The Supreme Committee should ensure that the Workers' Welfare Forums are highly effective in ensuring that the workers present many quality and quantity issues.

Recommendation 5: I recommend increasing the number of external monitors in the Workers' Welfare Forums, evaluating the frequency of meetings, fair representation, and the skills of the elected Workers' Welfare Officer(s).

- To ensure that the workers well understand the rules and regulations, the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs requested the local embassies to translate the booklets into the native languages of the immigrant workers (the most prominently used are Bengali, Tamil, Urdu, Nepali, amongst others) so that the workers were able to understand their rights. However, some of the laws stipulated in these books may not be easy to understand and therefore need to be explained further by the public/private sector so that workers understand their rights as employees clearly. When the workers clearly understand their rights, they can champion their rights through various grievance mechanisms and take appropriate measures.

Recommendation 6: The Government, through the Ministry of Administrative Development, Labour, and Social Affairs, should be committed to offering some regular seminars with interpreters and translated documents to educate the workers concerning the rights of the workers that have been illustrated under the news labour laws of Qatar.

6.6 Future Research

There is a need for future researchers to research more mega-sporting events. Unfortunately, this research has only paid attention to Qatar in highlighting the reforms that have been put in place to ensure that the rights of the workers are not violated. However, violation of human rights is an issue that has been experienced across the world. Moreover, with increased pressure from the international community, many countries fighting to stage the mega-sporting events are forced to ensure that human rights are not violated as they prepare for the events.

There is less research conducted concerning the long-term impacts of a nation by staging the mega-sporting events. The few research projects that have been completed do not provide sufficient knowledge and evidence to show that these events indeed provide adequate positive economic effects that are long-lasting. Additionally, these studies centre their arguments on the host nation's expenditure and investments in preparing for the events, normally outweighing the intended benefits. They do not tackle the economy's structural constraints. Further research in this area is therefore essential for making policies.

I am planning on publishing my thesis. In addition to changing labour law policy in Qatar, I anticipate writing an early paper with my supervisors on Qatar's response to human rights abuses through the hosting of a mega-sporting event, ahead of the World Cup in 2022, and being able to use this to assist others in the region to develop policy and practice.

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List of Appendices

Appendix 1: Participant Information Sheet

Appendix 2: Research Information sheet

Appendix 3: Interview questions